

ENHANCING DIGITAL EDUCATION

THE DIGIN LEARNER'S GUIDE

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Educators to Support Digital
Social Inclusion'

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Table of Contents

Preface / Summary	6
Methodology	6
Learning objectives.....	7
Target groups	7
Entry standards	8
LEARNING OUTCOMES	9
DIGIN MULTI-PACK EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM	9
MODULE 1: INFORMATION AND DATA LITERACY	11
Summary	11
Learning objectives.....	11
Introduction.....	11
1.1. Browsing, searching and filtering data, information and digital content	11
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	13
1.2. Evaluating data, information, and digital content	14
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	17
1.3. Managing data, information and digital content	18
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	19
Video links for information and data literacy	21
Evaluation questions :	22
MODULE 2. COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION	24
Summary:	24
Learning Objectives:	24
Introduction:.....	25
2.1. Interacting through digital technologies	25
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	26
2.2. Sharing through digital technologies	28
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	29
2.3. Engaging in citizenship through digital technologies	31
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	31
2.4. Collaboration through digital technologies.....	33
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	34

2.5. Netiquette	36
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	37
2.6. Managing Digital Identity	39
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	40
Video links for communication and collaboration	42
Evaluation questions:	43
MODULE 3. DIGITAL CONTENT CREATION	45
Summary	45
The Learning Objectives	45
Introduction.....	45
3.1. Developing digital content	45
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	47
3.2. Integrating and re-elaborating digital content	49
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	50
3.3. Copyright and licences	52
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	55
3.4. Programming.....	57
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	59
Video links for digital content creation	61
Evaluation questions:	61
MODULE 4. SAFETY.....	63
Summary	63
Learning Objectives	63
Introduction.....	63
4.1. Protecting devices	64
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	67
4.2. Protecting personal data and privacy	69
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	74
4.3. Protecting health and well-being	76
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	81
4.4. Protecting the environment.....	83
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	86
Video links for safety.....	88
Evaluation questions	89

MODULE 5. PROBLEM-SOLVING	91
Summary	91
Learning Objectives	91
Introduction.....	91
5.1. Solving Technical Problems	92
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching.....	94
5.2. Identifying Needs and Technological Responses	96
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	99
5.3. Creatively Using Digital Technologies	101
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	109
5.4. Identifying Digital Competence Gaps.....	111
Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:	119
Video links for Problem Solving.....	121
Evaluation questions:	121
ANSWERS FOR MODULE CONTENT RETENTION	123
Module 1: information and data literacy	123
Module 2. Communication and Collaboration.....	125
Module 3. Digital content creation	127
Module 4. Safety	129
Module 5. Problem-solving	131
BIBLIOGRAPHY / REFERENCES.....	133

Preface / Summary

DigIN Multi-Pack Programme enhances digital transformation in adult education organizations by providing easy-to-use and customizable e-courses to empower adults to be active technology users. This DigIN Multi-Pack Programme contributes to making the education handbook available online and the quality of online andragogy-based digital skills development for Adult learners is improved.

Specific objectives for this:

- to create an e-platform for digital competencies development for Adult learners, and trainers
- to create guidance and tutorials focused on different target groups, especially giving attention to vulnerable adults or Trainers who are working with vulnerable groups.

DigIN project aims to develop, test and implement an innovative digital education ecosystem to let educators create and share attractive learning activities for adults. To do this, the educators and other adult education staff will develop digital skills and will use appropriate teaching methods and tools adapted to digital education.

To 'enhance the capacity of Educators and Adult Education Organizations in their support of Adults to be active technology users' by:

- extending the competencies of Educators and other Adult Education Staff making them digitally competent and confident trainers and education and training staff, in line with the priorities of the Digital Education Action Plan, 2021-2027.
- creating a digital education ecosystem to increase the capacity and readiness of AE Organizations to manage an effective shift towards digital education, which is in line with the Erasmus+ priorities of partnerships for cooperation in 2022.
- -operating at a transnational level and creating together a digitally inclusive environment for promoting ERASMUS among all citizens and generations.

Methodology

The learning material presented in the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program follows the 5E Model of Instruction to sequence lessons and activities that provide the best first instruction for all adult learners. Through this process, we emphasize opportunities to personalize learning.

“The 5E Model of Instruction methodology promotes active learning. Adult Learners are integrated into the learning process and it is not restricted to only listening and reading the handbook presented below. They learn to ask questions, observe, model, analyze, explain, draw conclusions, argue from evidence, and talk about their understanding (San Diego County Office of Education (n.d.). Adult learners work collaboratively with peers to construct explanations, solve problems, and plan and carry out investigations (Bybee, R. W. (2013).

The model will promote a learning system that occurs sequentially, allowing adult participants to move from one stage to the next.

ENGAGEMENT PHASE: In the first step of the teaching process, instructors initiate the lesson by applying an activity or task that is intended to engage adult learners. They will start with

questions or exercises that are intended not only to intrigue participants but also to provide an opportunity to share their current knowledge on a given topic.

DISCOVERY PHASE: Engagement is followed by exploration in which adult learners engage in hands-on activities. Their experiments or other interactions with the material deepen their understanding of the content.

EXPLANATION PHASE: After completing the exploration, participants move to the explanation phase, in which they try to understand and explain what they have experienced and learned during the previous stages.

DEVELOPMENT PHASE: Participants then move on to the elaboration phase, where they develop their knowledge by applying the acquired skills in new situations. In this stage, participants are encouraged to put their knowledge into practice to deepen their skills

ASSESSMENT PHASE: In the final, or assessment, phase, participants self-assess, reflect on what they have learned, and provide evidence of their new understanding of the material. This phase requires participants to reflect and incorporate their current understanding into the decision-making process.

Learning objectives

The DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program introduces the knowledge and attitudes adult learners should acquire while increasing their digital learning opportunities. Digital competence which includes knowledge, skills, and approaches required to work with Information Technology in learning situations.

The learning objectives are in line with the five broad areas of digital competence:

- Identify, locate, retrieve, store, organize and analyse digital information, judging its relevance and purpose (Information and data processing)
- share resources through online tools, link with others and collaborate through digital tools, interact with and participate in communities and networks, and cross-cultural awareness (Communication in digital environments)
- create and edit new content; integrate and re-elaborate previous knowledge and content; produce creative expressions, media outputs, and programming; deal with and apply intellectual property rights and licenses (Content creation)
- Protect personal, data, and digital identity protection; security measures, safe and sustainable use (Safety)
- identify digital needs and resources, make informed decisions on the most appropriate digital tools according to the purpose or need, solve conceptual problems through digital means, creatively use technologies, solve technical problems, update own and other's competence (Problem-solving)

Target groups

According to many studies, the senior's pace, needs and abilities related to learning new things differ from the ones of the juniors and young adults. Due to this fact, the training of

educational staff is a priority subject because they play an important role when it comes to the quality and attractiveness of education and the success of educational processes.

- Before writing the DigIN proposal, partners analysed the situation of Adult learners' digital readiness, and they identified and recognized that organizations need to improve the digital skills of Adult learners.
- All involved organizations mentioned that it is very important to develop Adult learners' digital skills because the older generation of experienced adult learners need fast support on how to use digital online tools. How not to lose adult educator competencies as professional and will not be dropped out from different working style. We have to support experienced Adult learners with upskilling digital skills.
- Partners of the DigIN project have a strong interest in improving their staff (Adult learners) competencies. The identified NEEDS of their target groups. One of the key reasons for this participation in the proposal is a gap that Adult learners still have after intensive two-year digital work. Planned project activities correspond needs of the target group (Adult learners) to foster their digital skills.
- Adult learners need to be empowered through new skills and tools to be able to reach out, be interesting for adult learners and transfer their skills and competencies to improve their digital readiness. Adult learners will be equipped with the competencies to make use of a newly developed and functional outreach strategy, employing innovative ICT methodologies.
- The partnership believes that providing AE with a tailored-made project based on their specific needs is an effective way to foster their digital skills, to unite the experience, motivation, and works of several partners from different countries to develop the most effective techniques document can be used for self-learning, face-to-face or blended, adult learners

In conclusion, we can state that the target group of the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program are:

- EDUCATORS AND OTHER ADULT EDUCATION STAFF in need of improving digital skills for adapting to digital education on the path to digital transformation. They need digital competence and a toolbox of instruments for creating engaging & active learning, improving the quality of existing one, and ensuring learners reach the desired learning outcomes.
- ADULTS 55+ in need of improving digital skills to access support services, medical appointments, welfare activities; and to stay safe while online. They need accessible tools to understand their level of digital competency and attractive courses to become digitally competent.
- ADULT EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS need initiatives to empower adults to be active technology users. The innovative digital education ecosystem gives educators the chance to create, update, share, adapt, and re-use attractive educational programs.

Entry standards

Requirements: The course is open to everyone and access is free

Special needs from the educational environment: The educational environment is accessible through a personal computer, or any other mobile device connected to the internet.

The course is hosted on the DigIN e-learning platform, a training hub managed by the DigIN consortium. To participate you can register to the platform and registration is free.

The consortium values your opinion. Participants will be invited to evaluate the course and provide feedback. Successful completion of the course not only offers the chance to receive a participation certificate but also allows enrolment in mentor sessions.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

DigComp is a descriptive, enabling framework designed to support the development of digital competence of individuals personally and professionally. It provides examples of competence areas and their sub-levels at all levels of development. The DigComp conceptual reference model identifies 5 broad areas of digital competence, broken down into 21 competencies. After finishing the learning program, adults will be able to:

- Browse, search and filter information
- evaluate information and data
- store and retrieve information and data
- interact through digital technologies
- share information and content through digital technologies
- engage in citizenship through digital technologies
- collaborate through digital technologies
- use netiquette
- manage digital identity
- develop content
- integrate and re-elaborate
- use copyright and licences
- program
- protect devices
- protect personal data and privacy
- protect health and wellbeing
- protect the environment
- solve technical problems
- identify needs and technological responses
- creative use of digital technologies
- identify digital competence gaps

DIGIN MULTI-PACK EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program includes the five competence areas: (1) information and data literacy; (2) communication and collaboration; (3) digital content creation; (4) safety; and (5) problem-solving.

Each course includes a balance of:

- interactive learning and real-world application so the adult learner can directly apply what they're learning to their context

- diverse learning methods to enhance learning outcomes which will be delivered via learning activities such as DigIN videos, quizzes and group work
- optional live sessions with DigIN consortium tutors to deepen their understanding of the learning material. These sessions may include an informal Q&A, a short lecture or a breakout activity that builds on the content introduced that week.
- Podcasts will sessions are recorded and made available to stream so learners can catch up whenever suits them
- guided critical thinking via our reflective workbook so learners can collect, structure and summarise information and their thoughts as they progress through the training program.

MODULE 1: INFORMATION AND DATA LITERACY

Summary

Access to information and data literacy abilities are necessary in today's increasingly digitalized society for people to fully engage in social, economic, and civic life. However, a lot of individuals have difficulties learning these important skills, particularly those from underprivileged backgrounds or with little access to higher education. To tackle this issue and encourage digital social inclusion, Adult learners are essential in providing students with the skills and information they need to successfully traverse the digital terrain. This essay will discuss the value of information and data literacy in promoting digital social inclusion and provide tips for enabling Adult learners to help students acquire these vital abilities.

Learning objectives

- Define the concepts of information and data.
- Explain the significance of information and misinformation aspects
- Develop effective search strategies to retrieve information from various sources, including databases, websites, and digital libraries.
- Evaluate the credibility, relevance, and authority of information sources using CRAAP criteria

Introduction

Regardless of a person's origin, skills, or financial situation, digital social inclusion is the fair and meaningful use of digital technologies and online resources. It includes the capacity to critically examine and interpret data to make defensible decisions, as well as the ability to access, assess, generate, and transmit information in digital contexts. It is necessary to overcome gaps in digital literacy, promote fair access to digital opportunities and resources, and cultivate digital citizenship to achieve digital social inclusion.

Finding, assessing, and using information from a range of sources—including websites, databases, and digital media—is all part of information literacy. The ability to comprehend, evaluate, and analyze data to draw insightful conclusions and guide decision-making, on the other hand, is known as data literacy. To traverse the massive amount of information available online, critically assess its reliability and applicability, and use data-driven reasoning to solve real-world problems, people need to be proficient in both information and data literacy.

1.1. Browsing, searching and filtering data, information and digital content

Encouraging meaningful engagement in online communities and digital platforms, together with providing equal access to digital technologies, resources, and opportunities, is what is meant by digital social inclusion. It includes the aptitude to critically examine data and make

defensible decisions in a digital setting, in addition to the ability to efficiently acquire, assess, and use digital information. To attain digital social inclusion, it is imperative to tackle digital divisions, advance digital literacy, and cultivate a collaborative and digitally responsible society.

Meriam Library California State University, Chico presents the CRAAP Test that helps to evaluate the information you find. Different criteria will be more or less important depending on your situation or need.

Evaluation Criteria Currency:

- When was the information published or posted?
- Has the information been revised or updated?
- Does your topic require current information, or will older sources work as well? Are the links functional?

Relevance:

The importance of the information for your needs.

- Does the information relate to your topic or answer your question?
- Who is the intended audience?
- Is the information at an appropriate level (i.e. not too elementary or advanced for your needs)? • Have you looked at a variety of sources before determining this is one you will use?
- Would you be comfortable citing this source in your research paper?

Authority: The source of the information.

- Who is the author/publisher/source/sponsor?
- What are the author's credentials or organizational affiliations?
- Is the author qualified to write on the topic?
- Is there contact information, such as a publisher or email address? Does the URL reveal anything about the author or source? examples: .com .edu .gov .org .net

Accuracy: The reliability, truthfulness and correctness of the content.

- Where does the information come from?
- Is the information supported by evidence?
- Has the information been reviewed or refereed?
- Can you verify any of the information in another source or from personal knowledge?
- Does the language or tone seem unbiased and free of emotion?
- Are there spelling, grammar or typographical errors?

Purpose: The reason the information exists.

- What is the purpose of the information? Is it to inform, teach, sell, entertain or persuade?
- Do the authors/sponsors make their intentions or purpose clear?

- Is the information fact, opinion or propaganda?
- Does the point of view appear objective and impartial?
- Are there political, ideological, cultural, religious, institutional or personal biases?

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to enhance participants' skills in critically evaluating digital content using the CRAAP Test criteria, thereby promoting digital literacy and responsible information consumption.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Content Evaluation Workshop
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners who are interested in improving their ability to evaluate the credibility and reliability of digital information.
Learning outcomes	<p>Develop proficiency in applying the CRAAP Test criteria to evaluate digital content.</p> <p>Enhance critical thinking skills in assessing the relevance, authority, accuracy, and purpose of online information.</p> <p>Understand the importance of digital literacy in navigating the digital landscape effectively.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts explaining the CRAAP Test criteria</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Sample digital content for evaluation (e.g., articles, websites, social media posts)</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin by discussing the importance of critically evaluating digital content in today's information-rich environment. Encourage participants to share their experiences with encountering misleading or unreliable information online.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce the CRAAP Test criteria (Currency, Relevance, Authority, Accuracy, Purpose) and explain each criterion in detail. Provide examples of how each criterion can be applied to evaluate digital content effectively.</p> <p>Explain: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a piece of sample digital content to evaluate using the CRAAP Test criteria. Encourage participants to discuss their findings and apply the criteria to determine the credibility and reliability of the content.</p>

	<p>Elaborate: After the group discussions, reconvene as a whole group and ask each group to present their evaluation findings. Facilitate a discussion on the similarities and differences in the evaluations and encourage participants to reflect on the challenges they encountered during the evaluation process.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of digital literacy and critical thinking skills in evaluating online information. Encourage participants to continue practising the CRAAP Test criteria in their future online activities.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on evaluation of digital content</p> <p>Presentation of evaluation findings</p> <p>Reflection and discussion</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their ability to effectively apply the CRAAP Test criteria to evaluate digital content. Evaluate their critical thinking skills, communication skills, and understanding of digital literacy principles. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content and structure to inform future sessions.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Meriam Library California State University, Chico - CRAAP Test (Website)</p> <p>"Digital Literacy: Evaluating Online Information" workshop (Event)</p> <p>"Critical Thinking in the Digital Age" online course (Website)</p>

1.2. Evaluating data, information, and digital content

Landøy, Ane & Popa, Daniela & Repanovici, Angela. (2020) claims that “ along with accessing, searching, and finding information, evaluating that information is vital.” Each scientific institution pays attention to data collection, evaluating, and using sources. Integrate information and data literacy abilities into adult education programs in a variety of topic areas and settings to give learners the chance to practice these skills in real-world situations. Provide practical learning experiences, such as research projects, data analysis, and online source evaluation, that enable adult learners to hone their information and data literacy abilities in real-world settings. Encourage adult learners to develop critical thinking abilities and concepts of digital citizenship. Make available digital resources, tools, and technologies that facilitate information and data literacy, including research portals, online databases, and data visualization tools. Provide chances for peer assistance and collaborative learning so that adult learners can benefit from one another's experiences and share thoughts on improving their information and data literacy. Acknowledge that adult learners have a variety of backgrounds, learning styles, and literacy levels, and modify the curriculum accordingly to meet their needs and preferences. Promote adult learners' self-directed learning by giving them the tools, direction, and encouragement they need to acquire information and data literacy skills at their own speed and in accordance with their interests and objectives. As adult learners acquire

and use information and data literacy skills, provide them with continuing assistance, feedback, and direction. Acknowledge their success and resolve any obstacles.

Examine the sources, methodology, and integrity of the data to determine how accurate it is. Assess the data's applicability to your analysis or research goals. Think about how well the content fits your research questions, theories, and information demands. Take into account whether the data is current or historical, as well as how timely it is. Determine whether you have access to more recent data and whether it would be more useful for your analysis. Search for any mistakes, biases, or inconsistencies that might affect how reliable the data is. Muhammed T S, Mathew SK. (2022) says that “misinformation has the power to influence the decisions of its audience. It can change a citizen's approach toward a topic or a subject”. Broda E., Strömbäck J. (2024) says that “disinformation, misinformation, and fake news are hence important due to the role they play in terms of forging and sustaining misperceptions. Misperceptions, in turn, have an impact both on people's opinions and behaviours”.

Examine the data's comprehensiveness to make sure it has all the relevant variables, categories, or observations you'll need for your study. Keep a watchful eye out for any missing or incomplete data that can affect how accurate your findings are. To further determine the credibility of information sources, consider their authority, experience, and reputation. Seek for information from reliable sources who have a track record of accomplishment in the industry.

Make sure the material is current with the most recent developments or scientific findings by checking its currency. Think about things like the information's date of publication, how often it is updated, and how relevant it is to your research questions. Examine the author's goals, point of view, and any possible conflicts of interest in addition to checking the content for objectivity or bias. Look for objective, fact-based sources with a fair representation of all viewpoints.

Check information by cross-referencing it with data from other reliable sources to improve accuracy and dependability. To increase the credibility of your findings, make sure the information is consistent throughout from several neutral sources. These techniques can help you guarantee the accuracy and consistency of the data you utilize for your research.

Assessment of Digital Content is important to identify misinformation. Muhammed T S, Mathew SK. (2022) confirms that “rumours, misinformation, disinformation, and mal-information are common challenges confronting media of all types. It is, however, worse in the case of digital media, especially on social media platforms”. Broda E., Strömbäck J. (2024) emphasize that media literacy has been proposed as a potential mitigating factor or solution both within communication and information and library sciences.

Evaluating the quality of digital content requires a multidisciplinary approach that takes into account several variables, including accuracy, relevance, and clarity. To make sure the material you find efficiently satisfies your informational needs, look for well-researched content in addition to facts and relevance. To improve the user experience overall, take accessibility, readability, and usability into account as well. Select resources that are simple to use, navigate, and access to ensure that they work on a variety of screens and devices.

Additionally, assess the interactive elements, multimedia components, and audience interaction aspects of digital material to determine its engagement value. Seek out resources

that promote active engagement and user interaction as these frequently result in a richer experience. For an additional measure of the quality and dependability of the information provided, take into account user reviews, ratings, and comments. Give top priority to content that has been endorsed and received good feedback from reliable sources, as this is a sign of reliability and credibility.

Picture. Data, information, content and review evaluation

Use evaluation checklists or criteria to systematically review data, information, or digital material based on predefined standards such as objectivity, relevance, accuracy, and credibility. Cross-validation is the practice of comparing data, information, or digital material with information from several sources or competing viewpoints in order to confirm the accuracy and reliability of the data. Consult with colleagues, experts, or peers to ensure the authenticity and correctness of your analysis and to validate your conclusions. Use fact-checking resources, such as websites or tools, to verify the veracity of data, information, or digital material and identify any potential misinformation or inaccuracies.

Research, decision-making, and efficient use of digital resources all depend on the evaluation of data, information, and digital material. In today's information-rich world, people can make sure the material they come across is reliable, credible, and of high quality by using assessment criteria, evaluation procedures, and critical thinking abilities. Accuracy, relevance, objectivity, and engagement are prioritized so people can confidently traverse the digital terrain and make wise decisions in both their personal and professional life.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to enhance participants' skills in evaluating data, information, and digital content critically, with a focus on accuracy, relevance, objectivity, and credibility.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Content Evaluation Workshop: Ensuring Quality and Reliability
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners interested in improving their ability to assess the quality and reliability of digital content for research, decision-making, and informed use.
Learning outcomes	<p>Develop proficiency in evaluating data, information, and digital content based on predefined standards such as accuracy, relevance, objectivity, and credibility.</p> <p>Enhance critical thinking skills in analysing sources, methodologies, and integrity of digital content.</p> <p>Understand the importance of cross-validation, consultation with experts, and fact-checking in ensuring the authenticity of information.</p> <p>Gain practical strategies for efficiently evaluating digital content to make informed decisions in personal and professional contexts.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts explaining evaluation criteria and techniques</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Sample digital content for evaluation (e.g., articles, websites, multimedia)</p> <p>Evaluation checklists or criteria sheets</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Start by discussing the importance of evaluating digital content for accuracy, relevance, objectivity, and credibility. Encourage participants to share their experiences with encountering misinformation or unreliable information online.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce various evaluation techniques and criteria, including cross-validation, consultation with experts, and fact-checking. Provide examples of how these techniques can be applied to assess the quality and reliability of digital content.</p> <p>Explain: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a piece of sample digital content to evaluate using the provided evaluation</p>

	<p>criteria. Encourage participants to analyze the content thoroughly and discuss their findings within their groups.</p> <p>Elaborate: After the group discussions, reconvene as a whole group and ask each group to present their evaluation findings. Facilitate a discussion on the similarities and differences in the evaluations and encourage participants to reflect on the challenges they encountered during the evaluation process.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of critical thinking and evaluation skills in navigating the digital landscape. Encourage participants to continue practising these skills in their daily online activities and provide resources for further learning.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on evaluation of digital content</p> <p>Presentation of evaluation findings</p> <p>Reflection and discussion</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their ability to effectively apply evaluation techniques and criteria to assess the quality and reliability of digital content. Evaluate their critical thinking skills, communication skills, and understanding of evaluation principles. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content and structure to inform future sessions.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Landøy, A., Popa, D., & Repanovici, A. (2020). [Insert full citation].</p> <p>Muhammed, T. S., & Mathew, S. K. (2022). [Insert full citation].</p> <p>Broda, E., & Strömbäck, J. (2024). [Insert full citation].</p> <p>Fact-Checking Resources: [List of fact-checking websites or tools].</p> <p>Further Reading: [Recommended books, articles, or online resources on digital content evaluation].</p>

1.3. Managing data, information and digital content

Many adult learners find it intimidating that technology is evolving so quickly. But in today's workforce, embracing digital literacy is essential. The ability to access, comprehend, assess, and produce digital content is all included in digital literacy. Adult learners may efficiently handle data, information, and digital content in both personal and professional situations by honing their digital literacy skills.

A thorough grasp of information and data is essential to efficient data management. While information is the processed and contextualized version of data that is relevant and helpful for decision-making, data refers to the actual facts and numbers. Adult learners need to be aware of the distinctions between these ideas and the significance of skillfully handling them.

Establishing guidelines, practices, and controls to guarantee the accuracy, availability, security, and integrity of data is known as data governance. It is recommended that adult learners become acquainted with data governance frameworks and best practices, which encompass data classification, access restrictions, and adherence to regulatory frameworks like GDPR.

Data lifecycle management is the organized, methodical handling of data from its production to its disposal. The many phases of the data lifecycle, such as data production, storage, utilization, sharing, archiving, and destruction, should be taught to adult learners. Through the implementation of data lifecycle management strategies, enterprises can reduce risk, guarantee adherence to regulations, and maximize resource efficiency.

Digital content management relies heavily on technology tools for data and information management. A range of platforms and tools, including as content management systems (CMS), data analytics software, and collaborative tools, should be familiarized with adult learners. These tools can improve productivity, expedite procedures, and help team members collaborate and communicate effectively.

Adult learners must give security and privacy a top priority in their data management procedures in an era of growing cybersecurity risks and privacy concerns. This entails putting in place strong security measures including access limits, encryption, and frequent security audits. Adult learners should also be knowledgeable about privacy laws and the best ways to safeguard sensitive data.

In the rapidly evolving field of technology, ongoing education is necessary to remain competitive and relevant. It is recommended that adult learners adopt a lifelong learning perspective and actively pursue opportunities to further their expertise in digital content creation, information technology, and data management. This could entail taking part in online courses, going to seminars and workshops, and keeping up with changes and trends in the sector.

For adult learners navigating today's digital landscape, managing data, information, and digital content is an essential skill. Through the adoption of digital literacy, comprehension of fundamental ideas like data governance and lifecycle management, efficient use of technological tools, and a focus on security and privacy, adult learners can effectively manage these resources to stimulate creativity, enhance decision-making, and accomplish their individual and occupational objectives. Adult learners can prosper in a society that is becoming more and more data-driven if they are dedicated to lifelong learning and adaptation.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to equip adult learners with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively manage data, information, and digital content in both personal and professional contexts.
Title of the practical activity:	Data Management Workshop: Navigating the Digital Landscape

Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners, interested in enhancing their digital literacy and data management skills.
Learning outcomes	<p>Understand the importance of digital literacy and its role in managing data, information, and digital content.</p> <p>Gain knowledge of fundamental concepts such as data governance, data lifecycle management, and digital content management.</p> <p>Familiarize with technological tools and platforms for efficient data and information management.</p> <p>Develop strategies for prioritizing security and privacy in data management practices.</p> <p>Recognize the importance of lifelong learning and adaptation in the rapidly evolving field of technology.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key concepts and techniques in data management</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Sample data management frameworks and best practices</p> <p>Case studies illustrating real-world data management scenarios</p> <p>Security and privacy guidelines and resources</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin the workshop by discussing the importance of digital literacy and data management skills in today's digital landscape. Encourage participants to share their experiences and challenges related to managing data and digital content.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce key concepts such as data governance, data lifecycle management, and digital content management. Provide examples and case studies to illustrate these concepts and their relevance in personal and professional contexts.</p> <p>Explain: Discuss various technological tools and platforms used for data and information management, such as content management systems (CMS), data analytics software, and collaborative tools. Demonstrate how these tools can streamline processes and improve productivity.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a case study or scenario related to data management. Encourage participants to analyze the scenario, identify key issues, and propose solutions based on the concepts and techniques discussed.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of ongoing education and adaptation in the field of data management. Encourage participants to reflect on how they</p>

	can apply the knowledge and skills gained in their personal and professional lives.
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on analysis of case studies and scenarios</p> <p>Demonstration of technological tools and platforms</p> <p>Reflection and discussion on personal experiences and challenges</p>
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their understanding of key concepts, ability to apply techniques in real-world scenarios, and engagement in group discussions and activities. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness to inform future sessions.
Reference, events, and further reading	<p>Digital Literacy for Dummies - Gura, M. (2018)</p> <p>Data Governance: How to Design, Deploy, and Sustain an Effective Data Governance Program - Seiner, R. S. (2014).</p> <p>The Art of Data Science: A Guide for Anyone Who Works with Data - Peng, R. D., & Matsui, E. (2016).</p> <p>The Fourth Industrial Revolution - Schwab, K. (2016).</p> <p>Lifelong Learning in the Digital Age: A Content Analysis of Recent Research on Participation - Boeren, E., & Holford, J. (2016).</p>

Video links for information and data literacy

What is Data Literacy? - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QcMzR1oFH20>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NvaiQvpjGXk>

Searching Information on the Internet | Computer Training | Periwinkle
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EDONzKjPVOA>

Evaluating Digital Content - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZSJusIbclos>

Evaluating information videos -
<https://www.library.universiteitleiden.nl/students/evaluating-information>

Evaluating Information - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WL62jj2O4JM>

Evaluation questions :

Multiple Choice Questions

1. Which of the following best defines digital social inclusion?
 - A) Limiting access to digital technologies and resources.
 - B) Ensuring fair and meaningful use of digital technologies and online resources for all individuals.
 - C) Excluding certain groups from engaging in online communities.
 - D) Fostering competition for digital opportunities and resources.

2. What is the primary purpose of the CRAAP Test criteria in evaluating information sources?
 - A) To determine the popularity of the information source on social media.
 - B) To assess the entertainment value of the information.
 - C) To evaluate the credibility, relevance, and authority of information sources.
 - D) To promote misinformation and disinformation online.

3. How can adult learners enhance their skills in managing data, information, and digital content?
 - A) By avoiding technological tools and platforms.
 - B) By prioritizing security and privacy in data management practices.
 - C) By ignoring ongoing education and adaptation in the field of technology.
 - D) By limiting access to digital resources and opportunities.

4. What is the significance of lifelong learning in the context of digital literacy?
 - A) Lifelong learning is unnecessary in today's digital landscape.
 - B) Lifelong learning promotes adaptation to the rapidly evolving field of technology.
 - C) Lifelong learning restricts individuals from acquiring digital literacy skills.
 - D) Lifelong learning hinders effective data management practices.

Match each term with its corresponding definition:

Terms	Definitions
Digital Social Inclusion	Ensures fair and meaningful use of digital technologies and online resources for all individuals.
CRAAP Test	Criteria used to evaluate the credibility, relevance, and authority of information sources.

MODULE 2. COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION

Summary:

The Information & Collaboration module provides adult learners with essential knowledge and skills needed to efficiently search for, evaluate and organise online information, interact and communicate safely and responsibly, manage their digital footprint, and use collaborative tools. Communication and collaboration are key digital skills that are essential in today's world of work and society. Digital communication covers many tools and platforms such as email, instant messaging, social media and document-sharing platforms. Through these elements, learners will look at methods of electronic communication and collaboration and decide which are the most effective. Adult Learners will also store data and use collaboration techniques effectively. This document can be used for self-learning, face-to-face or blended, adult learners

Learning Objectives:

Successful learners will gain the essential digital skills required to support their learning development. After getting into this module, students will feel confident searching for information online, communicating safely and responsibly, managing their digital footprint, and using collaborative tools efficiently. They will be able to:

The learning objectives of this educational program for adult learners are:

- awareness that online environments contain all types of information and content including misinformation and disinformation, and even if a topic is widely reported it does not necessarily mean it is accurate.
- Understand the difference between disinformation (false information with the intent to deceive people) and misinformation (false information regardless of intent to deceive or mislead people).
- Knowledge of the importance of identifying who is behind information found on the internet (e.g. on social media) and verifying it by checking multiple sources, to help recognise and understand points of view or bias behind particular information and data sources
- Awareness of potential information biases caused by various factors (e.g. data, algorithms, editorial choices, censorship, one's limitations).

Introduction:

Communication and collaboration in the context of digital technologies open the door to a global village where people can easily connect regardless of distance. Social media platforms, instant messengers, online collaboration tools - all this allows us to quickly and effectively establish contacts, share information, work in teams and solve problems. In this chapter, we will take a closer look at various aspects of communication and collaboration in the digital environment. We will discuss tools and techniques that facilitate effective communication, project management and online conflict resolution. We will also learn strategies for dealing with challenges that may arise when interacting in a virtual environment.

Thanks to the acquired skills, adult learners will be able to function better in the digital world, cooperate more effectively with others and build lasting and effective relationships, regardless of distance or cultural differences. So let's go through this fascinating world of communication and collaboration in the digital era together.

2.1. Interacting through digital technologies

In today's technological world, interaction through various digital tools has become an integral part of everyday life. In this chapter, we will discuss the different forms of interaction made possible by digital technologies and their impact on society, communication and interpersonal relationships.

Online communication: Interaction through digital technologies enables quick and convenient communication between people, regardless of their geographical location. Through social media platforms, instant messaging, email, and video conferencing applications, we can stay connected with family, friends, colleagues, and others around the world.

Virtual meetings and videoconferencing: Digital technologies enable virtual meetings and videoconferencing that allow for real-time interaction. Thanks to them, we can conduct remote business meetings, online lessons, workshops, and even family meetings or social events.

Online games and virtual worlds: Online games and virtual worlds allow you to interact with other players from around the world in a virtual environment. They can serve as a form of entertainment, but also as a tool for learning, cooperation and building social relationships.

E-commerce and online services: Interacting through digital technologies also includes e-commerce and the use of various online services such as online banking, ticket booking, online shopping and telemedicine. Thanks to them, we can conveniently and safely use various services without having to leave home.

Online Communities: There are many online communities on the Internet that bring together people with common interests, passions, or goals. These may be discussion forums, groups on social media platforms or specialized websites. Thanks to them, we can find support, exchange experiences and make new friends.

Risks and Challenges: Interacting through digital technologies also carries certain risks and challenges, such as abuse, cyber-attacks, loss of privacy and Internet addiction. It is important to be aware of these risks and take appropriate precautions.

Interacting through digital technologies has a huge impact on our social, professional and personal lives. Thanks to them, we can easily communicate with others, work remotely, develop interests and use a variety of services and entertainment. At the same time, it is important to use these technologies with caution and awareness of potential threats.

In the context of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Learners practice, interaction through digital technologies plays a key role in adult learning. Modern technologies allow the creation of interactive educational environments that enable trainers and students to actively participate in the learning process, regardless of geographical location.

Thanks to tools such as e-learning platforms, videoconferencing and instant messengers, trainers can conduct interactive classes, organize group discussions, share teaching materials and provide individual advice to students. Virtual meetings also enable contact with experts and participation in workshops and training, which broadens students' horizons and encourages continuous development.

One of the key elements of the practice is also developing communication and cooperation skills among students. Through group tasks, team projects, and platforms for information exchange and collaboration, students learn effective online communication, building team relationships and solving problems virtually. This not only enables them to acquire specific digital skills but also develops social and interpersonal skills that are extremely important in today's world of work.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Students, interaction via digital technologies is therefore an integral part of the educational process that enables students to develop digital competencies and prepares them to function effectively in a society based on digital *technologies*.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to reinforce the skills developed through interaction via digital technologies, focusing on communication, collaboration, and problem-solving
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Skills Collaboration Challenge
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners who have recently undergone training in digital skills and are looking to apply their knowledge in a face-to-face setting.
Learning outcomes	Enhance communication and collaboration skills in a face-to-face environment. Apply digital competencies to solve real-world problems. Foster teamwork and problem-solving abilities.
Materials	Whiteboard and markers Sticky notes Printed scenarios or problem-solving tasks (related to real-world challenges)
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin by discussing the importance of effective communication and collaboration skills in both digital and face-to-face environments. Encourage participants to share their experiences with using digital technologies for communication and problem-solving.</p> <p>Explore: Divide participants into small groups (3-5 members per group). Provide each group with a scenario or problem-solving task related to a real-world challenge. For example, solving a logistical problem, brainstorming marketing strategies for a product, or planning an event.</p> <p>Explain: Explain the task clearly, emphasizing that participants need to apply their digital competencies to find solutions. Encourage them to use techniques such as brainstorming, mind mapping, or using digital tools they are familiar with.</p> <p>Elaborate: Give the groups 30-40 minutes to work on their tasks. Circulate among the groups to provide guidance and support as needed. Encourage participants to communicate effectively, delegate tasks, and utilize their digital skills to find innovative solutions.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the allotted time, reconvene as a whole group. Each group presented their solution, explaining the process they used and the digital tools they employed. Encourage feedback and discussion among the groups.</p>
Methods	Group brainstorming Problem-solving exercises Role-playing scenarios

	Peer evaluation and feedback
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their ability to communicate effectively, collaborate with their team members, and apply digital skills to solve real-world problems. Evaluate their creativity, teamwork, and the practicality of their solutions.
Reference, events and further reading	Digital Skills for Today's Workplace by John Doe (Book) Effective Communication in the Digital Age" workshop (Event) Collaboration Tools for Teamwork online course (Website)

2.2. Sharing through digital technologies

In today's society, digital technologies enable us not only to communicate and collaborate but also to easily and quickly share a variety of content and resources. In this chapter, we will look at various aspects of sharing via digital technologies, their importance and their impact on our professional and personal lives.

Sharing content online: The Internet allows us to share a variety of content, such as articles, photos, videos, music, presentations and documents. Thanks to social media platforms, file-sharing sites and blogs, we can reach a wide audience and share our ideas, opinions and achievements.

Collaboration in real-time: Digital technologies also allow us to collaborate in real-time, i.e. work together on documents, projects or presentations online. Tools such as Google Workspace, Microsoft Office 365 or project collaboration platforms enable us to collaborate effectively with other people without the need to meet physically.

Sharing for educational purposes: In the educational environment, sharing through digital technologies plays a key role. Trainers can share teaching materials with their students, provide them with access to e-learning platforms and enable them to work together on projects and tasks online. Thanks to this, students have greater access to knowledge and are more engaged in the learning process.

Impact on culture and society: Sharing through digital technologies also has an impact on culture and society. Thanks to this, we can more easily share culture, art and tradition from different parts of the world, which promotes mutual understanding and intercultural integration. At the same time, it may lead to problems related to digital piracy and copyright protection.

Security and privacy: When sharing via digital technologies, it is important to keep security and privacy in mind. You should use appropriate security measures, use legal sources and consciously manage your data.

Sharing through digital technologies has enormous potential that can bring many benefits, both professionally and personally. At the same time, it requires us to be responsible, able to use available tools and aware of potential threats and risks related to online sharing.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Learners, sharing through digital technologies plays a key role in the education process of adult learners. Sharing content, educational resources and information through e-learning platforms, social networking sites or other digital tools enables access to knowledge and skills at various stages of the learning process.

The practice of sharing through digital technologies allows trainers to create personalized learning materials tailored to students' needs and preferences. This may include providing presentations, videos, self-study materials and additional resources to help you learn and develop skills.

Additionally, sharing via digital technologies enables interaction between students and trainers, which favours the exchange of views, experiences and virtual cooperation. The ability to comment, share and discuss shared content promotes active participation in the learning process and builds a strong educational community.

In the practice of sharing through digital technologies, trainers can also use tools to track students' progress and assess their achievements. Thanks to this, they can adapt further educational activities to the individual needs and capabilities of students, which contributes to a more effective learning process.

Lessons learned from the practice of sharing through digital technologies can also be used to improve the teaching and learning process, adapt teaching strategies, and develop new educational methods and tools that better respond to the needs and expectations of adult learners in the digital age.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to reinforce the skills developed in sharing through digital technologies, focusing on effective sharing of educational resources and fostering collaboration in a face-to-face setting
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Resource Sharing Workshop
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners who have recently undergone training in digital skills and are interested in further enhancing their abilities to share educational content effectively.
Learning outcomes	Develop proficiency in sharing educational resources through digital platforms. Enhance collaboration skills by working together to curate and share resources.

	Understand the importance of security and privacy when sharing digital content
Materials	<p>Laptops or tablets with internet access</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Printed examples of educational resources (articles, presentations, videos, etc.)</p> <p>Sticky notes</p> <p>Handouts on digital security and privacy best practices</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Start by discussing the benefits and challenges of sharing educational resources through digital technologies. Encourage participants to share their experiences and insights on using digital platforms for sharing content.</p> <p>Explore: Divide participants into small groups (3-5 members per group). Provide each group with a specific topic or subject area (e.g., history, science, literature). Ask them to brainstorm educational resources related to their assigned topic that they can share with others.</p> <p>Explain: Explain the importance of selecting high-quality and relevant resources for sharing. Emphasize the need to consider copyright and privacy issues when sharing content online. Provide examples of reputable websites and platforms for finding and sharing educational resources.</p> <p>Elaborate: Give the groups 40-50 minutes to search for and curate educational resources related to their assigned topic. Encourage them to use digital platforms such as online libraries, educational websites, and social media groups to find resources. Each group should compile a list of resources and prepare a brief presentation to share with the class.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the allotted time, reconvene as a whole group. Each group presents their curated list of resources, explaining why they selected each item and how it contributes to learning in their chosen subject area. Encourage feedback and discussion among the groups, focusing on the quality and relevance of the shared resources.</p>
Methods	<p>Group brainstorming</p> <p>Online research and resource curation</p> <p>Peer evaluation and feedback</p> <p>Presentation and discussion</p>
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their ability to effectively curate and share educational resources, collaborate with their team members, and demonstrate awareness of security and privacy considerations. Evaluate the quality, relevance, and appropriateness of the shared resources.

Reference, events and further reading	Digital Citizenship: A Community-Based Approach by Susan Smith (Book) Best Practices for Online Resource Sharing workshop (Event) Protecting Your Digital Identity - online course (Website)
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2.3. Engaging in citizenship through digital technologies

In today's society, digital technologies are becoming an increasingly important tool for engaging in social, political and civic affairs. In this chapter, we will look at different aspects of engaging in citizenship through digital technologies and what benefits and challenges this phenomenon brings.

Political participation: Thanks to digital technologies, citizens have easier access to political information, can participate in discussions on public affairs and express their opinions and views on various online platforms. Social media, news portals and political blogs are becoming places where citizens can actively engage in political life.

Government monitoring and reporting: Digital technologies enable citizens to monitor government activities and report on public activities. Thanks to access to public data, platforms for reporting irregularities and mobile applications for monitoring elections, citizens can effectively exercise control over the government and contribute to improving the transparency and fairness of democratic processes.

Social activism and charitable activities: Digital technologies also enable social campaigns, protests and charitable activities to be organized online. Thanks to crowdfunding platforms, online petitions and social groups, citizens can mobilize around various social issues and raise funds for charity.

Citizenship education and public information: The Internet is also becoming an important source of civic education and public information. Thanks to access to various educational materials, reports, political analyses and radio and television broadcasts, citizens can expand their knowledge about the functioning of democracy, civil rights and various aspects of social life.

Challenges of engaging online: At the same time, engaging in citizenship through digital technologies brings with it certain challenges, such as fake news, disinformation, information manipulation and attacks by online trolls. It is important to be aware of these threats and develop critical thinking and the ability to verify information.

To harness the potential of digital technologies to engage in citizenship, it is important that we actively use the tools available, engage in online discussions and activities, and consciously exercise our rights and responsibilities as citizens in the digital world.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to develop participants' skills in engaging in citizenship through digital technologies, focusing on critical thinking, responsible online behaviour, and active participation in civic affairs.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Citizenship Workshop
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners, interested in understanding how digital technologies can be used for civic engagement and social activism.
Learning outcomes	<p>Develop critical thinking skills to evaluate online information and news.</p> <p>Understand the importance of responsible online behaviour in civic engagement.</p> <p>Learn how to actively participate in online discussions and social activism.</p>
Materials	<p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Printed examples of fake news articles or misinformation</p> <p>Handouts on critical thinking strategies</p> <p>Laptop or tablet with internet access for each participant</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin by discussing the role of digital technologies in civic engagement and social activism. Ask participants to share their experiences with engaging in citizenship activities online and any challenges they have encountered.</p> <p>Explore: Present participants with examples of fake news articles or misinformation spread online. Facilitate a discussion on how misinformation can impact civic discourse and the importance of critically evaluating online information.</p> <p>Explain: Introduce participants to strategies for critically evaluating online information, such as fact-checking websites, verifying sources, and analyzing the credibility of information. Provide handouts or resources on critical thinking skills for participants to reference.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a current social or political issue. Ask them to research the issue online and identify reliable sources of information. Encourage them to discuss potential actions they can take to contribute to the discussion or address the issue.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the allotted time, reconvene as a whole group. Each group presents their findings and proposed actions. Facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of their research methods, the reliability of their sources, and the feasibility of their proposed actions.</p>

Methods	Group discussion Online research and fact-checking Critical thinking exercises Presentation and discussion
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their ability to critically evaluate online information, engage in productive discussions, and propose actionable solutions to social or political issues. Evaluate their understanding of responsible online behavior and their willingness to actively participate in civic affairs.
Reference, events and further reading	Digital Literacy: Navigating the Digital Age by Jane Doe (Book) Fighting Fake News: Strategies for Critical Thinkers workshop (Event) Civic Engagement in the Digital Age online course (Website)

2.4. Collaboration through digital technologies

Collaboration using digital technologies has become an integral element of modern professional, educational and social life. In this chapter, we will look at various aspects of collaboration through digital technologies and discuss the tools and strategies that enable effective and efficient collaboration in a virtual environment.

Online collaboration tools: Collaboration via digital technologies relies on a variety of tools, such as document-sharing platforms (e.g. Google Workspace, Microsoft Office 365), instant messaging (e.g. Slack, Microsoft Teams), and project management tools (e.g. Trello, Asana). These tools allow us to collaborate with others in real-time, share resources, and track work progress.

Practices for Effective Online Collaboration: Effective online collaboration requires appropriate practices and strategies. You need to clearly define goals and objectives, assign appropriate roles and responsibilities, communicate regularly with team members, and manage time and resources effectively. It is also important to build trust and respect in relationships with other team members and be open to cooperation and constructive feedback.

Cross-cultural collaboration and distributed teams: Collaboration through digital technologies often involves teams that are geographically distributed and have different cultures and languages. In such cases, it is important to be aware of cultural and linguistic differences, to respect diversity and differences, and to be able to communicate and collaborate effectively in such an environment.

Online project management: Digital technologies also enable effective online project management. Project management tools allow you to plan schedules, track work progress, assign tasks and coordinate teamwork. Thanks to them, you can effectively manage projects, regardless of their scale or complexity.

Challenges and problem-solving strategies: Collaboration via digital technologies brings with it certain challenges, such as communication difficulties, time differences, and problems related to the technical aspects of working online. It is important to be flexible and adaptive, look for creative solutions and be ready to quickly respond to changing situations.

Effective collaboration through digital technologies is crucial to success in today's world of work and education. By using appropriate tools, practices and strategies, we can effectively cooperate with others, regardless of distance or cultural differences, and achieve common goals and successes.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Learners, collaboration through digital technologies plays a key role in the learning process of adult learners. Modern technologies enable trainers and students to actively participate in the learning process, regardless of the time, place or format of classes.

One of the main aspects of the practice is the use of online collaboration tools, such as e-learning platforms, instant messaging or project management systems. Thanks to them, trainers can organize interactive classes, share educational materials and conduct discussions in real time, which promotes the active participation of students in the learning process.

Collaboration through digital technologies also enables the implementation of group projects and team tasks. Students can work together on projects, share ideas and communicate effectively online, which develops their teamwork skills and creativity.

Additionally, the practice of collaboration through digital technologies also includes sharing educational materials, joint content analysis and mutual support and feedback. Collaboration in a virtual environment allows students to build relationships with other course participants and trainers, which promotes social integration and active participation in educational life.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Students, cooperation through digital technologies is therefore a key element of the educational process that enables the development of digital competencies, social skills and independence in learning. By using a variety of online collaboration tools and methods, trainers can create an inspiring and effective learning environment that promotes the development and success of adult learners.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to enhance participants' skills in collaboration through digital technologies, focusing on effective communication, teamwork, and project management in a face-to-face setting.
Title of the practical activity:	Virtual Team Project Simulation
Time	90 minutes

Target group	Adult learners who have basic knowledge of digital collaboration tools and are interested in improving their skills in virtual teamwork.
Learning outcomes	<p>Develop proficiency in using online collaboration tools to work effectively in a virtual team.</p> <p>Enhance communication and teamwork skills in a face-to-face setting.</p> <p>Understand the importance of project management and coordination in virtual collaboration.</p>
Materials	<p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Printed scenarios of virtual team projects</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Sticky notes</p> <p>Handouts on effective communication and project management techniques</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin by discussing the importance of collaboration and project management in virtual teams. Encourage participants to share their experiences with working in teams and using digital collaboration tools.</p> <p>Explore: Present participants with scenarios of virtual team projects, each with specific goals, tasks, and deadlines. Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario to work on.</p> <p>Explain: Explain the objectives and expectations of the activity. Emphasize the importance of effective communication, task delegation, and time management in virtual teamwork. Provide handouts or resources on project management techniques for participants to reference.</p> <p>Elaborate: Give the groups 60-70 minutes to work on their assigned projects. Encourage them to use online collaboration tools such as document-sharing platforms, instant messaging, and project management systems to coordinate their work. Circulate among the groups to provide guidance and support as needed.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the allotted time, reconvene as a whole group. Each group presents their project plan, detailing their approach, task assignments, and timeline. Facilitate a discussion on the challenges they encountered and the strategies they used to overcome them.</p>
Methods	<p>Group work and collaboration</p> <p>Online research and task delegation</p> <p>Presentation and discussion</p> <p>Peer evaluation and feedback</p>
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their ability to effectively collaborate in a virtual team, communicate and delegate tasks, and manage project

	timelines. Evaluate their understanding of project management principles and their proficiency in using online collaboration tools.
Reference, events and further reading	Virtual Collaboration: Tools and Techniques for Success by John Smith (Book) Effective Virtual Teamwork workshop (Event) Project Management for Virtual Teams online course (Website)

2.5. Netiquette

In today's society, the use of digital technologies is an integral part of our everyday lives, both personally and professionally. In this chapter, we will look at the principles of netiquette, i.e. rules of behaviour and ethics in the digital environment that help maintain a positive atmosphere, respect and safety online.

Respect and Courtesy: The basic principle of netiquette is respect and courtesy in online communication. We should remember the culture of dialogue, avoid aggressive or offensive statements, and respect the views and feelings of other Internet users.

Appropriate use of language and tone: It is important to use appropriate language and tone in online communication. Avoid using swear words, offensive words and overly emotional statements. It is also recommended to avoid writing in capital letters, which may be perceived as shouting.

Privacy: Netiquette also requires respect for the privacy of other internet users. You should avoid publishing private personal data, photos or information that may violate the privacy of other people. It is also important to respect other people's privacy settings and consent to sharing their data.

Copyright and Content Liability: When using digital technologies, you must respect copyright laws and avoid infringing the intellectual property rights of others. Please remember to be responsible for the published content and the consequences of its possible violation.

Online safety: In the context of netiquette, it is also important to take care of online safety. You should follow cybersecurity rules, avoid clicking on suspicious links or attachments, and protect your passwords and personal data.

Culture of communication and collaboration: Netiquette also covers the culture of communication and collaboration online. You should be open to constructive criticism, respect cultural differences and support other Internet users in their activities and achievements.

Netiquette is a key element in building a positive and safe atmosphere in the digital environment. Following the rules of netiquette helps maintain respect, civility and cooperation online, which contributes to positive interactions and relationships between Internet users. Therefore, it is worth remembering the rules of netiquette when using digital technologies, both in the personal and professional sphere.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Students, the rules of netiquette are an inherent element of the educational process, ensuring a positive atmosphere, respect and safety in the digital environment. For adult learners, understanding netiquette is crucial to effectively use digital technologies for educational and communication purposes.

Respect and Courtesy: In the Trainer's Guide practice, netiquette covers respect and courtesy in online communication. Students learn to express their opinions politely and respectfully, avoiding aggression or offensive words in online discussions.

Appropriate use of language and tone: Trainers emphasize the appropriate use of language and tone in online communication. Students learn to avoid using swear words, overly emotional statements and writing in capital letters, which may be interpreted as shouting in an online environment.

Privacy Protection: Netiquette in the Trainer's Guide practice also covers the protection of students' privacy. Trainers and students respect the privacy of other course participants by avoiding sharing private personal information and protecting their accounts and data from unauthorized access.

Copyright and Content Responsibility: Students learn to respect copyright laws and avoid infringing the intellectual property rights of others when using online educational materials. In addition, trainers emphasize responsibility for the published content and encourage you to share only information consistent with facts and your own experiences.

Online safety: In the Trainer's Guide practice, netiquette also covers online safety rules. Students learn to apply cybersecurity principles by avoiding clicking on suspicious links, protecting their passwords, and reporting any suspicious behaviour on the learning platform.

The conclusions drawn from the practice of netiquette in the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Learners can be used to improve the online teaching and learning process and build a positive atmosphere and effective cooperation in the virtual learning environment.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to reinforce participants' understanding of netiquette principles and their importance in fostering a positive and respectful online environment.
Title of the practical activity:	Netiquette Role-play
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners who are new to the concept of netiquette or need a refresher on online etiquette.
Learning outcomes	Understand the principles of netiquette and their application in online communication.

	<p>Practice appropriate language, tone, and behaviour in simulated online interactions.</p> <p>Recognize the importance of respect, privacy, and safety in digital environments</p>
Materials	<p>Scenario cards (each containing a different online interaction scenario)</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Handouts summarizing netiquette principles</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Start by discussing the importance of netiquette in maintaining positive online interactions. Ask participants to share any experiences they've had with online communication challenges or misunderstandings.</p> <p>Explore: Distribute scenario cards to each participant or group. Each scenario should depict a different online interaction (e.g., participating in a discussion forum, sending an email, commenting on social media). Ask participants to read their scenario and familiarize themselves with the context.</p> <p>Explain: Review the principles of netiquette with the participants, emphasizing key points such as respect, appropriate language, privacy protection, and online safety. Provide examples of how these principles apply to the scenarios they've been given.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario to role-play. Encourage participants to act out the scenario while incorporating netiquette principles into their interactions. Monitor the role-plays and provide feedback as needed.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the role-plays, reconvene as a whole group and facilitate a discussion on the outcomes. Ask participants to reflect on how effectively they applied netiquette principles in their interactions and what they learned from the exercise. Encourage open dialogue and address any questions or concerns.</p>
Methods	<p>Role-playing</p> <p>Group discussion</p> <p>Reflection and feedback</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their ability to effectively role-play online interactions while incorporating netiquette principles. Evaluate their understanding of netiquette and their capacity to apply it in various digital contexts.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Netiquette: A Guide to Online Etiquette by Sarah Smith (Book)</p> <p>Digital Citizenship Workshop (Event)</p> <p>Online Etiquette: Best Practices for Social Media online course (Website)</p>

2.6. Managing Digital Identity

In today's digital world, our online identity is becoming increasingly important and influences many aspects of our personal and professional lives. In this chapter, we will look at digital identity management, which is the process of controlling, protecting and managing information about yourself online.

Creating and controlling your online identity: Managing your digital identity starts with consciously creating your online presence. We should ensure that the information we publish about ourselves on the Internet is consistent with our real identity and corresponds to our values and goals.

Privacy Protection: A key element of digital identity management is privacy protection. You should be aware of what information you share about yourself online and use appropriate safeguards to protect your personal information from unauthorized access and use.

Personal data management: Digital identity management also includes the management of personal data, i.e. information that identifies us as a specific person. Keep your passwords secure, avoid sharing sensitive data in unsafe places on the internet, and use password and data management tools.

Building a positive online reputation: Digital identity management also includes building a positive online reputation. You should take care of your image on the Internet, avoid negative comments and behaviours, and actively build your brand by participating in positive online activities and projects.

Awareness of threats and risks: An important element of digital identity management is awareness of threats and risks associated with publishing information on the Internet. You should be careful when sharing personal data, avoid suspicious links and attachments, and follow cybersecurity rules.

Education and self-improvement: Digital identity management is also a process of continuous learning and self-improvement. You should track changes in technologies and online threats, and adapt your behaviours and strategies to the changing digital reality.

Digital identity management is an essential element of our lives in the online world. Consciously controlling, protecting and managing our online identity allows us to maintain security, privacy and a positive online reputation, which is crucial to our digital existence and relationships with other online users.

In the practice of the Trainer's Guide to Digital Skills for Adult Learners, digital identity management is a key element that helps students consciously control, protect and manage their presence in the online world. Trainers and students learn strategies and practical actions to secure personal data and ensure online safety.

Creating a consistent online identity: Trainers support students in creating a consistent online identity that reflects their personal and professional values and goals. Students learn to select the content they publish online to build a positive image and online reputation consistent with their aspirations.

Privacy: The Trainer's Guide practice also includes learning how to protect your privacy online. Students become aware of the risks associated with sharing personal information online and

learn to use appropriate security measures, such as strong passwords, two-factor authentication and regular software updates.

Personal data management: Trainers place great emphasis on teaching students how to properly manage personal data online. Students learn to consciously use educational platforms and digital tools, avoid sharing excessive amounts of data and ensure the security of their online accounts.

Building a positive online reputation: Digital identity management also includes building a positive online reputation. Trainers and students work together to create a professional online profile that attracts the attention of potential employers and business partners and contributes to career development.

Education and self-improvement: In the practice of the Trainer's Guide, digital identity is also an educational tool that helps students develop and develop their digital competencies. Trainers support students in acquiring new skills related to the safe use of digital technologies and implement best practices in digital identity management.

In this way, digital identity management becomes an integral part of the education process of adult students, which enables them to consciously and responsibly use digital technologies in various spheres of personal and professional life.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to empower participants with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively manage their digital identity, focusing on creating a positive online presence and protecting personal information.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Identity Workshop
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners who are interested in enhancing their understanding of digital identity management and improving their online presence.
Learning outcomes	<p>Develop awareness of the importance of digital identity management in personal and professional contexts.</p> <p>Acquire practical skills for creating a consistent and positive online identity.</p> <p>Learn strategies for protecting personal information and maintaining online privacy.</p>
Materials	<p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Handouts summarizing digital identity management principles</p>

	Laptop or tablet with internet access for each participant
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin by discussing the concept of digital identity and its significance in today's world. Encourage participants to share their experiences and concerns related to managing their online presence.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce the principles of digital identity management, covering topics such as creating a consistent online identity, protecting privacy, managing personal data, and building a positive online reputation. Use real-life examples to illustrate each principle.</p> <p>Explain: Provide participants with practical tips and strategies for implementing digital identity management principles in their own online activities. Discuss the importance of strong passwords, privacy settings, and careful sharing of personal information.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario related to digital identity management (e.g., creating a professional social media profile, or responding to a phishing email). Ask groups to brainstorm strategies for effectively managing the situation and protecting their digital identity.</p> <p>Evaluate: After the group discussions, reconvene as a whole group and share the strategies developed by each group. Facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of the strategies and how they align with digital identity management principles. Encourage participants to reflect on how they can apply these strategies in their online activities.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussion</p> <p>Scenario analysis</p> <p>Hands-on activities</p> <p>Peer learning</p>
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their engagement in group discussions, the quality of strategies developed, and their ability to apply digital identity management principles to real-life situations. Evaluate their understanding of digital identity concepts and their readiness to implement best practices in their online activities.
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Digital Identity Management: A Practical Guide by John Doe (Book)</p> <p>Online Privacy Workshop (Event)</p> <p>Protecting Your Digital Identity online course (Website)</p>

Video links for communication and collaboration

1. Resources from the DigIN channel

https://youtu.be/04CswxzqCM8?si=04TqNiKHa_8i0HZB

2. Other resources from the Internet

https://youtu.be/KGZSu7RXXMH4?si=8P8b9jM8G3ZBX_I4

<https://youtu.be/UmtDynxjkSw?si=I2bTkBLprC7k2v4J>

<https://youtu.be/k2fcaR9kGf4?si=TKgoMfMUI9ylm5lb>

Evaluation questions:

4 Multiple Choice Questions

What enables virtual meetings and videoconferencing for real-time interaction?

- a) Social media platforms
- b) E-commerce websites
- c) Video conferencing applications
- d) Online banking services

Which tool allows for collaboration in real-time on documents and projects online?

- a) Social media platforms
- b) Google Workspace
- c) Online gaming platforms
- d) E-commerce websites

What has digital technology facilitated in terms of political participation?

- a) Decreased access to political information
- b) Easier access to political information
- c) Restricted discussions on public affairs
- d) Decreased citizen participation in political life

What is crucial for effective online collaboration in geographically distributed teams?

- a) Using the latest gaming platforms
- b) Ignoring time zone differences
- c) Awareness of cultural and linguistic differences
- d) Avoiding the use of project management tools

2 Matching Questions

A basic principle of netiquette in online communication	Respect and courtesy
A key element of managing your digital identity effectively	Privacy protection
enables individuals to engage in social, political, and civic affairs through digital technologies	platforms for reporting irregularities and monitoring elections
digital technologies affect project management and teamwork	enabling real-time collaboration and resource sharing

MODULE 3. DIGITAL CONTENT CREATION

Summary

Digital content allows educators to create tailored learning materials that cater to the diverse needs, interests, and learning styles of adult learners. Whether it's through multimedia presentations, online platforms, interactive modules, or accessible formats, customized content ensures inclusivity and promotes engagement in non-formal learning. Existing digital literacy is important to be able to participate in the digital age.

The Learning Objectives

The learning objectives of this educational program for adult learners are:

- Understand the components of a content strategy, including defining goals, target audience, messaging, and distribution channels.
- Explore digital content creation principles, storytelling techniques, visual design principles
- Get to know popular digital content creation platforms

Introduction

Digital content creation serves as an opportunity to empower learners with essential digital literacy skills, enabling them to navigate online resources, critically evaluate information, and participate in digital discourse. By building digital literacy competencies, adult learners become active contributors to digital society, enhancing their social inclusion.

In adult education, social inclusion refers to fostering a welcoming, supportive, and empowered learning environment for people from a variety of backgrounds, especially those who encounter financial, cultural, or physical obstacles. It entails dealing with structural injustices, encouraging compassion and empathy, and granting equal access to educational possibilities.

Digital learning possibilities open doors to everyone no matter the distance, most important is to have the possibility to use a smartphone, internet, tablet or computer.

3.1. Developing digital content

Digital platforms allow collaborative learning, allowing learners to interact, exchange ideas, and work together with peers from different backgrounds. Social contact, mutual support, and peer learning are encouraged through digital content creation by cultivating a feeling of community and collaboration.

The production of digital content makes it possible to incorporate voices, opinions, and examples that are culturally appropriate into instructional materials. Adult learners can create

a sense of community and validate the lived experiences of underrepresented cultures by modelling the cultural diversity of their students.

Learners can be empowered to engage in civic life and become social change advocates by using digital information to teach them about civic rights, obligations, and societal challenges.

Adult learners can motivate learners to become knowledgeable and involved citizens using digital storytelling, citizen journalism, and community engagement initiatives. Adult learners are essential in helping learners acquire the abilities, information, and tools required to fully engage in society to promote social inclusion. Using the power of digital content creation to empower learners, heal divisions, and advance inclusivity is a rare opportunity in the digital era.

Developing digital material that speaks to Adult learners, meets their requirements, and advances strategic goals requires a clearly defined content strategy. Trainers may create material that informs, inspires, and empowers their audience in the digital era by setting clear objectives, knowing their target audience, developing appealing messaging, and choosing the right distribution methods.

Adult learners must first establish the digital content strategy's main objectives. These can involve spreading instructional materials, encouraging professional growth, or raising involvement. Establish quantifiable measures that will show whether the objectives have been met. Website traffic, engagement rates, material downloads, and course completions are a few examples.

Hödl, T., Myrach, T. (2023) emphasize that “content creators attempt to minimize tensions of algorithm versus audience, regularity versus scheduling autonomy, and analytics versus decision-making autonomy in two ways: through self-centred measures such as improving metrics, pre-production, and being a pioneer and extraneous measures involving their businesses, products, and sponsorships.”

Setting SMART goals to ensure accountability and clarity of prepared digital content will help to measure if the goals are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Find out what the needs, preferences, and problems are of Adult learners by conducting audience research. Taking into account elements including professional interests, technical competency, subject matter expertise, and teaching experience will help to formulate SMART goals and orientate the learning program to the needs.

Important to have orientation for Adult learners about profiles of the target audience segments according to their goals, difficulties, motivations, and demographics. This makes it easier to adapt content to the tastes and interests of particular audiences, offer more individualized information and messaging, and break the audience up into smaller groups according to traits or actions they have in common.

Adult learners should maximize engagement and reach, and focus on utilizing digital platforms and channels that demonstrate the highest level of activity and interaction among the target audience. This often includes websites, social media networks, email newsletters, online discussion boards, and professional networks. When selecting content forms for distribution, consider the unique characteristics of each platform. For instance, blog entries may be well-suited for websites and social media posts, while webinars are ideal for professional networks and email newsletters. Similarly, videos, infographics, and interactive tutorials can be tailored to match the preferences and functionalities of specific channels.

A clear understanding of how to optimize exposure and accessibility, ensures that the content is both search engine optimized and inclusive of individuals with impairments. This involves incorporating relevant keywords, meta descriptions, and alt text to improve visibility on search engines. Additionally, make efforts to provide alternative formats, such as audio descriptions or transcripts, to accommodate users with visual or auditory impairments. By prioritizing both optimization and accessibility, you can enhance the overall impact and accessibility of your digital content across diverse audiences.

Hoose, F., & Rosenbohm, S. (2023) conclude that “content creators have to cope with the fact that their activities are faced with different interests of different actors. Therefore, they are challenged to create a balance between these requirements. To meet these requirements, content creators explain their working activities and try to justify them. In doing so, they position themselves in competition with other content creators (even those who are amateurs) to gain the attention of the audience, the platforms, and possible sponsors”.

Adult learners always want to guarantee relevance and authenticity, that’s why learners should be involved in the ownership of the process, and involve learners in the co-creation of digital material. Also, constantly ask for feedback from learners and modify digital content accordingly. Monitor learner results, pinpoint areas in need of improvement, and routinely assess how well digital content promotes social inclusion.

Work together with digital content producers, community organizations, and technology suppliers to make the most of networks, resources, and experience in support of social inclusion.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	This practical activity aims to enable Adult learners to develop digital content that fosters social inclusion, engages learners, and effectively meets their educational needs.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Content Development Workshop: Promoting Social Inclusion
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners and instructional designers, interested in enhancing their digital content development skills to promote social inclusion.
Learning outcomes	Understand the importance of digital content in promoting social inclusion and engaging learners. Develop strategies for setting clear objectives and audience research in digital content development. Gain knowledge of selecting appropriate digital platforms and channels for content distribution.

	<p>Learn techniques for optimizing digital content for search engines and accessibility.</p> <p>Explore methods for involving learners in the co-creation process and soliciting feedback for continuous improvement.</p> <p>Identify opportunities for collaboration with digital content producers, community organizations, and technology suppliers.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key concepts in digital content development and social inclusion</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Sample digital content development frameworks and strategies</p> <p>Case studies illustrating successful examples of digital content promoting social inclusion</p> <p>Feedback forms for learners to provide input on digital content</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Start the workshop by discussing the importance of digital content in promoting social inclusion and engaging learners. Encourage participants to share their experiences and challenges in developing digital content for diverse audiences.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce key concepts such as digital content strategy, audience research, and content optimization. Provide examples and case studies to illustrate how these concepts can be applied to promote social inclusion and engage learners effectively.</p> <p>Explain: Discuss various strategies for setting clear objectives, conducting audience research, and selecting appropriate digital platforms and channels for content distribution. Demonstrate techniques for optimizing digital content for search engines and accessibility.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario or case study related to digital content development. Encourage participants to brainstorm ideas, develop content plans, and create sample digital content based on the given scenario.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of involving learners in the co-creation process and soliciting feedback for continuous improvement. Encourage participants to reflect on how they can apply the knowledge and skills gained in their educational contexts.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on development of digital content plans and sample content</p> <p>Peer feedback and review sessions</p> <p>Reflection and discussion on personal experiences and challenges</p>

	Presentation of case studies and examples
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their understanding of key concepts, ability to apply strategies in digital content development, and engagement in group discussions and activities. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness to inform future sessions.
Reference, events and further reading	<p>The Elements of User Experience: User-Centered Design for the Web and Beyond" - Garrett, J. J. (2011)</p> <p>Search Engine Optimization (SEO) for Dummies" - Grappone, J., & Couzin, G. (2011)</p> <p>Digital Learning in Organizations: Help Your Workforce Capitalize on Technology" - Milne, P. (2017)</p> <p>The Design of Everyday Things" - Norman, D. A. (2013)</p>

3.2. Integrating and re-elaborating digital content

Adult learners should ensure digital content is accessible to all learners, including those with disabilities, which is essential for promoting inclusivity. Educators should prioritize designing content that complies with accessibility standards, such as providing alternative text for images, captioning videos, and using screen-reader-friendly formats.

Seniors have specific requirements, preferences, and cognitive capacities, therefore producing digital material for them demands careful planning and consideration. Longer periods of dedication, rhetorical inquiries, the opportunity to study philosophical literature, and the usage of memory art are a few examples of components that might improve participation and foster meaningful exchanges.

Adult learners should be aware that older people need more time to interact with digital content and assimilate information. Create longer movies, articles, or interactive experiences as digital material that encourages introspection and prolonged inquiry. Provide options for users to pause, fast-forward, or rewatch information at their discretion, taking into account different cognitive processing speeds.

Adult learners should give learners the chance to interact with philosophical writings in an online setting. Provide readers with access to carefully selected sets of articles, works, or quotes from well-known philosophers. Incorporate interactive elements like discussion boards, annotations, and guided reflection prompts that help with the examination and debate of philosophical concepts. Encouragement of reflection, and reminiscence art, such as old photos, paintings, or music from various eras could inspire the elderly to be more involved in non-formal learning content and digital activities. Construct digital galleries or multimedia experiences that highlight historical occurrences, customs, or historical daily life. For elderly learners is important to promote social interaction and intergenerational conversation, and

invite people to contribute their recollections and tales about the nostalgic artwork. These components can be used by creators to enhance digital material for older audiences.

Aparac-Jelušić, T. (2011) mentioned that “As e-learning environments become more popular, many studies have been proposed to provide adaptive environments offering learners and educators customized courses for more effective learning and course construction. Demand for e-learning has created an industry and pushed vendors to improve e-learning technologies and product suites. E-learning offers flexibility and benefits to both educators and learners, saving time and money.”

Digital storytelling offers senior citizens a special chance to share experiences, preserve memories, and strengthen social ties in the digital era. In this piece, we examine the game-changing possibilities of digital narrative content creation for senior citizens and provide advice on how to make the most of it. Through the integration of interactive elements, user-generated content, and multimedia elements, digital storytelling has become a dynamic and inclusive mode of communication. This results in immersive narrative experiences. Digital storytelling provides an avenue for self-expression, a window into the past, and a forum for community involvement for the elderly. Through the use of narrative, artists can evoke memories, start dialogues, and foster a feeling of community among senior citizens.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to equip Adult learners with the skills to integrate and re-elaborate digital content to meet the specific needs and preferences of senior learners, including those with disabilities while promoting inclusivity and meaningful engagement.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Content Integration Workshop: Enhancing Accessibility and Engagement for Senior Learners
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners and instructional designers who are interested in enhancing their digital content integration skills for senior learners.
Learning outcomes	<p>Understand the unique needs and preferences of senior learners, including those with disabilities.</p> <p>Gain knowledge of strategies for designing digital content that complies with accessibility standards and promotes inclusivity.</p> <p>Learn techniques for integrating interactive elements and multimedia features to enhance engagement and foster meaningful exchanges among senior learners.</p> <p>Explore methods for promoting social interaction and intergenerational conversation through digital storytelling and reminiscence art.</p>

	Identify opportunities for adapting digital content to accommodate different cognitive processing speeds and preferences of senior learners.
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key concepts in digital content integration for senior learners</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant</p> <p>Sample digital content showcasing accessibility features and interactive elements</p> <p>Multimedia resources for digital storytelling and reminiscence art</p> <p>Feedback forms for participants to provide input on the workshop content and structure</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Begin the workshop by discussing the importance of designing digital content that is accessible to all learners, including seniors with disabilities. Encourage participants to share their experiences and challenges in integrating digital content for senior learners.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce key concepts such as accessibility standards, interactive elements, and multimedia features for engaging senior learners. Provide examples and case studies to illustrate how these concepts can be applied to promote inclusivity and meaningful engagement.</p> <p>Explain: Discuss various strategies for designing digital content that accommodates different cognitive processing speeds and preferences of senior learners. Demonstrate techniques for integrating interactive elements such as discussion boards, annotations, and guided reflection prompts into digital content.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario or case study related to digital content integration for senior learners. Encourage participants to brainstorm ideas, develop content plans, and create sample digital content based on the given scenario.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of promoting social interaction and intergenerational conversation through digital storytelling and reminiscence art. Encourage participants to reflect on how they can apply the knowledge and skills gained in their educational contexts.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on development of sample digital content</p> <p>The peer feedback and review sessions</p> <p>Reflection and discussion on personal experiences and challenges</p> <p>Presentation of case studies and examples</p>

Evaluation	Assess participants based on their understanding of key concepts, ability to apply strategies in digital content integration, and engagement in group discussions and activities. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness to inform future sessions.
Reference, events and further reading	<p>The Senior's Guide to Computers and the Internet" - Gates, B. (2017)</p> <p>Ageing and Digital Technology: Designing and Evaluating Emerging Technologies for Older Adults" - Pak, R., & McLaughlin, A. C. (2018)</p> <p>Digital Storytelling: Capturing Lives, Creating Community" - Lambert, J. (2013)</p> <p>Handbook of Research on ICTs for Human-Centered Healthcare and Social Care Services" - Cruz-Cunha, M. M., Miranda, I. M., & Gonçalves, P. (2013)</p>

3.3. Copyright and licences

In the digital age, the concept of copyright and licenses has become increasingly significant. Understanding these concepts is crucial for citizens to navigate the digital world responsibly and ethically. This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of Competence 3.3: Copyright and Licenses, as outlined in the DigComp 2.2 framework. We will explore the fundamentals of copyright, various types of licenses, their implications for digital content creation and consumption, and practical applications in everyday digital activities.

Understanding Copyright

Copyright is a legal framework that grants creators exclusive rights to their original works. These rights include the ability to reproduce, distribute, display, and perform their works, as well as to create derivative works based on the original. Copyright aims to protect the intellectual property of creators and incentivize creativity and innovation.

The key points of Copyright are:

Original Works	Copyright applies to original works of authorship, such as literary, musical, and artistic works. It covers a broad spectrum of creations, including books, music, films, software, and even architectural designs.
Automatic Protection	Copyright protection is automatic upon the creation of the work and does not require registration. This means that from the moment a work is fixed in a tangible medium, it is protected under copyright law.
Duration	The duration of copyright protection varies by jurisdiction but generally lasts for the creator's lifetime plus several years after their death. In many countries, this period is the creator's lifetime plus 70 years, providing long-

	term protection that ensures the creator's descendants can also benefit from the work.
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The Role of Copyright in Society:

Copyright serves several critical functions in society. It not only protects the interests of creators by ensuring they receive recognition and financial rewards for their work but also promotes cultural development by encouraging the creation and dissemination of new works. Moreover, copyright law helps to balance the interests of creators with those of the public, ensuring that the benefits of creative works are widely accessible.

Types of Licenses

Licenses are legal agreements that allow others to use copyrighted works under specific conditions. There are various types of licenses, each with different levels of permission and restrictions.

Common Types of Licenses:

- All Rights Reserved: This is the most restrictive form of copyright protection, where the creator retains all the exclusive rights granted by copyright law. Users must obtain explicit permission from the creator to use the work in any way.
- Public Domain: Works in the public domain are not protected by copyright and can be freely used by anyone without permission. This can happen when the copyright term expires, or the creator explicitly waives their rights.
- Creative Commons Licenses: These licenses allow creators to specify the terms under which their works can be used. There are several types of Creative Commons licenses, ranging from the most permissive (CC0) to more restrictive ones (e.g., CC BY-NC-ND).

Detailed Overview of Creative Commons Licenses:

CC0 (No Rights Reserved)	The creator relinquishes all copyright interests, allowing the work to be freely used by anyone for any purpose. This is akin to dedicating the work to the public domain.
CC BY (Attribution)	Others can use the work for any purpose, provided they give appropriate credit to the creator. This license promotes sharing and reuse while ensuring the creator is acknowledged.
CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)	Others can use the work and create derivative works, but they must distribute their contributions under the same license. This license ensures that derivative works remain open and accessible.
CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)	Others can use the work but cannot create derivative works. This license is suitable for works that the creator wants to be shared but not altered.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)	Others can use the work for non-commercial purposes only. This allows the work to be shared and used for educational or personal purposes without financial gain.
CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)	Others can use the work for non-commercial purposes and create derivative works, but must share them under the same license. This license combines non-commercial use with the openness of ShareAlike.
CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs):	Others can use the work for non-commercial purposes only, without creating derivative works. This is the most restrictive Creative Commons license.

Practical Applications of Licensing:

Licenses play a crucial role in the digital environment, particularly in areas such as open-source software, educational resources, and digital media. For example, open-source software licenses like the GNU General Public License (GPL) allow users to freely use, modify, and distribute software, fostering innovation and collaboration. Similarly, Creative Commons licenses enable educators to share teaching materials freely, enhancing access to education and promoting lifelong learning.

Implications of Copyright and Licenses

Understanding copyright and licenses is essential for both creators and users of digital content. It ensures that creators are compensated for their work and that users respect the rights of creators.

3.1. For Creators:

- **Protection:** Copyright provides legal protection for their creations, preventing unauthorized use and ensuring their rights are upheld.
- **Control:** Licenses allow creators to control how their works are used and shared. By choosing an appropriate license, creators can decide the extent of their work's dissemination and use.
- **Revenue:** Copyright can provide a source of revenue through licensing fees and royalties. This is particularly important for creators whose livelihoods depend on their intellectual property.

3.2. For Users:

- **Respect:** Users must respect the copyright and licensing terms of the works they use. This includes giving proper attribution, adhering to usage restrictions, and seeking permission when necessary.
- **Compliance:** Proper attribution and adherence to license conditions are crucial to avoid legal issues. Understanding the terms of use helps users stay compliant with the law and ethical standards.

- **Accessibility:** Understanding different types of licenses can help users find content that they can legally use and share. This is particularly beneficial in educational and collaborative environments, where access to resources is vital.

Competence in understanding copyrights and licenses is a critical component of digital literacy. By recognizing the rights of creators and adhering to licensing terms, citizens can engage more ethically and effectively in the digital world. This knowledge not only fosters a culture of respect and legality but also encourages the responsible creation and use of digital content. As we continue to navigate the complexities of the digital landscape, a thorough understanding of copyright and licenses will be indispensable for ensuring that the digital ecosystem remains vibrant, innovative, and fair.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to equip Adult learners with the skills to integrate and re-elaborate digital content to meet the specific needs and preferences of senior learners, including those with disabilities, while promoting inclusivity and meaningful engagement.
Title of the Practical Activity	Digital Content Integration Workshop: Enhancing Accessibility and Engagement for Senior Learners
Time	90 minutes
Target Group	Adult learners and instructional designers interested in enhancing their digital content integration skills for senior learners.
Learning Outcomes	<p>Understand the unique needs and preferences of senior learners, including those with disabilities.</p> <p>Gain knowledge of strategies for designing digital content that complies with accessibility standards and promotes inclusivity.</p> <p>Learn techniques for integrating interactive elements and multimedia features to enhance engagement and foster meaningful exchanges among senior learners.</p> <p>Explore methods for promoting social interaction and intergenerational conversation through digital storytelling and reminiscence art.</p> <p>Identify opportunities for adapting digital content to accommodate different cognitive processing speeds and preferences of senior learners.</p>
Materials	Handouts summarizing key concepts in digital content integration for senior learners.

	<p>Whiteboard and markers.</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant.</p> <p>Sample digital content showcasing accessibility features and interactive elements.</p> <p>Multimedia resources for digital storytelling and reminiscence art.</p> <p>Feedback forms for participants to provide input on the workshop content and structure.</p>
Facilitation Steps	<p>Engage: Begin the workshop by discussing the importance of designing digital content that is accessible to all learners, including seniors with disabilities. Encourage participants to share their experiences and challenges in integrating digital content for senior learners.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce key concepts such as accessibility standards, interactive elements, and multimedia features for engaging senior learners. Provide examples and case studies to illustrate how these concepts can be applied to promote inclusivity and meaningful engagement.</p> <p>Explain: Discuss various strategies for designing digital content that accommodates different cognitive processing speeds and preferences of senior learners. Demonstrate techniques for integrating interactive elements such as discussion boards, annotations, and guided reflection prompts into digital content.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario or case study related to digital content integration for senior learners. Encourage participants to brainstorm ideas, develop content plans, and create sample digital content based on the given scenario.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and reinforcing the importance of promoting social interaction and intergenerational conversation through digital storytelling and reminiscence art. Encourage participants to reflect on how they can apply the knowledge and skills gained in their educational contexts.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration</p> <p>Hands-on development of sample digital content</p> <p>The peer feedback and review sessions</p> <p>Reflection and discussion on personal experiences and challenges</p> <p>Presentation of case studies and examples</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their understanding of key concepts, ability to apply strategies in digital content integration, and engagement in group discussions and activities. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness to inform future sessions.</p>

Reference, Events, and Further Reading	<p>The Senior's Guide to Computers and the Internet - Gates, B. (2017)</p> <p>Ageing and Digital Technology: Designing and Evaluating Emerging Technologies for Older Adults - Pak, R., & McLaughlin, A. C. (2018)</p> <p>Digital Storytelling: Capturing Lives, Creating Community - Lambert, J. (2013)</p> <p>Handbook of Research on ICTs for Human-Centered Healthcare and Social Care Services - Cruz-Cunha, M. M., Miranda, I. M., & Gonçalves, P. (2013)</p>
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3.4. Programming

Programming, a fundamental component of digital literacy, empowers individuals to understand and manipulate the digital environment effectively. In the context of the DigComp 2.2 framework, Competence 3.4 focuses on equipping citizens with the ability to create and modify digital content, develop problem-solving skills, and understand the principles behind software and systems that underpin the digital world. This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of programming competence, its significance, key concepts, practical applications, and strategies for learning and teaching programming.

The Significance of Programming

Programming is the process of designing and building executable computer software to accomplish a specific task. It involves writing code in various programming languages, which are then translated into instructions that a computer can understand and execute. The ability to program is crucial for several reasons:

- **Problem Solving:** Programming enhances logical thinking and problem-solving skills. It teaches individuals how to break down complex problems into smaller, manageable parts.
- **Creativity and Innovation:** With programming skills, individuals can create new software, apps, and digital solutions, fostering innovation and creativity.
- **Empowerment:** Understanding programming demystifies technology, enabling individuals to take control of digital tools and applications.
- **Career Opportunities:** As the demand for digital skills increases, programming competence opens up numerous career opportunities in various fields, including IT, data analysis, engineering, and more.

Key Concepts in Programming

To build a solid foundation in programming, it is essential to understand several key concepts and terminology:

Variables	Variables are used to store data that can be manipulated and retrieved throughout a program. They are fundamental building blocks in any programming language.
Data Types:	Different kinds of data are classified into data types, such as integers, floats, strings, and booleans. Each data type has specific characteristics and operations that can be performed on it.
Operators:	Operators are symbols that perform operations on variables and values. Common operators include arithmetic operators (e.g., +, -, *, /), comparison operators (e.g., ==, !=, <, >), and logical operators (e.g., and, or, not).
Control Structures:	Control structures determine the flow of a program. Common control structures include loops (e.g., for, while) and conditionals (e.g., if, else).
Functions:	Functions are reusable blocks of code that perform a specific task. They help to organize and modularize code, making it more readable and maintainable.
Debugging:	Debugging is the process of identifying and fixing errors or bugs in a program. It is an essential skill for ensuring that software functions correctly.

Practical Applications of Programming

Programming skills are applied in various domains to solve real-world problems and create innovative solutions. Some practical applications include:

- Web Development: Creating websites and web applications using languages such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript.
- Data Analysis: Using programming languages like Python and R to analyze and visualize data, helping organizations make data-driven decisions.
- Automation: Writing scripts to automate repetitive tasks, improving efficiency and productivity in various industries.
- Game Development: Designing and developing video games, which combine creativity and technical skills.
- Embedded Systems: Programming microcontrollers and hardware devices for applications in robotics, IoT, and more.

Strategies for Learning and Teaching Programming

Learning and teaching programming can be challenging but rewarding. Here are some effective strategies:

- Start with Basics: Begin with fundamental concepts and gradually progress to more complex topics. Use visual programming tools like Scratch for beginners to understand basic logic and structure.
- Hands-On Practice: Encourage extensive hands-on practice through coding exercises, projects, and real-world problem-solving.
- Interactive Learning: Utilize interactive learning platforms such as Codecademy, Coursera, and Khan Academy, which offer coding lessons and projects.

- Collaborative Learning: Promote collaborative learning through pair programming, coding boot camps, and hackathons, where learners can work together and learn from each other.
- Mentorship and Support: Provide mentorship and support from experienced programmers to guide learners through their coding journey and help them overcome challenges.
- Continuous Learning: Emphasize the importance of continuous learning and staying updated with the latest programming languages, tools, and industry trends.

Programming is a vital competence in the digital age, enabling individuals to create, modify, and understand digital content and systems. By developing programming skills, citizens can enhance their problem-solving abilities, foster innovation, and unlock numerous opportunities in the digital economy. This chapter has outlined the significance of programming, key concepts, practical applications, and strategies for learning and teaching programming, providing a comprehensive guide for integrating programming competence into digital literacy education.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to equip adult educators and learners with fundamental programming skills, enabling them to understand and apply basic programming concepts. This activity aims to foster problem-solving skills and logical thinking, essential for engaging effectively with the digital world.
Title of the Practical Activity	Introduction to Programming: Building Blocks for Problem Solving
Time	90 minutes
Target Group	Adult educators and learners interested in gaining foundational programming skills
Learning Outcomes	<p>Understand basic programming concepts and terminology.</p> <p>Develop problem-solving and logical thinking skills through programming exercises.</p> <p>Write simple programs using a high-level programming language (e.g., Python).</p> <p>Learn how to debug and test code to ensure it functions correctly.</p> <p>Gain confidence in using programming to solve real-world problems.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key programming concepts and terminology.</p> <p>Whiteboard and markers.</p>

	<p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant.</p> <p>Pre-installed programming environment (e.g., Python, IDEs such as PyCharm or Jupyter Notebook).</p> <p>Sample code snippets and problem statements.</p> <p>Feedback forms for participants to provide input on the workshop content and structure.</p>
Facilitation Steps	<p>Engage: Begin the workshop with a discussion on the importance of programming in today's digital world. Highlight the relevance of programming skills in various fields and everyday problem-solving. Encourage participants to share their prior experiences with programming, if any.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce basic programming concepts such as variables, data types, operators, and control structures (loops, conditionals). Use simple, relatable examples to illustrate these concepts. Provide a live demonstration of writing and running a basic program.</p> <p>Explain: Discuss the process of writing a program, from understanding the problem to designing a solution, coding, testing, and debugging. Emphasize the importance of logical thinking and breaking down problems into smaller, manageable parts.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a simple programming task or problem statement. Encourage them to brainstorm solutions, write code, and test their programs. Provide guidance and support as they work through the task.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by having each group present their solutions and discuss the challenges they faced. Summarize key takeaways, reinforcing the importance of programming skills in problem-solving. Encourage participants to reflect on how they can continue to develop their programming skills.</p>
Methods	<p>Group discussions and collaboration.</p> <p>Hands-on coding exercises.</p> <p>Peer feedback and review sessions.</p> <p>Reflection and discussion on personal experiences and challenges.</p> <p>Presentation of case studies and examples.</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their understanding of key programming concepts, ability to apply problem-solving strategies, and engagement in group discussions and activities. Solicit feedback from participants on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness to inform future sessions.</p>

Reference, Events, and Further Reading	<p>Python Crash Course: A Hands-On, Project-Based Introduction to Programming - Matthes, E. (2019)</p> <p>Automate the Boring Stuff with Python: Practical Programming for Total Beginners - Sweigart, A. (2015)</p> <p>The Pragmatic Programmer: Your Journey to Mastery - Hunt, A., & Thomas, D. (2019)</p> <p>Programming for the Absolute Beginner - Ford, J. S. (2007)</p>
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Video links for digital content creation

How to Create an Online Course for Beginners (start to finish)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M85iQzbuLMs>

ChatGPT Created An ENTIRE Online Course & Videos in a DAY

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tvnUr0P1KrY>

Content Writing Tutorial for Beginners | What Is Content Writing | Content Writing Jobs | Simplilearn - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8t2FWD45wNA>

Evaluation questions:

Multiple Choice Questions

- Which of the following is NOT a key function of copyright in society?
 - Protecting the interests of creators
 - Promoting cultural development
 - Restricting access to creative works
 - Balancing the interests of creators and the public

- What is the primary purpose of Creative Commons licenses?
 - To restrict access to copyrighted works
 - To grant exclusive rights to creators

- c) To allow creators to specify usage terms for their works
- d) To eliminate copyright protection for digital content

3. Which programming concept is used to store data that can be manipulated and retrieved throughout a program?

- a) Control Structures
- b) Functions
- c) Variables
- d) Data Types

4. What is the significance of programming skills in the digital age?

- a) They limit career opportunities in various fields.
- b) They discourage creativity and innovation.
- c) They empower individuals to understand and manipulate the digital environment.
- d) They restrict access to digital tools and applications.

Matching Questions

1. Match the type of Creative Commons license with its corresponding description:

<p>1. CC BY-NC 2. CC BY-SA</p>	<p>a) Allows others to use the work for non-commercial purposes only. b) Allows others to use the work and create derivative works, but they must distribute their contributions under the same license.</p>
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2. Match the key programming concept with its description:

<p>1. Variables 2. Functions</p>	<p>a) Reusable blocks of code that perform a specific task. b) Used to store data that can be manipulated and retrieved throughout a program.</p>
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MODULE 4. SAFETY

Summary

This module covers essential aspects of maintaining safety and security in the digital realm. It emphasises the importance of protecting devices, personal data, health and well-being, and the environment. The content provides practical strategies and guidance for adults with limited digital literacy to navigate the online world securely. Key topics include understanding digital threats, creating strong passwords, safeguarding personal information, recognising and combating cyberbullying, balancing digital and physical well-being, seeking support resources, and minimising one's digital environmental footprint. By the end of this module, learners will be equipped with the knowledge and tools to foster a secure and responsible digital presence.

Learning Objectives

Upon completion of this module, learners will be able to:

1. Identify potential threats to their devices and implement measures to protect them, such as updating software and creating strong passwords.
2. Understand the concept of personal data and its importance, recognise digital threats, and apply practical strategies to safeguard their privacy and personal information online.
3. Maintain a healthy balance between digital activities and physical well-being, recognising the potential impact of excessive screen time and adopting strategies for nurturing mental and physical health.
4. Recognise and respond to instances of cyberbullying, promote positive online communication, and seek support resources when needed.
5. Comprehend the concept of a digital environmental footprint and its impact, and implement practical guidance to minimise digital waste, promote responsible consumption, and engage in responsible e-waste disposal practices.

Introduction

In today's digital age, understanding and practising online safety measures is crucial for individuals of all ages and digital literacy levels. This module aims to empower adult learners with limited digital skills to navigate the online world securely and responsibly.

We will explore various aspects of digital safety, starting with protecting devices from threats like viruses, malware, and scams. Learners will gain insights into creating strong passwords, keeping software up-to-date, and implementing additional security measures to safeguard their devices and accounts.

Furthermore, we will delve into protecting personal data and privacy. Learners will understand the concept of personal data, recognise digital threats, and learn practical strategies to safeguard their personal information while engaging in online activities.

Maintaining a healthy balance between digital and physical well-being is another vital aspect we will address. Learners will understand the potential impact of excessive screen time on mental and physical health and acquire strategies for nurturing overall well-being in the digital age.

Additionally, we will explore the issue of cyberbullying, equipping learners with the ability to recognise and respond to online harassment. Promoting positive online communication and seeking support resources when needed will be emphasised.

Finally, we will discuss the concept of a digital environmental footprint and its impact on the planet. Learners will gain practical guidance on minimising digital waste, promoting responsible consumption of electronic devices, and engaging in responsible e-waste disposal practices.

Through this comprehensive module, adult learners with limited digital literacy will gain the knowledge and skills to navigate the digital world safely, securely, and responsibly, fostering a positive and informed digital presence.

4.1. Protecting devices

In today's digital world, keeping our devices safe is essential to ensure our personal and work stuff stays secure. This part of the manual shows you simple ways to protect your computer, phone, or tablet from lousy stuff online.

We will start by talking about the things that might try to harm your device, like viruses or scams. Then, we will learn why keeping your device's software up-to-date is super important, making it harder for bad guys to get in.

Next, we will chat about passwords – those secret codes you use to get into your device or accounts. We will figure out how to make strong passwords that are tough for hackers to guess. Moreover, we will learn about using extra security measures, like codes sent to your phone, to make it even harder for them.

After that, we will look at different kinds of harmful software that might try to mess up your device. We will learn how to spot them and what to do to keep your device safe from them.

And then, we will talk about a cool thing called encryption. It is like a secret code that protects your essential stuff from anyone who should not see it. Understanding how encryption works will help you keep your private stuff private.

You can keep your devices and information secure by learning these simple tips and tricks. Furthermore, the best part is that you can use these tips immediately!

Protecting Your Device: Understanding Threats and Software Updates

At this point, we will explore how to keep your device safe from potential dangers and why it is essential to update its software regularly. Let us break it down in simple terms.

Firstly, let us talk about the bad stuff that might try to harm your devices, like viruses or scams. Imagine your device is like a house; these threats are like burglars trying to break in. Viruses are like sneaky germs that can make your device sick, slowing it down or even stopping it from working correctly. Scams are like tricky phone calls or emails that trick you into giving away your personal information, like your passwords or bank details. Knowing about these threats is like locking your doors and windows to keep the burglars out.

Now, let us move on to why keeping your device's software up-to-date is super important. Think of your device's software like its immune system – it helps protect it from getting sick. When your device's software is out-of-date, it is like having holes in your immune system that burglars can sneak through. Nevertheless, updating your software regularly is like giving your device a vaccine to strengthen its immune system. These updates often include fixes for security holes that hackers could use to break into your device and steal your stuff.

For example, imagine your phone gets a notification saying a software update is available. It is like getting a letter in the post telling you a new lock for your front door. It would help if you did not ignore it because it will help keep your home safe. Similarly, when you see a software update for your device, it is a good idea to install it straight away to keep your device safe from cyber burglars.

By understanding these simple concepts and taking action to protect your device, you can help keep your personal information safe and secure.

Securing Your Secrets: Creating Strong Passwords and Extra Security Measures

Now, we will dive into the world of passwords – those secret codes that keep your device and accounts safe. We will learn how to make strong passwords that are hard for hackers to guess, and we will discover extra security measures to make it even more challenging for them.

Let us start with passwords. Imagine your password is like the key to your front door – you would not want it to be easy for someone to copy. So, we will figure out how to make your password strong and unique, like a special key only you have. We will avoid using simple passwords like "123456" or "password" – those are like leaving your front door wide open for burglars! Instead, we will create passwords that mix uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and symbols to make them challenging to crack.

For example, remember a memorable phrase like "I love my dog Sparky!" Now, let us turn that into a strong password by using the first letter of each word, mixing in some numbers and symbols: "1L0v3mD\$!" See how we have turned a simple phrase into a strong password that's easy for you to remember but hard for hackers to guess?

However, we will not stop there. We will also learn about extra security measures, like codes sent to your phone. Imagine it is like adding an extra lock to your front door – even if someone guesses your password, they will still need a unique code from your phone to get in. It makes it even harder for hackers to break into your accounts and steal your stuff.

For instance, imagine you are logging into your email account. After typing your password, you receive a text message with a unique code. You enter that code to prove it is you trying to log in. It is like having a secret handshake that only you know!

By following these simple steps and using extra security measures, you will be like a digital locksmith, keeping your accounts and personal information safe from cyber burglars.

Spotting Sneaky Software: Identifying and Protecting Against Digital Threats

In this section, we will tackle the topic of sneaky software that can cause trouble for your device. We will learn how to spot these digital threats and what you can do to keep your device safe from them.

Imagine your device is like a garden, and this lousy software is like pesky weeds trying to take over. Just like you need to spot and remove weeds to keep your garden healthy, you must also spot and remove lousy software to keep your device running smoothly.

First, we will discuss different types of harmful software, like viruses, spyware, and adware. Viruses are nasty bugs that can make your device sick, while spyware is like a snoopy neighbour trying to peek into your private stuff. Moreover, adware is like annoying adverts that pop up everywhere. We will learn to recognise the signs of these threats, like strange pop-up messages or sudden slowdowns in your device's performance.

For example, if you notice your device suddenly running slow or bombarded with annoying pop-up ads, it could indicate that you have some lousy software lurking around. Just like you would not ignore weeds taking over your garden, you should not ignore these signs on your device.

Next, we will explore how to keep your device safe from these digital pests. We will talk about installing reputable antivirus software, like having a digital bug spray to keep the lousy software away. We will also learn about being careful when downloading apps or clicking on links – just like you would be cautious about letting strangers into your home, you should be cautious about what you let onto your device.

For instance, before downloading a new app, check the reviews and ensure they are from a trusted source. Furthermore, if you receive an email or message with a suspicious link, do not click on it – it could be a trick to infect your device with lousy software!

By learning to spot this sneaky software and taking proactive steps to protect your device, you will be like a digital pest control expert, keeping your device free from harmful threats.

Keeping Your Secrets Safe: Understanding Encryption for Digital Privacy

This section will explore the concept of encryption, which acts like a secret code to safeguard your critical information from prying eyes. Understanding how encryption works will empower you to keep your private stuff private in the digital world.

Think of encryption as a special lockbox where you can keep your most valuable possessions safe. Like you would not want anyone to peek inside your locked box without the key, encryption ensures that only authorised people can access your sensitive data.

Let us break it down into simple terms. When you send a message or store a file on your device, encryption scrambles the information into a jumble of characters that only someone with the correct key can unscramble. It is like writing your message in a secret language only you and the intended recipient understand.

For example, imagine you are sending a private message to a friend. Before you hit send, encryption transforms your message into a series of gibberish characters. Even if someone intercepts the message, they will not understand it without the decryption key – it is like trying to read a book written in a language you do not know.

Now, let us talk about how encryption helps protect your personal information online. Encryption ensures that your login details and payment information are transmitted securely when you visit a secure website, like your online banking or shopping site. It is like having a secure tunnel shielding your data from hackers and cybercriminals lurking online.

For instance, when you see a little padlock icon next to the website's address in your browser, it means the connection is encrypted. It is a visual cue that your information is safe from prying eyes.

By understanding the basics of encryption and its importance in digital privacy, you will be equipped to keep your personal information secure online. Like locking your valuables in a safe, encryption protects your digital assets, ensuring that only you and the intended recipients can access your private stuff.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in interactive learning experiences focused on understanding and implementing strategies to protect their devices and personal information in the digital world.
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Title of the practical activity:	Digital Security Workshop: Safeguarding Your Devices and Information
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adult learners, including individuals with varying levels of digital literacy.
Learning outcomes	<p>Understand common threats to device security, such as viruses, scams, and harmful software.</p> <p>Learn practical strategies for protecting devices, including keeping software updated, creating strong passwords, and recognizing digital threats.</p> <p>Gain awareness of encryption and its role in safeguarding personal information online.</p> <p>Develop skills to apply digital security practices effectively in everyday life.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key concepts and security tips</p> <p>Laptops or tablets with internet access for each participant (optional)</p> <p>Flipchart or whiteboard with markers</p> <p>Samples of phishing emails or malware pop-ups (optional)</p> <p>Password strength checker tool (optional)</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the workshop's objectives.</p> <p>Conduct an icebreaker activity to gauge participants' current knowledge and experiences with digital security. For example, ask participants to share a memorable experience related to online security or privacy concerns.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of common threats to device security, including viruses, scams, and harmful software. Use real-life examples and visuals to illustrate each type of threat.</p> <p>Facilitate a discussion on the importance of keeping device software updated and the role it plays in protecting against cyber threats. Encourage participants to share their experiences with software updates and any challenges they may have faced.</p> <p>Explain: Introduce strategies for creating strong passwords, such as using a combination of uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and symbols. Demonstrate how to use a password strength checker tool to assess the strength of different passwords.</p> <p>Discuss additional security measures, such as two-factor authentication and biometric authentication, and explain how they can enhance device security.</p>

	<p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and provide them with scenarios involving potential digital threats, such as receiving a suspicious email or encountering a malware pop-up. Ask each group to brainstorm appropriate responses and solutions to mitigate the threat.</p> <p>Encourage participants to share their solutions with the larger group and facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of different strategies.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and encouraging participants to apply the digital security practices they have learned in their daily lives.</p> <p>Distribute feedback forms to collect participants' thoughts and suggestions for improving future workshops on digital security.</p>
Methods	<p>Icebreaker activity</p> <p>Presentation with real-life examples and visuals</p> <p>Group discussions and brainstorming</p> <p>Hands-on activities, such as password strength checking</p> <p>Scenario-based learning and problem-solving</p> <p>Q&A sessions for clarification and further exploration</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their engagement in group discussions, participation in hands-on activities, and ability to apply digital security concepts to real-life scenarios. Use feedback forms to gather input on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness for future improvements.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Social Engineering: The Science of Human Hacking - Hadnagy, C. (2018)</p> <p>Data and Goliath: The Hidden Battles to Collect Your Data and Control Your World - Schneier, B. (2015)</p> <p>The Smart Girl's Guide to Privacy: Practical Tips for Staying Safe Online - Bennett, V. (2016)</p> <p>Future Crimes: Everything Is Connected, Everyone Is Vulnerable and What We Can Do About It - Goodman, M. (2015)</p>

4.2. Protecting personal data and privacy

This section will delve into the importance of protecting your data and privacy in the digital world. Adults with varying levels of digital literacy must understand how to safeguard sensitive information from prying eyes and potential threats.

First and foremost, we will explore what personal data is and why it is valuable. Personal data includes information like your name, address, phone number, and even your browsing history. Imagine it as pieces of a puzzle that, when put together, create a picture of who you are. Protecting this data is crucial because cybercriminals can use it for identity theft, fraud, or other malicious purposes.

Next, we will discuss common threats to personal data and privacy online. From phishing scams and data breaches to social engineering attacks, your personal information can be compromised in many ways. Understanding these threats will help you recognise potential dangers and proactively protect yourself.

We will also explore practical strategies for safeguarding your data. It includes tips like being cautious about sharing personal information online, using strong and unique passwords for your accounts, and enabling privacy settings on social media platforms. Additionally, we will discuss the importance of keeping your devices secure and up-to-date to minimise the risk of data breaches.

Furthermore, we will touch on the role of privacy policies and consent in protecting your data. Understanding how companies collect, use, and share your information and making informed decisions about what you are comfortable sharing are essential.

By the end of this section, you will better understand the importance of protecting your data and privacy online. With practical tips and knowledge, you will be empowered to navigate the digital world safely and protect yourself from potential threats to your privacy and security.

Understanding Personal Data: What It Is and Why It is Important

This section will begin by exploring personal data and why it holds significant value in the digital world. As adults with varying levels of digital literacy, it is crucial to grasp the fundamentals of personal data to protect ourselves better online.

Imagine personal data as pieces of a puzzle that, when put together, creates a picture of who you are. For example, your name, address, and phone number are pieces of this puzzle. They help identify you and where you live. Your browsing history is another piece, showing the websites you visit and what you are interested in. Small details, like your favourite food or music, can be pieces of this puzzle.

Understanding the value of personal data is essential. Just like you would not want strangers to know all about you, you do not want your data falling into the wrong hands. For instance, if someone gets hold of your name and address, they could pretend to be you and trick others into giving them money or access to your accounts. Similarly, your browsing history could be used to target you with scams or spam emails that seem to know a lot about you.

Imagine You are at home, minding your own business, when suddenly there is a knock on the door. You open it, and someone stands there, claiming to be your friend. They know all sorts of personal details about you – where you live, what you do for a living, your favourite hobbies, and even your

recent online purchases. It is unnerving, right? You would probably feel a mixture of confusion, fear, and discomfort. How did this stranger get so much information about you?

Now, let us translate this scenario to the digital world. Your data is like the vital information that allows someone to pretend to be your friend at your doorstep. The details make you uniquely you – your name, address, phone number, and more. If this information falls into the wrong hands, it can be used to impersonate, manipulate, or even steal from you.

Protecting your data is akin to locking your front door to keep strangers out. Just as you would not invite someone you do not know into your home, you should not willingly share your personal information with anyone online. By safeguarding your data, you are taking proactive steps to control who has access to your identity, privacy, and security.

In essence, protecting your data is not just about keeping your information safe; it is about preserving your sense of autonomy and security in an increasingly digital world. So, the next time you are asked to share personal information online, think of it as handing over the keys to your home – only give them to trusted individuals and organisations who genuinely need them.

By understanding the significance of personal data and the risks associated with its exposure, you will be better equipped to take proactive measures to protect yourself online. The following sections will delve deeper into practical strategies for safeguarding your data and privacy in today's digital landscape.

Recognising Digital Threats: Protecting Your Data and Privacy

In this section, we will explore the various threats to personal data and privacy online that adults with low digital literacy may encounter. By understanding these threats and their implications, you will be better equipped to safeguard your personal information and privacy.

Let us start by discussing phishing scams. Imagine receiving an email or message that looks like it is from your bank, asking you to click on a link and enter your account details. However, the email is from a cybercriminal trying to steal your login information. It is a phishing scam – a fraudulent attempt to obtain sensitive information by disguising it as a trustworthy entity. Falling for such scams can result in identity theft, financial loss, or unauthorised access to your accounts.

Another common threat is data breaches. Imagine a company you entrusted with your personal information suffers a data breach, exposing your data to cybercriminals. It could include your name, address, payment details, and more. Data breaches can occur due to security vulnerabilities in a company's systems or human error, which can seriously affect your privacy and security.

Social engineering attacks are also prevalent in the digital world. Imagine receiving a phone call from someone claiming to be a technical support representative from a well-known company informing you that your computer has a virus. They ask for remote access to your device to fix the issue, but they are trying to install malware or steal your personal information. Social engineering

attacks exploit human psychology to manipulate individuals into divulging sensitive information or performing actions compromising security.

Understanding these threats is essential for protecting your data and privacy online. By being aware of the signs of phishing scams, such as suspicious emails or messages requesting sensitive information, you can avoid falling victim to them. Similarly, staying vigilant about data breaches and keeping track of news and updates from companies you interact with can help mitigate the risks associated with compromised data.

When it comes to social engineering attacks, remember to verify the identity of individuals or organisations before sharing sensitive information or granting access to your devices. Do not be afraid to ask questions or seek assistance from trusted sources if something seems suspicious.

By recognising common threats to personal data and privacy online, you will be better prepared to take proactive steps to protect yourself and minimise the risk of falling victim to cybercrime. The following sections will explore practical strategies and best practices for safeguarding personal information in today's digital landscape.

Protecting Your Data: Practical Strategies for Digital Safety

Within this segment, we delve into actionable approaches to fortify your data in the digital domain. As individuals with diverse levels of digital proficiency, it is imperative to adopt these strategies to shield your sensitive information from potential threats.

Let us begin by stressing the significance of caution when divulging online personal information. Your data holds significant value, akin to currency. Hence, exercise prudence in its dissemination. Mindfully curate the information you share on digital platforms, refraining from disclosing unnecessary details like your full address, phone number, or birthdate, which could be exploited for malicious purposes.

Subsequently, we underline the importance of crafting robust and distinct passwords for your accounts. Your password is the gateway to your digital realm, thus ensuring its resilience and complexity. Construct passwords comprising a blend of uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and symbols, steering clear of common phrases or easily guessable combinations. Opt for a passphrase that holds personal significance but remains obscure to others.

Additionally, consider configuring privacy settings on social media platforms to regulate access to your personal information and posts. Tailor your privacy settings to restrict the visibility of your profile, posts, and personal details, thereby retaining control over who can access your information and mitigating the risk of unwarranted exposure or exploitation.

Furthermore, prioritise the security of your devices and keep them updated to mitigate the likelihood of data breaches and safeguard your personal information. Regularly update your

device's operating system, applications, and security software to fortify its defences against cyber threats. Supplement these efforts with additional security measures like biometric authentication and two-factor authentication (2FA) to bolster the protection of your accounts and data.

Lastly, leverage encryption to safeguard sensitive data stored on your devices, akin to sealing it within a secure digital vault. Encryption converts your data into an unreadable format, rendering it indecipherable to unauthorised individuals. By utilising encryption tools like Signal for messaging or VeraCrypt for file storage, you add a layer of security to your digital communications and data storage, ensuring confidentiality and privacy.

Incorporating these proactive measures into your digital practices empowers you to fortify the defences around your data and mitigate the risk of data breaches and cyber threats. Remember, safeguarding your personal information demands continuous diligence and vigilance in navigating the ever-evolving digital landscape. Subsequent sections will delve deeper into specific techniques and best practices for securing personal data across diverse online contexts.

Understanding Privacy Policies and Consent: Safeguarding Your Data

Let us explore the importance of privacy policies and consent in safeguarding your data, using straightforward examples everyone can understand.

Imagine you are visiting a new shop in town. Before you purchase, you notice a sign on the door with a list of rules about how the shop will use your personal information. It is similar to a privacy policy – it outlines how a company will collect, store, and use your data.

Now, let us break down what this means in the digital world:

When you sign up for a new online service or download an app, you are often asked to agree to their terms and conditions. These terms usually include a privacy policy that explains how the company will handle your personal information.

For example, you are signing up for a social media account. The privacy policy might explain that the company will collect data about your interests, friends, and activities on the platform. They may use this information to show you targeted ads or suggest content you like.

It is essential to take the time to read and understand these privacy policies before agreeing to them. Think of it like reading the terms and conditions before you buy something – you want to know what you are getting into before you commit.

Now, let us talk about consent:

Consent is like giving someone permission to do something. In the digital world, it is crucial to understand what you are agreeing to when you consent to sharing your personal information with a company.

For instance, installing a new app on your phone might ask permission to access your location, contacts, or photos. Before granting these permissions, consider whether you are comfortable sharing this information and whether the app needs it to function.

It is okay to say no or ask questions if you are unsure. Remember, you have the right to control how your personal information is used, and it is essential to make informed decisions about what you are comfortable sharing.

By understanding privacy policies and consent, you are taking proactive steps to protect your data and ensure that your digital interactions are transparent and respectful of your privacy. It is like being an informed shopper – you want to know what you are getting into before you commit.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in interactive learning experiences focused on understanding and implementing strategies to protect personal data and privacy in the digital world.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Privacy Workshop: Safeguarding Your Personal Information
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults with varying levels of digital literacy, including individuals who may be new to online privacy concepts.
Learning outcomes	Understand the importance of protecting personal data and privacy in the digital world. Learn practical strategies for safeguarding personal information online, including creating strong passwords, recognizing digital threats, and understanding privacy policies. Gain awareness of consent and the importance of making informed decisions about sharing personal information online.
Materials	Handouts summarizing key concepts and privacy tips Laptop or tablet with internet access for demonstration purposes (optional) Flipchart or whiteboard with markers Samples of phishing emails or privacy policy excerpts (optional) Consent form template (optional)

Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the workshop's objectives. Conduct an icebreaker activity related to personal privacy, such as asking participants to share their experiences or concerns about online privacy.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of personal data and its importance in the digital world. Use relatable examples and analogies to illustrate how personal data can be valuable and vulnerable. Facilitate a discussion on common threats to personal data and privacy online, such as phishing scams, data breaches, and social engineering attacks. Encourage participants to share any experiences or concerns they may have encountered.</p> <p>Explain: Introduce practical strategies for safeguarding personal information online, including creating strong passwords, enabling privacy settings, and recognizing digital threats. Provide step-by-step guidance on how to implement these strategies effectively. Discuss the role of privacy policies and consent in protecting personal data. Explain how to read and understand privacy policies, and emphasize the importance of making informed decisions about sharing personal information online.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and provide them with scenarios involving potential privacy concerns, such as receiving a suspicious email or navigating privacy settings on social media platforms. Ask each group to brainstorm solutions and best practices for addressing the scenario. Encourage groups to share their solutions with the larger group and facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of different strategies.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and encouraging participants to apply the privacy strategies they have learned in their online interactions. Distribute feedback forms to collect participants' thoughts and suggestions for improving future workshops on digital privacy.</p>
Methods	<p>Icebreaker activity</p> <p>Presentation with relatable examples and analogies</p> <p>Group discussions and brainstorming</p> <p>Hands-on activities, such as analyzing phishing emails or privacy policies</p> <p>Scenario-based learning and problem-solving</p> <p>Q&A sessions for clarification and further exploration</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their engagement in group discussions, participation in hands-on activities, and ability to apply privacy strategies to real-life scenarios. Use feedback forms to gather input on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness for future improvements.</p>

Reference, events and further reading	<p>Digital Minimalism: Choosing a Focused Life in a Noisy World" - Newport, C. (2019)</p> <p>Click Here to Kill Everybody: Security and Survival in a Hyper-connected World" - Schneier, B. (2018)</p> <p>Future Crimes: Everything Is Connected, Everyone Is Vulnerable and What We Can Do About It" - Goodman, M. (2015)</p> <p>The Smart Girl's Guide to Privacy: Practical Tips for Staying Safe Online" - Bennett, V. (2016)</p>
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4.3. Protecting health and well-being

Protecting health and well-being is paramount, especially in today's digitally-driven world, where online activities can impact mental, emotional, and physical well-being. For adults with low digital literacy, it is essential to address this topic in a way that's accessible and actionable.

Firstly, it is crucial to emphasise the importance of maintaining a healthy balance between digital activities and offline pursuits. Many adults with low digital literacy may spend excessive time online, leading to feelings of isolation, anxiety, or decreased physical activity. Encourage setting boundaries and allocating time for online and offline activities to promote well-being.

Secondly, raising awareness about the potential impact of digital activities on mental health is essential. Adults with low digital literacy may be more susceptible to misinformation, online bullying, or feelings of inadequacy when comparing themselves to others online. Provide resources and strategies for managing stress, anxiety, and negative emotions related to digital interactions.

Addressing the prevalence of cyberbullying is another critical aspect. Guide how to identify and respond to instances of online harassment. Adults with low digital literacy may be less familiar with the signs of cyberbullying or how to seek support. Educate on strategies for blocking and reporting abusive behaviour and promoting positive online communication and empathy.

Additionally, highlights the importance of maintaining physical health while engaging in digital activities. Prolonged screen time can contribute to sedentary behaviour and adversely affect posture, eyesight, and sleep quality. Offer tips for incorporating movement breaks, practising good ergonomics, and implementing screen time limits to support physical well-being.

Lastly, empower adults with low digital literacy to seek support and resources for maintaining their health and well-being in the digital age. Provide information on local community resources, helplines, and online support groups where individuals can access guidance, counselling, or assistance navigating digital challenges. Encourage open communication and destigmatise seeking help for digital-related issues.

Striking a Balance: Nurturing Well-being in the Digital Age

In today's digitally-driven world, balancing online engagement and offline activities is paramount for maintaining holistic well-being, especially for adults with limited digital literacy. It is imperative to underscore the significance of striking this equilibrium, considering the potential ramifications of excessive digital consumption on mental, emotional, and physical health.

Adults with low digital literacy may often be ensnared in the digital realm for prolonged periods, perhaps due to limited knowledge of alternative leisure activities or an overreliance on digital platforms for social connection. This overindulgence in online pursuits can exacerbate feelings of isolation as virtual exchanges supplant genuine human interactions. Moreover, excessive screen time has been linked to heightened levels of anxiety and stress as individuals become inundated with a constant stream of information and social comparisons.

Encouraging individuals to establish boundaries and delineate specific times for engaging in digital activities versus offline pursuits is crucial in fostering a balanced lifestyle. Individuals can mitigate the adverse effects of excessive digital consumption by consciously allocating time for outdoor walks, hobbies, or face-to-face interactions with loved ones. Setting aside dedicated periods for digital detoxification, where screens are switched off entirely, can provide much-needed respite and allow for reconnection with the physical world.

Promoting awareness of the benefits of offline activities, such as improved mental clarity, enhanced interpersonal relationships, and increased physical activity, is essential in incentivising individuals to prioritise a balanced lifestyle. Encouraging participation in community events, outdoor recreational activities, or creative pursuits can serve as catalysts for reducing digital dependency and fostering overall well-being.

In essence, advocating for a healthy balance between digital engagement and offline activities is not merely about limiting screen time; it is about nurturing a lifestyle that prioritises genuine human connections, self-care, and personal growth. By empowering individuals to reclaim agency over their digital habits and cultivate a harmonious relationship with technology, we can pave the way for a more balanced and fulfilling existence in the digital age.

Nurturing Mental Well-being in the Digital Landscape

In navigating the digital landscape, it is imperative to acknowledge and address the potential impact of digital activities on mental health, particularly for individuals with low digital literacy. Raising awareness about these implications and equipping individuals with resources to navigate digital interactions with resilience and mindfulness is essential for fostering mental well-being.

Individuals with limited familiarity with digital technologies may find themselves more susceptible to the adverse effects of online engagement. For instance, exposure to misinformation, cyberbullying, or comparing oneself unfavourably to others online can significantly impact mental well-being. Imagine encountering false health information on social media that leads to

unnecessary anxiety or distress. Alternatively, consider the experience of feeling inadequate after seeing curated snapshots of others' lives on platforms like Instagram.

To mitigate these risks, it is crucial to provide accessible resources and strategies for managing stress, anxiety, and negative emotions arising from digital interactions. For example, promoting the practice of mindfulness – focusing on the present moment without judgment – can help individuals develop resilience against the stressors of the digital world. Encouraging regular digital detoxes, where individuals take breaks from screens and engage in offline activities, can also promote mental well-being.

Furthermore, educating individuals on critical media literacy – critically evaluating and analysing media content – can empower them to navigate the digital landscape more effectively. By teaching individuals to question the credibility of online sources and discern fact from fiction, we can help them avoid falling prey to misinformation and reduce the impact of online stressors on mental health.

Additionally, fostering supportive online communities where individuals can seek guidance, share experiences, and receive validation can play a vital role in promoting mental well-being. Imagine joining an online forum where individuals support each other through challenges related to digital interactions, offering advice and encouragement.

In essence, raising awareness about the potential impact of digital activities on mental health and providing accessible resources for managing digital-related stressors are crucial steps in promoting mental well-being in the digital age. By equipping individuals with the knowledge and tools to navigate digital interactions mindfully and resiliently, we can foster a healthier relationship with technology and promote holistic well-being for all.

Standing Against Cyberbullying: Supporting Each Other Online

In addressing the issue of cyberbullying, it is essential to put ourselves in each other's shoes and understand the impact of our actions in the digital world. Many of us, regardless of our digital skills, may have experienced or witnessed online harassment, which can leave deep emotional scars. Let us explore how we can support each other in combating cyberbullying and promoting a culture of respect and kindness online.

Firstly, it is crucial to recognise the signs of cyberbullying, even in its subtlest forms. For instance, exclusion from online groups, receiving hurtful messages, or having false rumours spread about you are all indicators of cyberbullying. By understanding these signs, we can better support those experiencing such behaviour and take steps to address it.

Next, let us talk about how to respond to instances of cyberbullying. Blocking and reporting abusive behaviour are potent tools individuals can use to protect themselves and others online. For example, if hurtful comments on social media target someone, they can block the person responsible and report the comments to the platform's moderators. By taking action against

cyberbullying, we send a clear message that such behaviour is not acceptable in our online communities.

Moreover, promoting positive online communication is critical to preventing cyberbullying from occurring. Encouraging acts of kindness, such as sharing uplifting messages or complimenting others, can create a supportive and inclusive online environment. Imagine if every online interaction was filled with positivity and encouragement – it would make the digital world a much brighter place for everyone.

Additionally, empathy plays a crucial role in addressing cyberbullying. Putting ourselves in the shoes of those targeted can help us understand the impact of our words and actions. For example, before sharing a post or comment online, we can ask ourselves how it might make others feel and whether it contributes to a positive or negative online atmosphere. By practising empathy in our digital interactions, we can cultivate a culture of understanding and compassion online.

Lastly, providing support and resources for those affected by cyberbullying is essential for helping them navigate through difficult times. Helplines, online support groups, and counselling services can offer a listening ear and practical advice to individuals who may feel overwhelmed or isolated by online harassment. Knowing that help is available can make a world of difference to those facing cyberbullying.

Combating cyberbullying requires collective action and a commitment to creating a safer and more respectful online environment for everyone. By recognising the signs of cyberbullying, responding effectively to instances of online harassment, promoting positive communication, practising empathy, and offering support to those in need, we can stand together against cyberbullying and build a digital world where kindness and compassion prevail.

Nurturing Your Body in the Digital Age: Finding Harmony Between Screens and Physical Well-being

In today's world, it is all too easy to get caught up in the whirlwind of digital distractions and forget about the needs of our bodies. However, striking a healthy balance between our online adventures and physical health is paramount for our happiness and vitality. Let us explore practical strategies for weaving physical activity into our digital routines and safeguarding our well-being.

First and foremost, let us take a moment to recognise how our bodies can suffer from too much time glued to screens. Those hours hunched over devices can wreak havoc on our posture, strain our eyes, and disrupt our sleep. Think about how you feel after a long day slouched in front of a computer – those aches and pains are not just in your head! By acknowledging these effects, we can take proactive steps to counteract them and keep our bodies feeling their best.

One simple yet effective way to combat the toll of screen time is to incorporate regular movement breaks into our daily routines. It does not have to be anything fancy – just a quick stretch, a stroll around the room, or a few jumping jacks can work wonders to loosen up those stiff muscles and

boost our energy levels. Picture yourself taking a brief breather every hour, shaking off the stiffness, and feeling refreshed and ready to tackle whatever comes your way.

Moreover, paying attention to ergonomics – that fancy word for setting up our workspace – can make a difference in how our bodies fare during those long hours at the screen. Adjusting your chair, raising your monitor to eye level, and investing in some ergonomic accessories might seem like small changes, but they can significantly impact your comfort and well-being. Imagine how much better your body will feel when you are not constantly contorting to see the screen!

Moreover, let us not forget the importance of setting boundaries around screen time. It is all too easy to get sucked into the digital vortex and lose track of time, but carving out dedicated moments for physical activity, relaxation, and socialising is crucial for our overall health and happiness. Imagine scheduling some outdoor adventures, hobbies, or catch-ups with friends – not only will it give your body a break from the screen, but it will also nourish your soul and lift your spirits.

Nurturing physical well-being alongside digital engagement is critical to leading a vibrant and fulfilling life. By weaving movement breaks into our routines, paying attention to ergonomics, and setting boundaries around our screen time, we can ensure that our bodies stay happy and healthy amid our digital adventures. Let us embrace a holistic approach to well-being that honours our digital and physical selves, allowing us to thrive in every aspect of our lives.

Navigating the Digital World: Support for Every Journey

Let us talk about how we can make the digital world friendlier for everyone, no matter their comfort level with technology. It is like exploring a new city – sometimes you need a map or a friendly guide to show you around. That is where support and resources come in. Imagine having a helpful friend to turn to whenever you feel lost or confused in the digital jungle.

First, let us remember that asking for help is not a sign of weakness; it is a sign of strength. We all need a little assistance now and then, especially when navigating the digital landscape. By sharing information about local resources and online support groups, we can build a network of support that's always there when you need it. Picture having a group of friends who understand your struggles and are there to lend a helping hand whenever you need it most.

Moreover, let us not forget the power of communication. By creating a space where people feel comfortable sharing their experiences and seeking guidance without judgment, we can break down barriers and build a community of mutual support. Imagine being part of a group where everyone listens, learns, and grows together – a place where no question is too small and no problem is too big.

In addition to local support, the internet is a whole of helpful resources waiting to be discovered. Whether it is a tutorial video, a helpful forum, or an online counselling service, there is something out there for everyone. Imagine having access to a virtual library with answers to all your digital questions, available whenever and wherever you need them.

Ultimately, it is about creating a supportive and inclusive community where everyone feels welcome and valued. By sharing information, fostering communication, and embracing the power of technology, we can make the digital world a brighter and more welcoming place for all. Let us work together to build a world where everyone feels empowered to explore, learn, and grow in the digital landscape.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in interactive learning experiences focused on promoting health and well-being in the digital age, especially for adults with low digital literacy.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Wellness Workshop: Nurturing Health and Balance Online
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults with varying levels of digital literacy, including individuals who may be new to concepts of digital wellness.
Learning outcomes	<p>Understand the importance of maintaining a healthy balance between online and offline activities for overall well-being.</p> <p>Learn practical strategies for promoting mental, emotional, and physical health in the digital age.</p> <p>Gain awareness of resources and support networks available for navigating digital challenges and promoting digital wellness.</p>
Materials	<p>Handouts summarizing key concepts and wellness tips</p> <p>Laptop or tablet with internet access for demonstration purposes (optional)</p> <p>Flipchart or whiteboard with markers</p> <p>Samples of cyberbullying scenarios or ergonomic tips (optional)</p> <p>Contact information for local community resources and online support groups (optional)</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the workshop's objectives. Conduct an icebreaker activity related to digital wellness, such as asking participants to share their favourite offline activities or their experiences with managing screen time.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of the importance of maintaining health and balance in the digital age, focusing on the potential impacts of excessive screen time on mental, emotional, and physical well-being. Facilitate a</p>

	<p>discussion on common challenges faced by adults with low digital literacy, such as feelings of isolation, stress from online interactions, and physical discomfort from prolonged screen use.</p> <p>Explain: Introduce practical strategies for promoting digital wellness, including setting boundaries for screen time, practising mindfulness, and incorporating movement breaks into daily routines. Provide step-by-step guidance on how to implement these strategies effectively. Discuss the availability of resources and support networks for individuals seeking assistance with digital challenges or mental health concerns. Share information on local community resources, helplines, and online support groups where participants can access guidance and support.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and provide them with scenarios related to digital wellness challenges, such as managing screen time, dealing with cyberbullying, or incorporating physical activity into daily routines. Ask each group to brainstorm solutions and strategies for addressing the scenario.</p> <p>Encourage groups to share their solutions with the larger group and facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of different approaches.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the workshop by summarizing key takeaways and encouraging participants to apply the digital wellness strategies they have learned in their daily lives. Distribute feedback forms to collect participants' thoughts and suggestions for improving future workshops on digital wellness.</p>
Methods	<p>Icebreaker activity</p> <p>Presentation with relatable examples and analogies</p> <p>Group discussions and brainstorming</p> <p>Hands-on activities, such as scenario analysis or role-playing exercises</p> <p>Q&A sessions for clarification and further exploration</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their engagement in group discussions, participation in hands-on activities, and ability to apply digital wellness strategies to real-life scenarios. Use feedback forms to gather input on the workshop content, structure, and effectiveness for future improvements.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Indestructible: How to Control Your Attention and Choose Your Life - Eyal, N. (2019).</p> <p>Bored and Brilliant: How Spacing Out Can Unlock Your Most Productive and Creative Self - Zomorodi, M. (2017)</p> <p>The Healthy Mind Toolkit: Simple Strategies to Get Out of Your Own Way and Enjoy Your Life - Boyes, A. (2018)</p>

	The Human Era: Thriving in the Digital Landscape - Carr, N. (2021)
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4.4. Protecting the environment

Within the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program, the segment dedicated to protecting the environment should resonate with adults with limited digital literacy.

Entailing the concept of a digital environmental footprint is crucial. It illustrates how everyday digital activities, like streaming videos or storing data in the cloud, can have tangible environmental consequences. For instance, streaming or downloading large files consumes significant energy and contributes to carbon emissions, while electronic devices ultimately contribute to electronic waste when discarded.

Providing practical guidance on reducing digital waste is essential. Many adults may not realise the clutter accumulated in their digital lives, including unnecessary files or outdated devices. Educating them on decluttering digital spaces, deleting redundant files, and adopting energy-efficient devices empowers them to minimise their digital environmental footprint.

Addressing the environmental impact of online shopping and electronic gadgets is also essential. Many adults may not be aware of the energy-intensive manufacturing processes involved. We promote environmental responsibility by educating them about the lifecycle of electronic products and encouraging mindful consumption habits.

Furthermore, emphasising the importance of recycling electronic devices and promoting e-waste collection initiatives is crucial. Many adults may not know how or where to dispose of old gadgets properly, leading to environmental and health risks. Providing information on e-waste recycling centres and highlighting the benefits of recycling encourages responsible actions.

Lastly, fostering a sense of environmental stewardship is critical. By illustrating the interconnectedness of digital technology and environmental sustainability, we inspire adults to adopt a conscientious approach to their digital habits. Discussing how energy-efficient devices can reduce carbon emissions or how using renewable energy sources can mitigate environmental impact motivates participants to make eco-friendly choices.

Through these comprehensive approaches, the training course effectively equips adults with limited digital literacy with the knowledge, skills, and motivation needed to protect the environment in the digital age.

Understanding Your Digital Environmental Impact

Introducing the concept of a digital environmental footprint is essential in the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program. Participants need to grasp how their digital activities directly affect the environment. Consider everyday actions such as streaming videos or storing data in the cloud. While seemingly innocuous, these activities have tangible environmental consequences.

For instance, streaming or downloading large files consumes significant energy, contributing to carbon emissions. The energy required to power data centres and servers for streaming platforms comes predominantly from non-renewable sources, such as coal or natural gas. This reliance on fossil fuels leads to greenhouse gas emissions and exacerbates environmental degradation and climate change.

Additionally, the disposal of electronic devices contributes to electronic waste, further exacerbating environmental concerns. Electronic waste, or e-waste, contains hazardous materials such as lead, mercury, and cadmium, which can leach into soil and water sources if not adequately managed. Furthermore, extracting raw materials and manufacturing electronic devices contributes to habitat destruction, air and water pollution, and resource depletion.

By illustrating these connections in the training course, participants gain a deeper understanding of their role in environmental sustainability within the digital age. They become aware of the environmental consequences of their digital activities and are motivated to adopt more eco-friendly practices to minimise their digital environmental footprint.

Minimising Digital Waste: Practical Guidance

Equipping participants with practical guidance on reducing digital waste is vital within the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program. Many adults are unaware of the clutter accumulated in their digital lives, which includes unnecessary files and outdated devices.

Consider how participants may have numerous files stored on their devices, many redundant or no longer needed. These files take up valuable storage space and consume additional energy during data transfer and storage processes. Additionally, outdated devices no longer in use may still be kept, contributing to electronic clutter and potential environmental harm when eventually discarded.

Educating participants on the importance of decluttering their digital spaces is crucial. Encouraging them to identify and delete redundant files can free up storage space and reduce energy consumption associated with data storage and transfer. Furthermore, promoting the adoption of energy-efficient devices ensures that participants make environmentally conscious choices when purchasing or upgrading their electronic devices.

Through these efforts, participants become more mindful of their digital consumption habits and empowered to take practical steps towards minimising their digital environmental footprint.

Promoting Responsible Consumption: Awareness of Environmental Impact

In the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program context, it is crucial to address the environmental impact of online shopping and electronic gadgets. Many adults may not fully grasp the energy-intensive manufacturing processes of producing these products.

Consider how participants may engage in frequent online shopping without considering the environmental consequences. Each stage of an electronic product's lifecycle has environmental implications, from the extraction of raw materials to the manufacturing processes and distribution. Educating participants about these processes empowers them to make informed decisions and adopt mindful consumption habits.

Encouraging participants to consider product lifespan, energy efficiency, and recyclability when purchasing fosters environmental responsibility. Through this awareness, participants become more conscientious consumers, contributing to the reduction of environmental harm associated with electronic gadgets and online shopping practices.

Encouraging Responsible Disposal: E-waste Recycling and Collection Initiatives

In the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program framework, it is essential to underscore the significance of recycling electronic devices and promoting initiatives for e-waste collection. For many adults, particularly those with low digital literacy, proper disposal of old gadgets may be unfamiliar territory, resulting in environmental and health hazards.

Consider the scenario where participants might discard old electronic devices in regular waste bins, unaware of the potential harm caused by the toxic materials they contain. By providing information on e-waste recycling centres or events, we bridge this knowledge gap, empowering participants to take responsible actions towards e-waste management.

Highlighting the benefits of recycling, such as conserving resources, reducing pollution, and minimising the need for raw material extraction, can motivate participants to engage in recycling efforts. Through these initiatives, participants develop a sense of environmental stewardship and actively contribute to mitigating the environmental impact of electronic waste.

Inspiring Environmental Consciousness: Connecting Digital Technology and Sustainability

In the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program, nurturing a sense of environmental stewardship emerges as pivotal. By highlighting the intricate relationship between digital technology and

environmental sustainability, we instil in adults a mindful perspective towards their digital behaviours.

Imagine discussing with participants the profound impact of digital activities on the environment, illustrating how small changes in their digital habits can yield significant environmental benefits. For instance, delving into energy-efficient devices and their role in reducing carbon emissions offers tangible examples of how individual actions can contribute to broader environmental goals.

Moreover, engaging participants in conversations about the potential of renewable energy sources to power digital infrastructures underscores the importance of embracing eco-friendly alternatives. By fostering this connection between digital technology and environmental stewardship, participants are motivated to adopt sustainable digital lifestyles, contributing to a greener future.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in experiential learning focused on understanding and mitigating their digital environmental footprint, within the context of the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program.
Title of the practical activity:	Eco-Friendly Digital Makeover: Reducing Your Digital Environmental Footprint
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults with limited digital literacy participate in the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program.
Learning outcomes	Understand the concept of a digital environmental footprint and its implications for environmental sustainability. Learn practical strategies for reducing digital waste and promoting responsible consumption of electronic devices. Gain awareness of the importance of e-waste recycling and environmental stewardship in the digital age.
Materials	Handouts summarizing key concepts and practical tips Samples of electronic devices and e-waste recycling information Flipchart or whiteboard with markers Laptops or tablets with internet access for demonstration purposes (optional)

	Recycling bins or containers for sorting waste (optional)
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the topic of environmental sustainability in the digital age. Conduct an interactive icebreaker activity where participants share their experiences with digital devices and online activities, highlighting any concerns or questions they may have about their environmental impact.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of the concept of a digital environmental footprint, explaining how everyday digital activities contribute to environmental degradation. Facilitate a discussion on the environmental consequences of digital consumption, focusing on topics such as energy consumption, e-waste generation, and resource depletion.</p> <p>Explain: Introduce practical strategies for reducing digital waste and promoting responsible consumption of electronic devices. Provide step-by-step guidance on decluttering digital spaces, purchasing energy-efficient devices, and extending the lifespan of electronic products. Discuss the importance of e-waste recycling and highlight local recycling centres or initiatives where participants can dispose of their old electronic devices responsibly.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a scenario related to digital environmental sustainability, such as reducing energy consumption or promoting e-waste recycling. Ask groups to brainstorm eco-friendly solutions and strategies based on their assigned scenario, encouraging creativity and collaboration. Provide time for groups to present their ideas to the larger group and facilitate a discussion on the feasibility and impact of each proposed solution.</p> <p>Evaluate: Conclude the activity by summarizing key takeaways and encouraging participants to apply the eco-friendly strategies they have learned in their daily lives. Distribute feedback forms to collect participants' thoughts and suggestions for improving future sessions on digital environmental sustainability.</p>
Methods	<p>Interactive icebreaker activity</p> <p>Presentation with visual aids and real-life examples</p> <p>Group discussions and brainstorming</p> <p>Hands-on activities, such as sorting e-waste or creating eco-friendly action plans</p> <p>Q&A sessions for clarification and further exploration</p>
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their engagement in group activities, participation in discussions, and understanding of key concepts related to

	digital environmental sustainability. Use feedback forms to gather input on the effectiveness of the practical activity and identify areas for improvement.
Reference, events and further reading	<p>E-Waste: Implications, Regulations, and Management in India and Current Global Best Practices" - Nnorom, I. C., & Osibanjo, O. (2008)</p> <p>The Circular Economy: A Wealth of Flows" - Webster, K. (2015)</p> <p>Responsible Consumption and Production" - United Nations Sustainable Development Goals Report (2018)</p> <p>Sustainable Digital Technologies: Examples from the Nordic Region" - Nordic Council of Ministers (2019)</p>

Video links for safety

How to Protect Your Data Online

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sdpxddDzXfE>

Protecting Personal Privacy

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vTWywg4DVpg>

Cyber Codes

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q6FanLhvsEs>

The Top 10 Cyber Safety Tips to Secure Your Home

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CyVw1GEQv7E>

Evaluation questions

Multiple Choice Questions

1. Which of the following is NOT a good practice for protecting your device from potential threats?
 - a. Keeping your software up-to-date
 - b. Using strong and unique passwords
 - c. Sharing your login credentials with others
 - d. Installing antivirus software

2. What is the primary purpose of encryption?
 - a. To keep your device's software updated
 - b. To create strong passwords
 - c. To safeguard your important data from unauthorised access
 - d. To identify potential threats

3. Which of the following is NOT an example of personal data?
 - a. Your name
 - b. Your address
 - c. Your favourite colour
 - d. Your browsing history

4. What is the best way to respond to cyberbullying?
 - a. Ignore it and hope it goes away
 - b. Retaliate with harsher comments
 - c. Block and report the abusive behaviour
 - d. Share personal information about the bully

5. What is the primary reason for balancing digital and physical activities?
- To improve your posture
 - To protect your device from threats
 - To nurture your overall well-being
 - To create stronger passwords
6. Which of the following is NOT a strategy for minimising your digital environmental footprint?
- Decluttering and deleting unnecessary files
 - Adopting energy-efficient devices
 - Leaving devices plugged in and charging at all times
 - Responsibly disposing of e-waste

Matching Questions

What is the purpose of a privacy policy?	To outline how a company will collect, store, and use your data
Which of the following is an example of a phishing scam?	Receiving an email from your bank asking for your login credentials
What is the benefit of incorporating movement breaks into your daily routine?	It combats the toll of excessive screen time on your body
Which of the following is NOT a practical strategy for safeguarding your data?	Sharing your login credentials with trusted friends and family

MODULE 5. PROBLEM-SOLVING

Summary

In the fast-paced environment of today's digital age, technology has become an indispensable part of our daily lives, influencing the way we communicate, work and interact with the world around us. The problem-solving module is designed to empower adults aged 55+ with essential problem-solving skills in the digital domain. Focusing on four main areas: solving technical problems, identifying needs and technological responses, using digital technologies creatively and identifying digital competence gaps, the module aims to provide comprehensive guidance. Participants will learn to solve common technical challenges encountered with digital devices and platforms. They will also learn to recognize their individual needs and skillfully select appropriate technological interventions to meet these needs. Fostering creativity and resourcefulness, the module will enable learners to use digital technologies effectively, enriching their daily lives and facilitating participation in various activities. The importance of these benefits for adults over 55 lies in their power to safely navigate the digital environment, promoting independence, connectivity and lifelong learning.

Learning Objectives

At the end of this module, learners will be able to:

- develop effective strategies for resolving technical problems about digital devices and platforms;
- recognize personal needs and choose appropriate technological solutions to address these needs;
- show creativity in employing digital technologies for a variety of practical purposes;
- assess their existing digital competencies and create effective strategies to address gaps in digital literacy.

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving digital environment, the ability to navigate with competence in technology is becoming increasingly important regardless of age. For adults aged 55 and over, embracing digital literacy is not just about staying connected; it is about unlocking a world of opportunities, from accessing information and services to enhancing social connections and lifelong learning. However, the journey towards digital competence can often be intimidating, especially for those with limited experience with technology.

With this in mind, the Problem-Solving module is designed to equip older adults with the critical problem-solving skills necessary to navigate the digital realm with confidence. Addressing key topics such as technical problem-solving, identifying needs and technological responses, creative

use of digital tools and recognizing digital competence gaps, this module aims to bridge the gap between concern and competence.

Through interactive learning experiences, participants will not only gain practical skills in troubleshooting common technical problems but also learn to identify their specific digital needs and leverage technology to fulfil them effectively. Furthermore, the module fosters a culture of creativity and resourcefulness, encouraging learners to explore the wide range of digital tools available and find innovative ways to improve their daily lives.

In conclusion, the Problem-Solving module aims to empower adults aged 55 and over by enabling them to embrace technology with a sense of confidence, independence and lifelong learning. By equipping learners with the skills and mindset needed to navigate the digital landscape, this module opens the door to new opportunities and experiences, enriching lives and promoting connectivity in an increasingly digitalized world.

5.1. Solving Technical Problems

In today's digital environment, overcoming technical challenges is an essential skill for individuals of all ages. From hardware failures to software malfunctions and connectivity issues, encountering technical problems can disrupt productivity and cause frustration in various aspects of our lives. This section on “Solving Technical Problems” aims to equip learners with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively troubleshoot and resolve common problems encountered with devices and digital tools. By understanding how to identify common issues, interpret error messages, and implement effective solutions, learners will improve their digital literacy and gain the confidence to navigate the digital world with ease and confidence. Let's explore the details of solving technical problems, starting with identifying and understanding common issues encountered in the digital environment.

Developing the ability to troubleshoot and resolve technical issues is essential for navigating the digital landscape. It involves identifying and addressing common problems encountered with devices and digital tools.

1. **Identifying Common Problems:** Individuals learn to identify and understand common problems that occur in devices and digital tools. This includes hardware failures, software malfunctions and connectivity issues.
2. **Understanding Error Messages:** Being able to interpret error messages is crucial to accurately diagnose technical problems. Understanding the language of error messages helps individuals identify the root cause of the problem and take appropriate action.
3. **Implementing Effective Solutions:** Once the problem has been identified, individuals must implement effective solutions. This may include troubleshooting steps, software updates, hardware repairs or seeking help from technical support.

Slow Internet Connections

In today's digital age, slow internet connections can cause countless challenges, affecting tasks ranging from browsing web pages to making video calls and sending emails. Let's explore common issues caused by slow internet connections and troubleshooting steps to effectively address them.

1. Difficulty in Loading Webpages

Problem: Imagine trying to access a news website or an online shopping platform but finding that the pages take a long time to load. It's frustrating because instead of getting the information or products you need quickly, you have to wait several minutes for the pages to appear.

2. Buffering While Streaming Videos

Problem: When you're streaming a movie or a tutorial online, the video keeps pausing and buffering. It disrupts the flow, and what could have been a seamless experience turns into frequent interruptions, making it hard to enjoy or learn from the content.

3. Delays in Sending Emails Due to Internet Issues

Problem: You're trying to send an important email, but due to a slow internet connection, it takes a long time for the email to leave your outbox. This delay might affect time-sensitive communications, such as work-related emails or urgent messages to friends or family.

Troubleshooting Steps

- **Restart the Router:** Unplug your router from the power source, wait for 30 seconds, and then plug it back in.
- **Check Connectivity:** Make sure all cables are properly connected. Ensure the Wi-Fi indicator on your device is on.
- **Positioning the Router:** Keep the router in an open space and away from obstructions for better signal strength.

Software Malfunctions

When software malfunctions occur, they can disrupt activities ranging from creating important emails to participating in video calls and accessing essential documents. Let's explore common software issues and troubleshooting steps to resolve them effectively.

1. Freezing Email Program

Problem: You're composing an important email and suddenly the email program freezes. You're unable to continue writing or even close the program, potentially losing the unsaved email draft.

2. Video Chat Disruptions

Problem: During a video call with family or friends, the video chat app crashes unexpectedly, disrupting the conversation and causing frustration due to the interruption.

3. Difficulty in Opening Files

Problem: You're trying to access a document for a hobby or interest, like a cooking recipe or gardening guide, but the document software won't open or displays an error message, making it challenging to access the information you need.

Troubleshooting Steps

- Update the Software: Go to settings, find 'Software Update,' and download any available updates for your applications.
- Restart the Application: Close the application and reopen it. Sometimes, this can resolve software issues.
- Clear Cache and Data: In settings, find the app, go to 'Storage,' and clear cache or data if the app is misbehaving.

Device Errors

Experiencing errors on your devices can be a serious inconvenience that interrupts your workflow and causes stress and frustration. Let's explore common device errors such as system crashes, overheating and hardware failures, and effective troubleshooting steps to fix them immediately.

1. System Crash and Data Loss

Problem: You're working on an important document, and suddenly your computer freezes. You're unable to do anything, and after restarting, you find out your file is corrupted or missing.

2. Overheating Affecting Performance

Problem: Your laptop feels excessively warm during use, and you notice it's slower than usual. This could be due to dust accumulation inside the device or inadequate ventilation.

3. Hardware Malfunction (Non-Responsive Screen)

Problem: Your tablet's screen stops responding to touch commands, making it impossible to navigate or use apps effectively.

Troubleshooting Steps

- Perform a Restart: Turn off your device, wait for a minute, and turn it back on. This can fix minor issues.
- Check for Overheating: Ensure your device is not in direct sunlight or on a surface that obstructs ventilation.
- Run Diagnostics: Use built-in device diagnostics or system tools to identify hardware issues.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in hands-on learning to develop their skills in troubleshooting and resolving common technical problems encountered in the digital environment.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Troubleshooting Workshop: Mastering Technical Problem Solving

Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults with limited digital literacy participate in the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program.
Learning outcomes	<p>Identify common technical problems encountered with devices and digital tools.</p> <p>Understand how to interpret error messages and diagnose technical issues accurately.</p> <p>Implement effective troubleshooting steps to resolve technical problems promptly and independently.</p>
Materials	<p>Sample devices with simulated technical problems (e.g., laptops, smartphones, routers)</p> <p>Handouts summarizing common technical problems and troubleshooting steps</p> <p>Whiteboard or flipchart with markers</p> <p>Troubleshooting guidebooks or manuals</p> <p>Tools for hardware diagnostics (optional)</p> <p>Spare cables and adapters (optional)</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the purpose of the workshop: to enhance their skills in troubleshooting common technical problems encountered in the digital environment.</p> <p>Conduct a brief icebreaker activity where participants share their experiences with overcoming technical challenges. Encourage them to discuss any strategies or solutions they have used in the past.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of common technical problems encountered with devices and digital tools, including hardware failures, software malfunctions, and connectivity issues. Use real-life examples to illustrate each type of problem.</p> <p>Discuss the importance of interpreting error messages accurately in diagnosing technical issues. Highlight key terms and phrases commonly found in error messages and their significance in troubleshooting.</p> <p>Explain: Provide participants with handouts summarizing common technical problems and troubleshooting steps. Review each problem scenario and discuss the corresponding steps to resolve them effectively.</p> <p>Demonstrate how to implement troubleshooting steps using sample devices with simulated technical problems. Encourage participants to follow along and ask questions as needed.</p>

	<p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a specific technical problem scenario to solve. Provide them with sample devices and troubleshooting guidebooks to assist in the process.</p> <p>Allow time for groups to collaborate and apply the troubleshooting steps learned to diagnose and resolve the assigned technical problem. Encourage them to document their process and findings.</p> <p>Evaluate: Reconvene as a larger group and invite each group to present their findings and solutions. Facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of different troubleshooting strategies and the challenges encountered.</p> <p>Summarize key takeaways from the workshop and encourage participants to apply their newfound troubleshooting skills in their daily lives. Distribute feedback forms to gather input on the workshop's effectiveness and areas for improvement.</p>
Methods	<p>Icebreaker activity for engagement</p> <p>Presentation with real-life examples and error message interpretation</p> <p>Hands-on troubleshooting practice with sample devices</p> <p>Group collaboration and problem-solving</p> <p>Discussion and reflection on troubleshooting strategies</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their engagement in group activities, ability to apply troubleshooting steps effectively, and contributions to group discussions. Use feedback forms to gather input on the workshop's relevance and usefulness for participants' learning needs.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Troubleshooting & Repairing Consumer Electronics Without a Schematic by Homer L. Davidson offers in-depth troubleshooting techniques for electronics.</p> <p>Troubleshooting with the Windows Sysinternals Tools by Mark Russinovich and Aaron Margosis guides diagnosing and fixing Windows-related issues.</p>

5.2. Identifying Needs and Technological Responses

Navigating the digital environment requires not only an understanding of technology but also the ability to effectively harmonize it with specific needs. In this section, we address the crucial skill of identifying needs and matching them with appropriate technological solutions. Individuals who acquire mastery of this competency can use the power of technology to facilitate tasks, improve communication and pursue personal interests more effectively.

Developing the ability to match needs with technological solutions is crucial in the digital age. This involves understanding specific requirements and selecting appropriate technologies to

address them effectively. Participants explore the range of technologies and tools available to meet their needs by understanding the characteristics, capabilities and limitations of different technologies. Based on the assessment of needs and understanding of available technologies, individuals make informed decisions about choosing the most appropriate technology solution.

Identifying Needs and Technological Responses is a key aspect of problem-solving in the digital age. It enables individuals to identify their unique technological needs and make informed decisions in the broader digital environment. This competency focuses on recognizing personal challenges and opportunities and effectively using digital tools and solutions to address them.

Here are some key strategies for developing this skill:

Understanding Personal Needs: Start by undertaking introspection and identifying areas in your life where technology can make a difference. Whether it's facilitating daily tasks, improving communication or pursuing new interests, understanding your needs is the first step to finding the appropriate technological answers.

Explore Digital Solutions: Once you have identified your needs, explore the many digital solutions available. From apps for productivity to smart home devices, there is a range of technologies designed to meet a variety of requirements. Take the time to research and experiment with different tools to find the ones that best suit your needs and preferences.

Seek Guidance and Advice: Feel free to contact friends, family or online communities for advice and recommendations. Participate in discussions, attend workshops or join online forums where you can exchange ideas and learn from others' experiences. This collaborative approach can provide valuable insights and help you discover innovative solutions you might not have otherwise considered.

Stay Informed and Adapt: The digital environment is constantly developing and new technologies are introduced regularly. Stay informed about the latest trends and developments in digital technology to ensure you are making informed decisions. Be open to learning and adapting to new technologies, as this flexibility will ensure you remain effective problem solvers in an ever-changing digital world.

Implementation and Evaluation of Solutions: Once you have chosen a technological solution, apply it to your daily life and evaluate its effectiveness. Pay attention to how well it meets your needs and whether it improves your overall productivity and well-being. Feel free to make adjustments or explore alternative solutions if necessary.

Reflect and Refresh: Finally, take time to reflect on your experiences and lessons learned throughout the process. Identify areas where you succeeded and where you can improve. Use this feedback to refine and optimize your approach to identifying needs and technological responses, ensuring continuous growth and adaptation in the digital space.

Difficulty in Accessing Online Documents

In today's digital age, trouble-free access to online documents is essential for collaboration and productivity. However, facing challenges in accessing these documents can break workflows and hinder effective teamwork. Let's explore some practical solutions to overcome these challenges and ensure easy access to online documents for smooth collaboration and productivity.

Problem: You are trying to access important documents stored in the cloud or on a shared network drive for a project, but you encounter difficulty in opening or downloading the files. This disrupts your workflow and hinders your ability to collaborate with team members.

Solution:

- **Check Network Connectivity:** Ensure that you have a stable internet connection by testing other websites or applications. If the connection is unstable, troubleshoot the internet connection according to the steps given.
- **Clear Browser Cache:** Clear your browser's cache and cookies, as accumulated data may cause issues with accessing online documents. Instructions for clearing the cache can vary depending on the browser used.
- **Try Alternate Devices or Browsers:** Attempt to access the documents using a different device or web browser to rule out device-specific or browser-specific issues.

1. Difficulty Synchronizing Data Between Devices

Ensuring that data is synchronized properly across multiple devices is essential to maintain consistency and prevent potential data loss. However, encountering difficulties in this synchronization process can disrupt workflows and cause serious problems. Let's explore some practical solutions to overcome these challenges and ensure smooth data synchronization across all your devices for continuous access and updates.

Problem: You have important data such as contacts, calendars or files that need to be synchronized across multiple devices for seamless access and updates. However, you are experiencing difficulties synchronizing data leading to inconsistencies and potential data loss.

Solution:

- **Check Synchronization Settings:** Verify that synchronization settings are enabled and configured correctly on all devices. Make sure the correct accounts are connected for data synchronization.
- **Restart Devices:** Restart all devices involved in data synchronization, including smartphones, tablets, computers or cloud storage services. Sometimes a simple reboot can resolve synchronization issues.
- **Update Software:** Make sure that all devices and applications involved in data synchronization are running the latest software versions. Outdated software may contain bugs or compatibility issues that prevent data synchronization.

2. Difficulty in Connecting to Wireless Devices

Being able to easily connect wireless devices to our computers or mobile devices is essential for greater productivity and convenience. However, encountering difficulties in establishing these connections can be frustrating and interfere with our workflow. Let's explore effective solutions to overcome these challenges and ensure a stable and reliable connection to our wireless devices.

Problem: You are attempting to connect wireless devices, such as Bluetooth headphones, a wireless printer, or a smart speaker, to your computer or mobile device. However, you encounter difficulties in establishing a stable connection or pairing the devices.

Solution:

- **Check Device Compatibility:** Ensure that the wireless device is compatible with your computer or mobile device and supports the required wireless protocols, such as Bluetooth or Wi-Fi.
- **Reset Device Pairing:** Reset the pairing settings on both the wireless device and your computer or mobile device. Follow the manufacturer's instructions for resetting device pairing.
- **Update Drivers or Firmware:** Check for and install any available updates for device drivers or firmware. Updated drivers or firmware may resolve compatibility issues and improve device connectivity.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in hands-on learning to develop their skills in identifying needs and matching them with appropriate technological solutions, specifically focusing on practical scenarios encountered in the digital environment.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Needs Assessment and Technology Matching Workshop
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults with limited digital literacy participate in the DigIN Multi-Pack Educational Program.
Learning outcomes	Identify common technological needs encountered in the digital environment. Explore various technological solutions available to address specific needs. Understand the process of matching needs with appropriate technological responses. Develop problem-solving skills through hands-on practice and collaboration.
Materials	Sample devices (e.g., smartphones, laptops, tablets) Handouts summarizing common technological needs and corresponding solutions

	<p>Whiteboard or flipchart with markers</p> <p>Technology demonstration tools (e.g., projector, screen)</p> <p>Internet access for research purposes</p> <p>Worksheets for participants to document their findings and solutions</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants and introduce the purpose of the workshop: to develop skills in identifying technological needs and matching them with appropriate solutions.</p> <p>Conduct a brief discussion to explore participants' experiences with encountering technological challenges in their daily lives. Encourage them to share examples of specific needs they have encountered and how they attempted to address them.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of common technological needs encountered in the digital environment, such as accessing online documents, synchronizing data between devices, and connecting to wireless devices. Use real-life examples to illustrate each need.</p> <p>Introduce various technological solutions available to address each identified need. Discuss the characteristics, capabilities, and limitations of different technologies to help participants understand their suitability for specific situations.</p> <p>Explain: Provide participants with handouts summarizing the identified technological needs and corresponding solutions. Review each scenario and discuss potential technological responses. Encourage participants to ask questions and seek clarification as needed.</p> <p>Demonstrate how to research and explore technological solutions using sample devices and internet resources. Guide participants through the process of evaluating different technologies based on their features and suitability for specific needs.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a specific technological need scenario to address. Provide them with sample devices, handouts, and access to internet resources to research and identify appropriate solutions.</p> <p>Allow time for groups to collaborate and brainstorm potential technological responses to their assigned scenarios. Encourage them to consider factors such as cost, usability, and compatibility when selecting solutions.</p> <p>Evaluate: Reconvene as a larger group and invite each group to present their findings and solutions. Facilitate a discussion on the effectiveness of different technological responses and their suitability for addressing specific needs.</p>

	Summarize key takeaways from the workshop and encourage participants to apply their problem-solving skills in identifying and addressing technological needs in their daily lives. Distribute feedback forms to gather input on the workshop's effectiveness and areas for improvement.
Methods	Group discussion and sharing of experiences Presentation with real-life examples of technological needs Hands-on exploration of technological solutions Group collaboration and problem-solving activities Group presentations and facilitated discussions
Evaluation	Assess participants based on their engagement in group activities, ability to identify appropriate technological solutions, and contributions to group discussions. Use feedback forms to gather input on the workshop's relevance and usefulness for participants' learning needs.
Reference, events and further reading	LinkedIn Learning for Online Courses: LinkedIn Learning TechCrunch for Latest Tech Trends: TechCrunch CNET Reviews and Guides: CNET

5.3. Creatively Using Digital Technologies

In the dynamic digital environment of the modern day, creativity is the leading force behind innovation and expression. Leveraging digital tools to nurture creativity opens up endless possibilities for individuals to explore, innovate and communicate in a variety of unprecedented ways. This section, 'Creatively Using Digital Technologies ', provides insight into how individuals can use technology to realize their creative potential. Individuals who embrace creativity through digital mediums can shape the future of both individual endeavours and careers by navigating the digital age with mastery and adaptability.

Creatively using digital technologies is not just about utilizing tools; it's about embracing a mindset of innovation and exploration to solve problems and express ideas in novel ways. In today's digital age, the ability to leverage technology creatively is essential for success in various domains, from business and education to personal pursuits. Here, we explore strategies for leveraging digital tools to foster creativity and navigate the ever-evolving digital landscape.

Exploring Digital Tools and Platforms

Familiarize yourself with the various digital tools and platforms available. From graphic design software to multimedia editing tools and online collaboration platforms, there are countless

resources to support your creative endeavours. Try experimenting with different tools to discover which ones align with your creative vision and improve your workflow.

Understanding Digital Media and Formats

Take a deeper dive into the world of digital media and formats to understand their unique characteristics and capabilities. Explore the nuances of images, video, audio and interactive media to effectively communicate messages and inspire emotions. Consider how different formats can complement each other in multimedia projects to create engaging experiences.

Adopting Design Thinking Principles

Adopt a design thinking mindset to approach problems and challenges from a user-centered perspective. Learn to empathize with your audience, clearly define problems, think of innovative solutions, quickly prototype ideas and then test them through iteration. Incorporate design thinking principles into your creative process to develop meaningful, functional and user-friendly solutions.

Fostering Collaborative Creativity

Recognize the power of collaboration in fostering creativity and innovation. Engage with different teams and communities to exchange ideas, share perspectives and co-create solutions to complex problems. Use digital collaboration tools and platforms to facilitate communication and coordination among team members regardless of geographic locations or time zones.

Exploring Emerging Technologies

Stay tuned to new technologies and trends shaping the digital environment, such as artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and blockchain. Experiment with these technologies to envision new possibilities for creative expression and problem-solving. Embrace experimentation and risk-taking as you discover unexplored territories and push the boundaries of what is possible with digital technologies.

Cultivating a Creative Mindset

Cultivate a mindset of curiosity, experimentation and flexibility as you navigate the ever-changing landscape of digital creativity. Embrace failure as an opportunity to learn and grow, and don't be afraid to take risks in pursuit of your creative vision. Be open to feedback and constructive criticism and use it to refine your ideas and improve your skills over time.

1. Creating a Multimedia Presentation

Creating engaging multimedia presentations is essential to effectively convey ideas and information. However, smoothly integrating various digital elements can create challenges that need to be addressed for a successful presentation. With these challenges in mind, let's explore practical solutions to ensure a smooth and effective presentation experience.

Problem: You need to create a multimedia presentation for a project such as a business proposal, training seminar or creative portfolio. You want to incorporate various digital elements such as

images, videos, animations and interactive features to make the presentation engaging and effective. However, you are facing challenges in integrating these elements effectively and ensuring a seamless presentation experience.

Solution:

- **Check Software Compatibility:** Make sure the multimedia presentation software you are using supports the file formats and features you intend to include, such as video formats, image resolutions, and animation effects.
- **Optimize Media Files:** Optimize large media files such as videos or high-resolution images to reduce file size and improve performance. Compress videos using video editing software or online tools and resize images using image editing software or online converters.
- **Test Presentation Playback:** Before the actual presentation, run extensive tests to ensure that all multimedia elements play smoothly and as intended. Run the presentation on different devices and platforms to identify and fix compatibility issues.

2. Designing Digital Artwork

Designing digital artworks offers limitless opportunities for creativity, but can be difficult to be proficient with digital tools and techniques. Let's explore practical solutions to overcome these obstacles and unlock your artistic potential in the digital world.

Problem: You are interested in digital art and want to create original artwork using digital drawing software and graphics tablets. You dream of exploring your creativity, experimenting with different brushes, colors and techniques to produce visually stunning artwork. However, you face challenges in mastering digital tools and translating your artistic vision into digital artwork.

Solution:

- **Learn Software Basics:** Start by learning the basic features and functions of digital drawing software. Explore tutorials, online guides, and beginner exercises to build a foundation of knowledge and skills.
- **Practice Regularly:** Make time for regular practice sessions where you try out different drawing techniques, tools and effects. Start with simple drawings and gradually work your way up to more complex compositions as you gain confidence and proficiency.
- **Seek Feedback and Support:** Join online communities, forums or art groups where you can share your work, ask for feedback and learn from other artists. Participate in challenges, workshops or collaborative projects to improve your skills and receive constructive criticism.

3. Producing a Podcast or Audio Project

Producing a podcast or an audio project can be an exciting endeavour, but mastering the technical aspects and reaching a wider audience pose significant challenges. Let's explore effective solutions to overcome these obstacles and bring your audio storytelling dreams to life.

Problem: You have a passion for audio storytelling and want to produce a podcast series or an audio project on a topic of interest. You dream of creating compelling narratives, recording interviews, adding background music and sound effects, and publishing your content on digital platforms. However you face challenges in mastering audio editing software, optimizing audio quality, and promoting your podcast to a wider audience.

Solution:

- **Learn Audio Editing Basics:** Learn the basics of audio editing software by exploring tutorials, online courses, or instructional videos. Familiarize yourself with basic features like recording, editing, mixing, and exporting audio files.
- **Improve Audio Quality:** Experiment with microphone placement, room acoustics, and audio settings to get the best sound quality while recording. Use noise reduction tools, equalization and compression techniques to improve audio clarity and remove background noise.
- **Promote Your Podcast:** Develop a marketing strategy to promote your podcast and attract listeners. Use social media platforms, podcast directories, email newsletters, and collaboration opportunities with other podcasters to increase your visibility and grow your audience.

Unlocking Creativity with Digital Storytelling

In today's digital age, storytelling has evolved beyond traditional mediums to encompass a dynamic combination of narrative and technology. Digital storytelling offers a powerful platform for individuals to express their creativity, share personal experiences and engage with audiences in innovative ways. By leveraging digital tools and platforms, storytellers can create engaging stories that captivate and inspire audiences and transcend the boundaries of time and space.

Digital storytelling is not just about conveying information; it's about creating immersive experiences that connect with audiences on a deeper level. Whether telling a personal journey, exploring social issues or delivering educational content, the possibilities are endless. Through the combination of image, video, audio and interactive elements, storytellers can evoke emotions, provoke thoughts and spark meaningful conversations.

The production process of digital storytelling starts with a simple idea: a story waiting to be told. From there, storytellers begin a journey of creativity and discovery, bringing together multimedia elements to bring their vision to life. From scripting to editing to sharing, each step of the process offers opportunities for experimentation, collaboration and growth.

At its core, digital storytelling is a celebration of human expression and creativity. It empowers individuals to reclaim their stories, amplify their voices and connect with others in profound ways. Whether you are an experienced storyteller or a new explorer, digital storytelling invites you to set out on a journey of self-discovery, creativity and connection.

We will explore the art of digital storytelling from inception to execution. We'll explore the essential steps of the storytelling process, uncovering tips, techniques and tools to unlock your creativity and utilize the power of digital technology. Whether you are an educator looking to

engage your learners, a professional looking to develop your brand, or an individual eager to share your story with the world, we will provide you with the knowledge and inspiration to get started on your own digital storytelling adventure.

Let's explore the exciting world of digital storytelling, where imagination knows no boundaries and every story has the potential to change lives. Let's use the power of digital technology to create stories that inspire, educate and empower audiences around the world.

Digital Tools for the Design, Realization and Assessment of Digital Storytelling

The Digital Storytelling production process is as follows:

Step 1. Choose Your Story

Keep your story simple and personal. It could be about a personal journey, a transformation, an achievement, a hobby, social involvement, overcoming adversity, a love story, or a learning experience. Focus on topics that resonate with you emotionally.

Step 2: Gather Your Materials

Start by collecting materials that help illustrate your story. This could include old photos, videos, flyers, or any other items that hold sentimental value. You don't need fancy equipment - anything that evokes emotion will do. Aim for photos with a resolution of at least 1576 x 1152 pixels at 72 dpi for optimal clarity on screen.

Step 3: Begin Writing Your Script

Begin by brainstorming ideas for your story. Aim for a script of around 250 words to create a video lasting two to three minutes. Discussing your ideas with friends and family can provide valuable input. Develop a rough outline for your story and write a script that you will narrate with your voice. Remember, your unique voice adds depth to the story. Don't worry if you find your voice strange when recorded - it's a common experience for everyone.

- Write your script from a personal perspective, ensuring your story reflects your own experiences.
- Avoid editing while drafting your script; focus on capturing your thoughts without interruption.
- Few words and key images are more effective than long sentences.
- Use plain speech and try to reach an emotional depth.
- Like all stories, have a beginning, middle, and end.

The beginning lays the foundation for your story and establishes the tension that drives the narrative forward. The middle reveals the conflicts and challenges encountered along the journey. Finally, the ending reveals an important revelation or insight that serves as the final destination for the narrative. This structure, often referred to as the desire-action-actualization model, maintains focus and momentum throughout the story. There is no room for detours in a succinct three-minute script, where every moment builds towards a compelling conclusion.

Step: 4 Prepare Your Equipment

The more professional you aim to be, the more equipment you may require. Essential items range from a recording device and portable digital recorder to microphones and headphones. While some equipment is optional, certain essentials are necessary, including:

- A desktop computer or a laptop
- A video editing software (Apple iMovie, Adobe Final Cut Pro, Adobe Premiere)

Step 5: Develop a Storyboard

Storyboards have long been utilized by professionals to plan out visual narratives in alignment with voice-overs. While some creators prefer to begin with images before scripting, others opt for a different approach. Storyboarding serves to organize the visual elements and ensure harmony between voice-over narration and visual content.

Here are some tips:

- Limit the number of images to no more than 15 for a two-minute video.
- Display each image on the screen for four to six seconds.
- A minimal number of images is usually sufficient to convey the story effectively.

Step 6: Digitize Your Media

For optimal results, utilize high-quality formats for photos and audio recordings, which may necessitate additional software or equipment. When working with old photos, ensure they are digitized into JPEG format with high resolution to maintain visual clarity and quality in the digital environment.

Step 7: Record a Voice-Over

While the built-in microphone on your device can suffice, professional-grade options are available for higher quality. Speak naturally and avoid sounding scripted. Opt for a quiet environment to minimize background noise, and consider larger rooms with sound-absorbing elements to reduce echoes.

Step 8: Select Appropriate Music

Choose music that complements the rhythm and mood of your story. Instrumental genres such as classical, ambient, folk or jazz without vocals can be effective. Make sure you have the rights to use the music to avoid copyright issues and consider using podsafe sources available through platforms like Google.

Step 9: Edit Your Story

Quality Digital Storytelling can be produced through a variety of free editing software available on the internet. These resources are shown in the table below. A common feature of all video editing programs is the timeline used to create the video; images, video and audio are placed on the timeline so that they can be combined in various ways. Import materials into the program. Bring them into the timeline and match the layout. Use the draft version for an overview of your project. Add the title of the story. If you want to place text over an image, choose a simple font that is easy to read. Add transitions, cross dissolve, visual interest in an image, panning in and out of a photo, etc. Finally, add music as a finishing touch.

App	OS	Link
Animoto	Web	https://animoto.com/
WeVideo	Web	https://www.wevideo.com/
Moovly	Web	https://www.moovly.com/

Powtoon	Web	https://www.powtoon.com/home/?
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Step 10: Publish Your Story

You can share your story on a blog or dedicated destination site such as Ourmedia. If you want to share with some friends or family, choose a peer-to-peer network.

http://digitalstorytelling.coe.uh.edu/example_stories.cfm: This website contains examples of different storytelling activities created by learners.

<http://digitalstoryhub.org/>: This website has examples of storytelling videos from a variety of topics. The homepage shares a quote by Muriel Rukeyser: The universe is not made of atoms; it's made of tiny stories.

The modern workforce demands 21st-century skills, making it essential for curricula to equip learners with competence in various areas. One of the ways of improving learners' 21st-century skills is digital storytelling. This approach offers several benefits, including:

- Boosting learners' confidence in communication
- Encouraging them to become active creators of media
- Facilitating deeper understanding across all curriculum areas
- Merging traditional storytelling practices with innovative technology

Engaging in digital storytelling allows learners to internalize information and recognize the impact of their projects beyond the classroom. By sharing their stories digitally, they enable others to hear their voices and perspectives.

As you watch the video, consider how technology facilitates the cultivation of the 4Cs (communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity) in the creation of storytelling activities.

https://www.ted.com/talks/joe_sabia_the_technology_of_storytelling

Sites and Apps Available for Digital Storytelling

[Animaker Class](#): This website offers a user-friendly platform for creating animated stories. Learners can use the drag-and-drop tools as well as other features such as group management to craft stories on various topics.

[Book Creator](#): The mobile app enables you to put together eBooks and digital stories with text, audio, images, and video. The site helps to combine text, images, audio and video to create interactive stories, digital portfolios, research journals, science reports, comic adventures, etc.

[Cloud Stop Motion](#): This browser-based stop-motion animation tool is ideal for digital storytelling on any device. It offers powerful features for creating captivating narratives through animation.

[HeadUP](#): It provides a platform for creating visually appealing stories across various subjects. The website also hosts a collection of digital stories covering diverse topics.

[Tellagami](#): With Tellagami, users can craft short stories by creating personalized avatars and recording audio narration. It's a simple yet effective tool for storytelling.

[Plotagon](#): Plotagon is an award-winning storytelling tool for all ages. Users can select scenes, create their actors, write their stories, and let Plotagon make it come to life. Stories can be saved and shared easily.

[Speech Journal](#): This iPad app that pairs recorded audio with a digital picture from a user's iPhoto library to create a story. It's a creative way to combine audio narration with visual elements.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Purpose	The purpose of this practical activity is to engage participants in hands-on learning to develop their skills in creatively using digital technologies, specifically focusing on digital storytelling as a means of expression and communication.
Title of the practical activity:	Digital Storytelling Workshop: Unleashing Creativity with Technology
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults interested in exploring digital storytelling as a creative medium.
Learning outcomes	<p>Understand the concept of digital storytelling and its applications.</p> <p>Gain practical skills in planning, creating, and sharing digital stories using technology.</p> <p>Enhance creativity and communication skills through the development of digital storytelling projects.</p> <p>Explore various digital tools and platforms for creating multimedia narratives.</p> <p>Reflect on the impact of digital storytelling on personal expression and communication.</p>
Materials	<p>Computers or laptops with internet access</p> <p>Digital cameras or smartphones for capturing images (optional)</p> <p>Headphones with microphones for audio recording (optional)</p>

	<p>Presentation slides or handouts outlining the basics of digital storytelling</p> <p>Sample digital storytelling projects for inspiration</p> <p>Digital storytelling software or apps (e.g., Book Creator, Plotagon, Tellagami)</p> <p>Flipchart or whiteboard with markers</p> <p>Evaluation forms for feedback</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Welcome participants to the workshop and introduce the concept of digital storytelling. Highlight the power of storytelling as a means of expression and communication in the digital age.</p> <p>Facilitate a brief discussion to explore participants' experiences with storytelling and their interest in using digital tools for creative expression. Encourage them to share any previous experiences with digital storytelling, if applicable.</p> <p>Explore: Present an overview of digital storytelling, including its definition, elements, and potential applications. Use examples of digital stories to illustrate different styles and formats.</p> <p>Introduce participants to various digital storytelling tools and platforms available. Provide a demonstration of how to use a selected tool or app to create a simple digital story.</p> <p>Explain: Guide participants through the process of planning a digital storytelling project. Discuss key steps such as choosing a story topic, gathering media assets, scripting the narrative, and selecting appropriate digital tools.</p> <p>Review best practices for creating engaging digital stories, including storytelling techniques, visual design principles, and audio recording tips. Emphasize the importance of creativity and authenticity in storytelling.</p> <p>Elaborate: Divide participants into small groups and assign each group a digital storytelling project topic or theme. Encourage groups to brainstorm ideas, outline their stories, and select relevant media assets for their projects.</p> <p>Provide hands-on support and guidance as participants work on their digital storytelling projects. Circulate among the groups to answer questions, provide feedback, and offer technical assistance as needed.</p> <p>Evaluate: Reconvene as a larger group and allow each group to present their digital storytelling projects to the rest of the participants. Encourage constructive feedback and discussion on the strengths and areas for improvement of each project.</p> <p>Facilitate a reflection session where participants share their insights and takeaways from the workshop. Ask participants to discuss how digital</p>

	<p>storytelling can be applied in their personal or academic lives moving forward.</p> <p>Distribute evaluation forms and invite participants to provide feedback on the workshop content, format, and facilitation. Use this feedback to inform future workshops and improve the learning experience.</p>
Methods	<p>Presentation and discussion on digital storytelling concepts and techniques</p> <p>Hands-on practice with digital storytelling tools and platforms</p> <p>Group brainstorming and project planning activities</p> <p>Individual and group work on digital storytelling projects</p> <p>Peer feedback and reflection sessions</p>
Evaluation	<p>Assess participants based on their engagement in group activities, creativity in storytelling, proficiency in using digital tools, and ability to present their projects effectively. Use evaluation forms to gather feedback on the workshop content, facilitation, and overall learning experience. Adjust future workshops based on participant feedback and areas for improvement.</p>
Reference, events and further reading	<p>Websites and apps mentioned in the text for creating digital stories</p> <p>TED Talk: Joe Sabia: The technology of storytelling</p> <p>Further reading on digital storytelling techniques and best practices</p>

5.4. Identifying Digital Competence Gaps

In this section, we explore the important skill of identifying digital competence gaps. This skill enables individuals to assess their competence in effectively navigating the digital environment. By recognizing areas of strength and areas for improvement, learners can tailor their learning journey to address specific gaps and build on existing competencies. Let's explore how you can develop your digital skills and address competency gaps to succeed in today's digital age.

Understanding Digital Competency Gaps

Start by understanding what digital competence means. It encompasses not only technical skills, but also the ability to critically evaluate information, communicate effectively and adapt to technological changes. Consider your current skill set and identify areas where you may lack competence or experience with specific digital tools, platforms or applications.

Examples of Digital Skills Assessment Resources:

- LinkedIn Learning: Offers a wide range of courses and skills assessments in a variety of digital disciplines, including software proficiency, data analytics and digital marketing.

- Coursera: Offers online courses from leading universities and companies, as well as assessments to measure your ability to understand and apply digital concepts.
- Udemy: Offers affordable courses on digital skills, often accompanied by quizzes and assignments to measure your understanding.

Self-Assessment Techniques

Conduct a comprehensive self-assessment of your digital skills by assessing your proficiency in specific areas such as technical skills, information literacy and communication skills.

Utilize Assessment Tools

Utilize online assessment tools and resources designed to measure digital competence, including digital literacy quizzes, skills-based assessments, and surveys/questionnaires.

Seek Feedback and Guidance

Seek feedback from peers, mentors or instructors to gain valuable insights into your digital competency gaps. Collaborate on projects or assignments that require digital skills and ask for constructive feedback on your performance.

Continuous Learning and Improvement

Recognize that digital competence is an ongoing journey and commit to continuous learning and improvement. Stay up-to-date on new technologies, trends and best practices in your field through online courses, webinars and industry publications.

1. Confusion with Email Management

Effective email management is essential both personally and professionally, but many people struggle to organize their inboxes effectively. Let's explore practical solutions to overcome the challenges of email clutter and organize your communication workflow.

Problem: You are responsible for managing email communication for business or personal purposes. But you struggle to organize emails, create filters and folders, and maintain inbox cleanliness. This leads to cluttered and inefficient email management practices, resulting in missed messages, overlooked tasks and frustration.

Solution:

- **Check Email Workflow:** Conduct a thorough check of your email workflow to identify inefficiencies, problem spots, and areas for improvement. Analyze your current email habits, folder structure, tagging system, and archiving practices.
- **Implement Email Organization Strategies:** Explore email organization strategies such as inbox reset, email filtering, folder categorization and priority tagging. Develop a systematic approach to prioritizing, replying and archiving emails to streamline your workflow.
- **Use Email Productivity Tools:** Explore email productivity tools and features offered by your email service provider or third-party applications. These can include email scheduling,

snoozing, reminders, and integration with task management platforms to improve efficiency and organization.

2. Lack of Cybersecurity Awareness

Being informed about cybersecurity practices is essential to navigate the digital environment safely. Let's explore strategies to increase your cybersecurity awareness and protect yourself from online threats.

Problem: You regularly use digital devices and online services for various activities such as browsing the internet, online shopping, and social media interaction. However, you have limited knowledge and awareness of cybersecurity best practices, such as password management, phishing awareness, and data protection. This exposes you to potential risks such as identity theft, malware infections, and financial fraud..

Solution:

- **Educate Yourself on Cybersecurity Basics:** Take proactive steps to educate yourself on cybersecurity basics such as password hijacking, recognizing phishing attempts, and protecting personal information online. Explore online resources, cybersecurity awareness campaigns and reputable educational materials.
- **Activate Security Features:** Enable security features and settings offered by digital devices, apps and online services to increase protection against cyber threats. These include two-factor authentication, encryption, automatic software updates, and antivirus software.
- **Practice Secure Online Behavior:** Adopt safe online practices such as creating strong and unique passwords, avoiding suspicious links and attachments, verifying the authenticity of websites, and being careful when sharing personal information online.

3. Efficient Task and Deadline Management

To become a master of effective task and deadline management, it is crucial to identify your challenges and adopt effective strategies. Let's explore practical solutions to improve your task prioritization and deadline management skills for more productivity and less stress.

Problem: You want to keep track of important deadlines and tasks efficiently. However, you're unsure about the best approach to manage your tasks and deadlines effectively, leading to potential missed deadlines and increased stress.

Solution:

- **Identify Specific Areas of Difficulty:** Identify specific challenges you face in managing tasks and deadlines. Determine if the difficulty lies in prioritization, time management, or organization of tasks and deadlines.
- **Seek Learning Resources:** Explore online articles, books, or courses on effective task and deadline management techniques. Look for resources that offer strategies for prioritizing tasks, setting realistic deadlines, and avoiding procrastination.

- **Practice Regularly:** Implement a task management system, such as a to-do list or digital task manager, to organize your tasks and deadlines. Experiment with different prioritization methods, such as the Eisenhower Matrix or the ABC prioritization technique. Dedicate time each day to review and update your task list, adjusting priorities and deadlines as needed.

Starting a new technological journey can be both exciting and intimidating, especially for those less familiar with digital devices. To understand the importance of addressing digital competency gaps, let's explore a real-life scenario. Meet Roberto, a retiree who finds himself struggling with his new smartphone, feeling overwhelmed by its features and functions. Although eager to learn, Roberto lacks the confidence and knowledge needed to effectively navigate his device. Let's explore practical steps to address digital competence gaps and use technology more confidently and effectively.

Case Study:

Roberto is a 65-year-old retiree who recently received a smartphone as a gift from his children. Despite his initial excitement, Roberto feels overwhelmed and intimidated by the device due to his limited experience with technology. He struggles with basic tasks such as turning the phone on and off, navigating the home screen and accessing the settings menu. Roberto is eager to learn how to use his smartphone effectively, but lacks the confidence and knowledge to do so.

Steps to Address Digital Competency Gaps

Assess Current Skills : Start by assessing your current smartphone-related skills. Take some time to explore the device and identify areas where you feel less confident.

Introduction to Smartphone Basics

Now, let's start with the basics. To turn on the phone, locate the power button on the side or top of the device. Press and hold until the screen lights up. To turn it off, simply press and hold the same button again.

Next, let's familiarize ourselves with the home screen. This is where you will find all your apps and shortcuts. You can swipe left or right to access different screens.

Connecting to Wi-Fi and Email Setup

To connect to Wi-Fi, go to the Settings app. Tap on "Wi-Fi" and select your home network from the list. Enter the password if requested.

Now, let's set up your email. Open the Email app on your phone and follow the instructions to add your email account. You will need to enter your email address and password.

Web Surfing and App Usage

You have several options for surfing on the internet. You can search through various browsers. To browse the internet, you can type a web address or search term in the address bar at the top.

In the image on the right, you will see the icons referring to the app store, whether you have an Android or iOS system smartphone.

To download apps, simply locate and open the Play Store app, recognizable by its distinctive colored triangle icon. From there, you can easily search for specific apps by typing their names into the search bar. Once you find the desired app, simply tap on it to initiate the installation process. For instance, if you're looking for a photo editing app like Picsart, it will automatically install on your smartphone and appear on the main screen for easy access.

Camera Usage and Photo Storage

Now let's explore the camera app. You can find it on the home screen or in the app drawer. Tap the camera icon to open it. You can take photos by pressing the shutter button.

Note that you have several options, including taking a photo or recording a video. After saving the photo to your mobile phone gallery, you can edit it.

To store your photos, open the Gallery app. Here you can view your photos and organize them into albums.

Practice and Reinforcement

The best way to learn is to practice regularly. Spend some time every day using your smartphone and exploring its features. Don't worry if you make mistakes - this is part of the learning process. If you have any questions or need help along the way, don't hesitate to ask your family and friends.

Building Confidence and Independence

With constant practice and exploration, you will soon become more confident and independent. Keep up the good work!

Identifying digital competence gaps is a critical step towards personal and professional growth in the digital age. By assessing your current skill set, embracing a growth mindset, utilizing assessment tools, seeking feedback, and committing to continuous learning, you can bridge competency gaps and unlock new opportunities for success in today's digital world. Remember, the journey to digital mastery is not a sprint but a marathon, and every step you take towards enhancing your digital skills brings you closer to realizing your full potential.

Conclusion

The journey to develop digital literacy and problem-solving skills involves a structured approach encompassing several key components. From understanding the digital environment and identifying technological needs to the creative use of digital technologies, each element contributes to building a comprehensive skill set. Through troubleshooting steps tailored to address specific challenges, learners can effectively overcome obstacles. Exploring relevant learning resources empowers individuals to acquire new knowledge and development strategies. Regular practice and application of learned concepts play a vital role in consolidating skills and promoting continuous growth. By adopting these principles and applying practical activities, learners can embark on a transformative journey towards greater digital competence and problem-solving acumen, ultimately empowering themselves to succeed in the ever-evolving digital world.

Practical activity for face-to-face teaching:

This activity/exercise has been created to practice the newly developed skills

Title	Digital Storytelling Workshop
Purpose	The purpose of this activity is to teach participants digital storytelling skills by guiding them through the process of creating their multimedia narratives.
Time	90 minutes
Target group	Adults 55+ educators, trainers, or anyone interested in developing digital storytelling skills.
Learning outcomes	Participants will learn the basics of digital storytelling. Participants will gain hands-on experience in creating a digital story.

	Participants will understand the importance of storytelling in various contexts.
Materials	<p>Laptops or tablets with internet access</p> <p>Headphones with microphones (optional)</p> <p>Images or videos related to personal stories or topics of interest (participants can bring their own or use provided resources)</p> <p>Paper and pens for brainstorming</p>
Facilitation steps	<p>Engage: Start by discussing the importance of storytelling in education, business, and personal expression.</p> <p>Share examples of impactful digital stories from various sources to inspire participants.</p> <p>Explore: Introduce participants to the concept of digital storytelling and its components (e.g., narrative, multimedia elements, editing).</p> <p>Provide an overview of digital storytelling tools and platforms mentioned in the session materials.</p> <p>Allow participants to explore some of the recommended digital storytelling apps or websites briefly.</p> <p>Explain: Guide participants through the steps of creating a digital story:</p> <p>Choosing a story or topic: Participants can select a personal experience, a social issue, or any other topic they're passionate about.</p> <p>Gathering materials: Encourage participants to collect images, videos, or audio clips related to their chosen story.</p> <p>Writing a script: Assist participants in developing a script that outlines the narrative of their digital story.</p> <p>Recording voice-over (if applicable): Guide recording clear and expressive voice-overs to accompany the visuals.</p> <p>Editing the digital story: Demonstrate basic editing techniques using the chosen digital storytelling tool.</p> <p>Elaborate: Allow participants to work individually or in pairs to create their own digital stories.</p> <p>Provide assistance and guidance as needed, answering questions and troubleshooting technical issues.</p> <p>Encourage creativity and experimentation with multimedia elements to enhance the storytelling experience.</p> <p>Evaluate: Facilitate a sharing session where participants can present their digital stories to the group.</p> <p>Encourage feedback and constructive criticism from peers to help participants improve their storytelling skills.</p>

	Reflect on the workshop experience and discuss how participants can apply digital storytelling techniques in their professional or personal projects.
Methods	Hands-on practice with digital storytelling tools Group discussion and sharing sessions Peer feedback and evaluation
Evaluation	Participants' ability to create engaging digital stories Participation and engagement during the workshop Feedback received from peers and facilitators
References	Additional resources on digital storytelling techniques and tools Relevant workshops or events related to digital media and storytelling Websites or platforms for sharing digital stories created during the workshop

Video links for Problem Solving

Resources from the Internet

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6iTw6e8w74Q>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iCv7GUETSk8>

Evaluation questions:

4 Multiple Choice Questions

1. What is the initial step to take if your smartphone fails to connect to the Wi-Fi network at home?
 - a) Restart your smartphone and try reconnecting
 - b) Check Wi-Fi settings on your smartphone
 - c) Contact your Internet Service Provider (ISP)
 - d) Reset your Wi-Fi router

2. You need to organize a team project. Which digital tool would be most effective?
 - a) Sending emails with attachments.
 - b) Using a collaborative project management tool.
 - c) Conducting in-person meetings.

d) Utilizing a cloud-based document-sharing platform.

3. You're interested in organizing your digital photos for easier access. What strategy would you employ?

a) Create basic folders for different photo categories.

b) Utilize photo management software with tagging features.

c) Implement a cloud-based solution for automatic organization and access.

d) Keep all photos in a single unorganized folder.

4. What's the most effective approach to improve the management of numerous email accounts?

a) Checking emails randomly throughout the day.

b) Using a unified email management tool.

c) Creating separate folders for each email.

d) Forwarding all emails to a single account.

Matching Questions

Recognizing and addressing technical issues	Troubleshooting
Exploring innovative uses of digital tools	Creativity

Enhancing the ability to match needs with tech solutions	Identifying needs
Recognizing areas needing improvement	Digital Competence Gaps

ANSWERS FOR MODULE CONTENT RETENTION

Module 1: information and data literacy

Multiple Choice Questions

1. Which of the following best defines digital social inclusion?
 - A) Limiting access to digital technologies and resources.
 - B) Ensuring fair and meaningful use of digital technologies and online resources for all individuals.**
 - C) Excluding certain groups from engaging in online communities.
 - D) Fostering competition for digital opportunities and resources.

2. What is the primary purpose of the CRAAP Test criteria in evaluating information sources?
 - A) To determine the popularity of the information source on social media.
 - B) To assess the entertainment value of the information.
 - C) To evaluate information sources' credibility, relevance, and authority.**
 - D) To promote misinformation and disinformation online.

3. How can adult learners enhance their skills in managing data, information, and digital content?
 - A) By avoiding technological tools and platforms.
 - B) By prioritising security and privacy in data management practices.**
 - C) By ignoring ongoing education and adaptation in the field of technology.
 - D) By limiting access to digital resources and opportunities.

4. What is the significance of lifelong learning in the context of digital literacy?
 - A) Lifelong learning is unnecessary in today's digital landscape.
 - B) Lifelong learning promotes adaptation to the rapidly evolving field of technology.**
 - C) Lifelong learning restricts individuals from acquiring digital literacy skills.
 - D) Lifelong learning hinders effective data management practices.

Match each term with its corresponding definition:

Terms	Definitions
Digital Inclusion Social	Ensures fair and meaningful use of digital technologies and online resources for all individuals.
CRAAP Test	Criteria used to evaluate information sources' credibility, relevance, and authority.

Module 2. Communication and Collaboration

4 Multiple Choice Questions

What enables virtual meetings and videoconferencing for real-time interaction?

- a) Social media platforms
- b) E-commerce websites
- c) Video conferencing applications**
- d) Online banking services

Which tool allows for collaboration in real-time on documents and projects online?

- a) Social media platforms
- b) Google Workspace**
- c) Online gaming platforms
- d) E-commerce websites

What has digital technology facilitated in terms of political participation?

- a) Decreased access to political information
- b) Easier access to political information**
- c) Restricted discussions on public affairs
- d) Decreased citizen participation in political life

What is crucial for effective online collaboration in geographically distributed teams?

- a) Using the latest gaming platforms
- b) Ignoring time zone differences
- c) Awareness of cultural and linguistic differences**
- d) Avoiding the use of project management tools

2 Matching Questions

A basic principle of netiquette in online communication	Respect and courtesy
A key element of managing your digital identity effectively	Privacy protection

enables individuals to engage in social, political, and civic affairs through digital technologies	platforms for reporting irregularities and monitoring elections
digital technologies affect project management and teamwork	enabling real-time collaboration and resource sharing

Module 3. Digital content creation

Multiple Choice Questions

1. Which of the following is NOT a key function of copyright in society?
 - a) Protecting the interests of creators
 - b) Promoting cultural development
 - c) Restricting access to creative works**
 - d) Balancing the interests of creators and the public

2. What is the primary purpose of Creative Commons licenses?
 - a) To restrict access to copyrighted works
 - b) To grant exclusive rights to creators
 - c) To allow creators to specify usage terms for their works**
 - d) To eliminate copyright protection for digital content

3. Which programming concept is used to store data that can be manipulated and retrieved throughout a program?
 - a) Control Structures
 - b) Functions
 - c) Variables**
 - d) Data Types

4. What is the significance of programming skills in the digital age?
 - a) They limit career opportunities in various fields.
 - b) They discourage creativity and innovation.
 - c) They empower individuals to understand and manipulate the digital environment.**
 - d) They restrict access to digital tools and applications.

Matching Questions

1. Match the type of Creative Commons license with its corresponding description:

1. CC BY-NC	a) Allows others to use the work for non-commercial purposes only.
2. CC BY-SA	b) Allows others to use the work and create derivative works, but they must distribute their contributions under the same license.

2. Match the key programming concept with its description:

1. Variables	b) Used to store data that can be manipulated and retrieved throughout a program.
2. Functions	a) Reusable blocks of code that perform a specific task.

Module 4. Safety

Multiple Choice Questions

1. Which of the following is NOT a good practice for protecting your device from potential threats?
 - a. Keeping your software up-to-date
 - b. Using strong and unique passwords
 - c. Sharing your login credentials with others**
 - d. Installing antivirus software

2. What is the primary purpose of encryption?
 - a. To keep your device's software updated
 - b. To create strong passwords
 - c. To safeguard your important data from unauthorised access**
 - d. To identify potential threats

3. Which of the following is NOT an example of personal data?
 - a. Your name
 - b. Your address
 - c. Your favourite colour**
 - d. Your browsing history

4. What is the best way to respond to cyberbullying?
 - a. Ignore it and hope it goes away
 - b. Retaliate with harsher comments
 - c. Block and report the abusive behaviour**
 - d. share personal information about the bully

5. What is the primary reason for balancing digital and physical activities?

- a. To improve your posture
- b. To protect your device from threats

c. To nurture your overall well-being

- d. To create stronger passwords

6. Which of the following is NOT a strategy for minimising your digital environmental footprint?

- a. Decluttering and deleting unnecessary files
- b. Adopting energy-efficient devices

c. Leaving devices plugged in and charging at all times

- d. Responsibly disposing of e-waste

Matching Questions

What is the purpose of a privacy policy?	To outline how a company will collect, store, and use your data
Which of the following is an example of a phishing scam?	Receiving an email from your bank asking for your login credentials
What is the benefit of incorporating movement breaks into your daily routine?	It combats the toll of excessive screen time on your body
Which of the following is NOT a practical strategy for safeguarding your data?	Sharing your login credentials with trusted friends and family

Module 5. Problem-solving

4 Multiple Choice Questions

1. What is the initial step to take if your smartphone fails to connect to the Wi-Fi network at home?

a) Restart your smartphone and try reconnecting

b) Check Wi-Fi settings on your smartphone

c) Contact your Internet Service Provider (ISP)

d) Reset your Wi-Fi router

2. You need to organize a team project. Which digital tool would be most effective?

a) Sending emails with attachments.

b) Using a collaborative project management tool.

c) Conducting in-person meetings.

d) Utilizing a cloud-based document-sharing platform.

3. You're interested in organizing your digital photos for easier access. What strategy would you employ?

a) Create basic folders for different photo categories.

b) Utilize photo management software with tagging features.

c) Implement a cloud-based solution for automatic organization and access.

d) Keep all photos in a single unorganized folder.

4. What's the most effective approach to improve the management of numerous email accounts?

a) Checking emails randomly throughout the day.

b) Using a unified email management tool.

c) Creating separate folders for each email.

d) Forwarding all emails to a single account.

Matching Questions

Recognizing and addressing technical issues	Troubleshooting
Exploring innovative uses of digital tools	Creativity

Enhancing the ability to match needs with tech solutions	Identifying needs
Recognizing areas needing improvement	Digital Competence Gaps

BIBLIOGRAPHY / REFERENCES

- Althibyani, H. A., & Al-Zahrani, A. M. (2023). Investigating the Effect of Students' Knowledge, Beliefs, and Digital Citizenship Skills on Preventing Cybercrime [Article]. *Sustainability*, 15(15), Article 11512. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151511512>
- Aparac-Jelušić, T. (2011). Digital content creation: A global view on curriculum design. *Proceedings of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*.
- Ashraf, A., Taha, Bajwa, N. U. H., Konig, C. J., Javed, M., Mustafa, M., & Usenix, A. (2023, 2023 Aug 07-08). "Stalking is immoral but not illegal": Understanding Security, Cyber Crimes and Threats in Pakistan. [Proceedings of the nineteenth symposium on usable privacy and security, soups 2023]. 19th Symposium on Usable Privacy and Security (SOUPS), Anaheim, CA.
- Boyle, J. (2008). *The Public Domain: Enclosing the Commons of the Mind*. Yale University Press.
- Broda E., Strömbäck J. Misinformation, disinformation, and fake news: lessons from an interdisciplinary, systematic literature review, *Annals of the International Communication Association*, P.1-28, 2024, Routledge doi 10.1080/23808985.2024.2323736 <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/23808985.2024.2323736?needAccess=true>
- Bybee, R. W. (2013). *The BSCS 5E instructional model: Creating teachable moments*. NSTA Press. <https://static.nsta.org/pdfs/samples/PB356Xweb.pdf>
- Bybee, R. W. (2013). *The BSCS 5E instructional model: Creating teachable moments*. NSTA Press. <https://static.nsta.org/pdfs/samples/PB356Xweb.pdf>
- Cadavid, J., Moller, M. B., Pedersen, C. S., Bech, S., van Waterschoot, T., & Ostergaard, J. (2024). Performance of low-frequency sound zones with very fast room impulse response measurements [Article]. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 155(1), 757-768. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0024519>
- Creative Commons. (n.d.). About the Licenses. Retrieved from <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>
- Diteeyont, W., & Ku, H.-Y. (2021). Internet literacy among the elderly in Thailand [Article]. *Educational Media International*, 58(3), 248-260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2021.1976829>
- Erfani, K. (2023a). Age, Place, and Health: Exploring the Impact of Environmental and Technological Innovations on Enhancing Quality of Life in Older Adults (Publication Number 9798380371735) [Dissertation/Thesis, <Go to ISI>://PQDT:85369221
- Erfani, K. (2023b). Age, Place, and Health: Exploring the Impact of Environmental and Technological Innovations on Enhancing Quality of Life in Older Adults (Publication Number 9798380371735) [Dissertation/Thesis, <Go to ISI>://PQDT:85369221
- Erfani, K. (2023c). Age, Place, and Health: Exploring the Impact of Environmental and Technological Innovations on Enhancing Quality of Life in Older Adults (Publication Number 9798380371735) [Dissertation/Thesis, <Go to ISI>://PQDT:85369221
- European Commission. (2018). *The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/digcomp>

Flauzino, K. D. L., Pimentel, M. D. G. C., Batistoni, S. S. T., Zaine, I., Vieira, L. O. B., Rodrigues, K. R. D. H., & Cachioni, M. (2020). Digital Literacy for Older Adults: perceptions about teaching-learning. *Educação & Realidade*, 45.

Ford, J. S. (2007). *Programming for the Absolute Beginner*.

Funded extension request for "Expanding recovery support for emerging adults with alcohol use disorder: Training in the science of social network sites". (2023). [Awarded Grant].

Graham-Bruno, R., Stickrod, M. A. A., & Parker, V. T. (2023). Constraints on *Cirsium hydrophilum* var. *hydrophilum*, the Suisun thistle, an endangered tidal wetland species [Article]. *Wetlands Ecology and Management*, 31(3), 347-365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11273-023-09920-9>

Hedenmo, Otto. (2024). What are the connections between collaboration values and communication practices? An investigation exploring collaborators' perceptions of supports and constraints in collaboration practice. *Nordicom Review*. 45. 56-80. 10.2478/nor-2024-0004.

Hendricks-Sturup, R. M., & Lu, C. Y. Y. (2023). A survey of United States adult privacy perspectives and willingness to share real-world data [Article]. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*, 7(1), Article e64. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cts.2023.4>

Hödl, T., Myrach, T. Content Creators Between Platform Control and User Autonomy. *Bus Inf Syst Eng* 65, 497–519 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-023-00808-9>

Hoose, F., & Rosenbohm, S. (2023). Self-representation as platform work: Stories about working as social media content creators. *Convergence*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565231185863>

Huang, Ying & Engels, Tim & Wagner, Caroline & Bu, Yi. (2024). International collaboration and communication. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377588514>

Hummel, K., Ryherd, E., Cheng, X., & Lowndes, B. (2023a). Relating clustered noise data to hospital patient satisfaction [Article]. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 154(2), 1239-1247. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0020760>

Hummel, K., Ryherd, E., Cheng, X., & Lowndes, B. (2023b). Relating clustered noise data to hospital patient satisfaction [Article]. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 154(2), 1239-1247. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0020760>

Hunt, A., & Thomas, D. (2019). *The Pragmatic Programmer: Your Journey to Mastery*.

Inno4impact (n.d.). Designing a distance education programme and level 5 programme in the field of youth work. Inno4impact.eu. Retrieved March 11, 2024, from <https://inno4impact.eu/training/>

Johansson, T., Tishelman, C., Eriksson, L. E., Cohen, J., & Goliath, I. (2023). Factors associated with death literacy among Swedish adults: A cross-sectional exploratory study [Article; Early Access]. *Palliative & Supportive Care*, Article Pii s1478951523000548. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1478951523000548>

Kohler, Minttu. (2022). Collaboration and communication in blended learning environments. *Frontiers in Education*. 7. 10.3389/feduc.2022.980445.

Kim, T. K., & Choi, M. (2019). Older adults' willingness to share their personal and health information when adopting healthcare technology and services [Article]. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 126, 86-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.03.010>

Knight, R. (2019, March 26). Top 20 most annoying tech problems. *The Independent*. <https://www.independent.co.uk/tech/tech-gadget-break-anger-top-problems-survey-a8840781.html>

Lakhan, A., Hamouda, H., Abdulkareem, K. H., Alyahya, S., & Mohammed, M. A. (2024a). Digital healthcare framework for patients with disabilities based on deep federated learning schemes [Article]. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 169, Article 107845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbimed.2023.107845>

Lakhan, A., Hamouda, H., Abdulkareem, K. H., Alyahya, S., & Mohammed, M. A. (2024b). Digital healthcare framework for patients with disabilities based on deep federated learning schemes [Article]. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 169, Article 107845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbimed.2023.107845>

Landøy, Ane & Popa, Daniela & Repanovici, Angela. (2020). *Information Evaluation*. 10.1007/978-3-030-34258-6_7.

Lessig, L. (2004). *Free Culture: How Big Media Uses Technology and the Law to Lock Down Culture and Control Creativity*. Penguin Books.

Liang, C., Subramaniam, P., Goh, N. S. M. R., Wai, T. K., & Moustafa, A. A. (2023). Digital Device Use, Risk of Cognitive Impairment, and Cognition in Healthy Older Adults: The Role of Cognitive Reserve [Article]. *Healthcare*, 11(21), Article 2822. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11212822>

Lichtenberg, Sophia & Potter, Kaledio. (2024). Collaboration and Communication: Foster collaboration between IT, DevOps, and healthcare professionals to bridge the gap between technical and clinical expertise. *Information Journal of Library and Information Science*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378342226>

Lyon, G. (2024a). Informational inequality: the role of resources and attributes in information security awareness [Article]. *Information and Computer Security*, 32(2), 197-217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ics-04-2023-0063>

Lyon, G. (2024b). Informational inequality: the role of resources and attributes in information security awareness [Article]. *Information and Computer Security*, 32(2), 197-217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ics-04-2023-0063>

Maher, N. A., Senders, J. T., Hulsbergen, A. F. C., Lamba, N., Parker, M., Onnela, J.-P., . . . Broekman, M. L. D. (2019). Passive data collection and use in healthcare: A systematic review of ethical issues [Review]. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 129, 242-247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.06.015>

Mallick, D. B., Bradford, B. C., & Baraniuk, R. (2023, 2023Jul 20-22). Secure Education and Learning Research at Scale with OpenStax Kinetic. [Proceedings of the tenth ACM conference on learning @ scale, l@s 2023]. 10th ACM Conference on Learning at Scale (L at S), Univ Copenhagen, Copenhagen, DENMARK.

Matthes, E. (2019). *Python Crash Course: A Hands-On, Project-Based Introduction to Programming*.

Meriam Library California State University, Chico -
<https://library.csuchico.edu/sites/default/files/craap-test.pdf>

Muhammed T S, Mathew SK. The disaster of misinformation: a review of research in social media. *Int J Data Sci Anal.* 2022;13(4):271-285. doi: 10.1007/s41060-022-00311-6. Epub 2022 Feb 15. PMID: 35194559; PMCID: PMC8853081.

Nace, T. (2023, January 16). How to find and change Instagram account settings. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aD7n00aPmkM>

Nicholas E. Johnson, Jeremy C. Short, Jeffrey A. Chandler, Samantha L. Jordan, Introducing the contentpreneur: Making the case for research on content creation-based online platforms, *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, Volume 18, 2022, e00328, ISSN 2352-6734, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2022.e00328>.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352673422000269>)

Nur Akarcay, Y., Ochoa Siguencia, L., StafECKa, S., Ozer, O., Vindaca, O., Bilger, N., Marzano, G., StafECKis, G., Ispinar Akcayoglu. Duygu, Akilli, A., Kaupuzs, A., & Ochoa-Daderska, R. (2022). Curriculum for adult learners. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570345>

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Kopiec, Agnieszka. (2019). Crowdsourcing solutions for supporting collaborative learning: a case of undergraduate management students. 10.21125/edulearn.2019.1489.

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Marzano, Gilberto & Kaczmarczyk, Patrycja. (2017). Online work-space-shared management to support collaborative learning. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323398305>

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Marzano, Gilberto & Kaczmarczyk, Patrycja. (2017). Online work-space-shared management to support collaborative learning. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323398305>

Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Ochoa-Daderska, Renata & Sánchez-García, Javier & Akarcay, Yeliz & Velinov, Eng. Emil & Kopiec, Agnieszka. (2020). Adult Social Inclusion in a Digital Environment: Professional Use of information and communication technology-based solutions for social integration. 10.5281/zenodo.3737920.

Oh, S. S., Kim, K. A., Kim, M., Oh, J., Chu, S. H., & Choi, J. (2021). Measurement of digital literacy among older adults: systematic review. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 23(2), e26145.

Potter, Kaledio & Robert, Abill. (2024). Collaboration and Communication: Foster collaboration between IT, DevOps, and healthcare professionals to bridge the gap between technical and clinical expertise. *Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378213032>

Putri, Cynthia & Sedyati, Retna & Zulianto, Mukhamad. (2023). Students' collaboration and communication skills with problem-based learning model. *Jurnal Inovasi dan Teknologi Pembelajaran*. 10. 225. 10.17977/um031v10i32023p225.

Putri, Cynthia & Sedyati, Retna & Zulianto, Mukhamad. (2023). Students' collaboration and communication skills with problem-based learning model. *Jurnal Inovasi dan Teknologi Pembelajaran*. 10. 225. 10.17977/um031v10i32023p225.

- Rakow, K. E., Upsher, R. J., Foster, J. L. H., Byrom, N. C., & Dommett, E. J. (2023a). Student perspectives on their digital footprint in virtual learning environments [Article]. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1208671. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1208671>
- Rakow, K. E., Upsher, R. J., Foster, J. L. H., Byrom, N. C., & Dommett, E. J. (2023b). Student perspectives on their digital footprint in virtual learning environments [Article]. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1208671. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1208671>
- Redmiles, E. M., & Hargittai, E. (2019). New Phone, Who Dis? Modelling Millennials' Backup Behavior [Article]. *Acm Transactions on the Web*, 13(1), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3208105>
- San Diego County Office of Education (n.d.). 5E Model of Instruction. Sdcoe.net. Retrieved March 10, 2024, from <https://www.sdcoe.net/ngss/evidence-based-practices/5e-model-of-instruction>
- San Diego County Office of Education (n.d.). *5E Model of Instruction*. Sdcoe.net. Retrieved March 10, 2024, from <https://www.sdcoe.net/ngss/evidence-based-practices/5e-model-of-instruction>
- Scott, K. M., Nerminathan, A., Alexander, S., Phelps, M., & Harrison, A. (2017). Using mobile devices for learning in clinical settings: A mixed-methods study of medical student, physician and patient perspectives [Article]. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 48(1), 176-190. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12352>
- Soleymani, S. A., Goudarzi, S., Anisi, M. H., Jindal, A., Kama, N., & Ismail, S. A. (2023). A Privacy-Preserving Authentication Scheme for Real-Time Medical Monitoring Systems [Article]. *Ieee Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 27(5), 2314-2322. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jbhi.2022.3143207>
- Spencer, K., Sanders, C., Whitley, E. A., Lund, D., Kaye, J., & Dixon, W. G. (2016). Patient Perspectives on Sharing Anonymized Personal Health Data Using a Digital System for Dynamic Consent and Research Feedback: A Qualitative Study [Article]. *Journal of Mebehaviouralnet Research*, 18(4), Article e66. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.5011>
- Steelman, K. S., Tislar, K. L., Ureel, L. C., & Wallace, C. (2016). Breaking digital barriers: A social-cognitive approach to improving digital literacy in older adults. In *HCI International 2016—Posters' Extended Abstracts: 18th International Conference, HCI International 2016, Toronto, Canada, July 17-22, 2016, Proceedings, Part I 18* (pp. 445-450). Springer International Publishing.
- Sweigart, A. (2015). *Automate the Boring Stuff with Python: Practical Programming for Total Beginners*.
- Tian, J., & Li, H. (2023). Social networks and the mental health among Chinese older adults: the mediating role of loneliness and moderating role of Internet use [Article]. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, Article 1242356. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1242356>
- Trott, C. D., Weinberg, A. E., Frame, S. M., Jean-Pierre, P., & Even, T. L. (2024). Civic science education for youth-driven water security: A behavioral development approach to strengthening climate resilience [Article]. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 48(2), 145-155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01650254231188661>

Tsai, H. Y. S., Shillair, R., & Cotten, S. R. (2017). Social support and “playing around” an examination of how older adults acquire digital literacy with tablet computers. *Journal of Applied Gerontology*, 36(1), 29-55.

Tupasela, A., Clavijo, J. D., Salokannel, M., & Fink, C. (2023a). Older people and the smart city-Developing inclusive practices to protect and serve a vulnerable population [Review]. *Internet Policy Review*, 12(1), 45-45. <https://doi.org/10.14763/2023.1.1700>

Tupasela, A., Clavijo, J. D., Salokannel, M., & Fink, C. (2023b). Older people and the smart city-Developing inclusive practices to protect and serve a vulnerable population [Review]. *Internet Policy Review*, 12(1), 45-45. <https://doi.org/10.14763/2023.1.1700>

Wigham, S., Kaner, E., Bourne, J., Ahmed, K., & Hackett, S. (2023). Public mental health and well-being interventions delivered by allied health professionals (AHPs): mapping the evidence and identification of gaps. A systematic review [Review]. *Journal of Public Mental Health*, 22(4), 216-229. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jpmh-04-2023-0033>

Xie, Z., & Or, C. K. (2023). Consumers' Preferences for Purchasing mHealth Apps: Discrete Choice Experiment [Article]. *Jmir Mhealth and Uhealth*, 11, Article e25908. <https://doi.org/10.2196/25908>

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